

A SEARCH FOR ENVIRONMENTALLY DRIVEN STAR FORMATION IN
NEARBY GALAXY CLUSTERS

by
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Contents

1	Introduction	1
1.1	Morphological Classification of Galaxies	1
1.1.1	The Hubble System	2
1.1.2	The Revised Hubble System	3
1.1.3	The Yerkes System	3
1.1.4	The DDO System	4
1.1.5	Limitations of the Hubble System	4
1.2	Measuring the Star Formation Rate in Galaxies	5
1.3	Galaxy Clusters: Basic Properties	6
1.4	Environmental Effects in Cluster Galaxies	7
1.5	Star Formation Properties of Cluster Galaxies	9
1.6	Purpose of Dissertation	13
2	Sample Selection and Data Collection	15
2.1	Cluster Selection	15
2.2	Galaxy Selection	18
2.3	Observations	19
2.4	Image Reductions	20
2.5	Photometry	22
2.6	H α Measurements	29

2.7	Morphologies	35
3	The Relation Between Cluster Substructure and $H\alpha$ Emission in Galaxies	39
3.1	Cluster Selection	39
3.2	Cluster Substructure	40
3.2.1	Multipole Expansion	41
3.2.2	Interpretation of Power Ratios	43
3.3	Measured Power Ratios	44
3.4	Measuring Star Formation in Galaxies	49
3.4.1	Parameterization of Star Formation in Normal Galaxies	53
3.4.2	Definitions of $H\alpha$ Excess and Deficit	60
3.5	Cluster Data	62
3.6	The Nature of the Discordant Galaxies	71
3.6.1	$H\alpha$ Deficient Galaxies	75
3.6.2	$H\alpha$ Excess Galaxies	76
3.7	Summary and Discussion	78
4	An $H\alpha$ Survey of the Hercules Cluster	81
4.1	Cluster Structure and Dynamics	81
4.2	Kitt Peak Observations	84
4.2.1	Image Reductions	86
4.3	Galaxy Selection	86
4.3.1	Notes on HI Detections	88
4.3.2	Broadband Photometry	96
4.3.3	$H\alpha$ Observations	109
4.4	Photometric Results	119
4.4.1	The $H\alpha$ Bright Galaxies	119

4.4.2	The $H\alpha$ Excess Galaxies	122
4.4.3	The Color-Magnitude Diagram	125
4.4.4	$H\alpha$ Deficit Galaxies	131
4.4.5	HI Detections: Basic Properties	131
4.5	The Spatial Distribution of Galaxies	134
4.5.1	Qualitative Impressions	134
4.5.2	Statistical Analysis	139
4.6	Summary	140
5	The Distribution of Star Formation in Hercules Cluster Galaxies	143
5.1	Star Formation Models	144
5.2	Comparison Sample	146
5.2.1	Surface Brightness Extraction	146
5.2.2	Broadband Data	147
5.2.3	$H\alpha$ Data	148
5.2.4	Results for Field Galaxies	148
5.3	Cluster Galaxies	149
5.4	Discussion	159
5.4.1	Type I Profiles	160
5.4.2	Type O Profiles	164
5.4.3	Whence the Steep Slopes?	164
5.5	Summary	165
6	The Nature of the $H\alpha$ Excess Galaxies in the Hercules Cluster	166
6.1	Optical Spectroscopy	166
6.2	Comments on Individual Galaxies	172
6.3	Classification	175
6.3.1	Major Galaxy-Galaxy Interactions	175

6.3.2	Spirals With Disk-Wide Star Formation	176
6.3.3	Compact Galaxies	177
6.3.4	Star Forming S0's	180
6.4	The Color-Magnitude Diagram, Revisited	180
6.5	Local Environment and Possible Triggering Mechanisms	183
6.5.1	Ram Pressure	183
6.5.2	Cluster Tides	184
6.5.3	Minor Interactions or Mergers	186
6.6	Summary	187
7	NGC 3312	188
7.1	Previous Work	188
7.2	Optical Spectroscopy	190
7.2.1	Reductions	190
7.3	Abundance Determination	196
7.3.1	Derived Abundance	199
7.3.2	Expected Abundance	201
7.4	Summary	203
8	Conclusions	204
8.1	Future Work	206

List of Tables

2.1	Basic data for preliminary candidate clusters.	17
2.2	Observing log.	19
2.3	Photometric transformation coefficients.	23
2.4	Results of broad band photometry for cluster galaxies.	26
2.4	Results of broad band photometry for cluster galaxies.	27
2.5	Effective widths and peak transmissions for the narrow band filters.	30
2.6	$H\alpha+N[II]$ Equivalent widths and fluxes for cluster galaxies.	33
2.6	$H\alpha+N[II]$ Equivalent widths and fluxes for cluster galaxies.	34
2.7	Revised Hubble types and concentration indices for the sample galaxies.	37
2.7	Revised Hubble types and concentration indices for the sample galaxies.	38
3.1	Measured power ratios, in units of 10^{-7} . The value for Abell 1656 is from Buote & Tsai (1996).	49
3.2	Median values of $H\alpha+[NII]$ equivalent width for the reference sample as a function of Hubble type.	54
3.3	Fractions of galaxies in the reference, relaxed cluster, and unrelaxed cluster samples showing $H\alpha$ excesses and deficits.	70
3.4	Basic data for the $H\alpha$ excess galaxies.	78

4.1	All $H\alpha$ detections brighter than $B_T = 18.0$	91
4.1	All $H\alpha$ detections brighter than $B_T = 18.0$	92
4.2	All cluster galaxies brighter than $B_T = 18.0$ and known redshifts, but with no $H\alpha$ detections.	93
4.2	All cluster galaxies brighter than $B_T = 18.0$ and known redshifts, but with no $H\alpha$ detections.	94
4.3	All HI detections in the Dickey (1997) survey that fall within the current study area.	95
4.4	Broadband Photometry of bright Abell 2151 $H\alpha$ detected galaxies derived from Kitt Peak data.	102
4.4	Broadband Photometry of bright Abell 2151 $H\alpha$ detected galaxies derived from Kitt Peak data.	103
4.5	Broadband Photometry of bright Abell 2151 galaxies with no $H\alpha$ detections derived from Kitt Peak data.	104
4.5	Broadband Photometry of bright Abell 2151 galaxies with no $H\alpha$ detections derived from Kitt Peak data.	105
4.6	Measured properties of the low surface brightness galaxies.	109
4.7	Central wavelength, effective widths, and peak transmissions for the Kitt Peak narrow band filters.	111
4.8	$H\alpha$ measurements for bright galaxies in Abell 2151.	113
4.8	$H\alpha$ measurements for bright galaxies in Abell 2151.	114
4.9	Basic data for the $H\alpha$ excess galaxies in the Hercules cluster.	126
5.1	Galaxies with centrally condensed $H\alpha$ emission.	156
5.2	Hercules galaxies with steep $R/H\alpha$ surface brightness relations.	162
6.1	Derived fluxes in detected lines, in units of 10^{-15} ergs/sec/cm ²	171
6.2	Derived V band extinctions and redshifts for the observed galaxies.	172

6.3	Effective radii and surface brightnesses for Hercules cluster compact galaxies.	179
7.1	Derived parameters from the line fitting. For all lines except $H\beta$, fluxes are quoted relative to $H\beta$	196

List of Figures

2.1	Comparison of magnitudes and colors determined in this work with those from other sources.	28
2.2	Transmission curves for the narrow band filters used during the observing runs at the Lowell Observatory.	31
3.1	Contour plots of x-ray images for Abell 262, Abell 754, Abell 1367, Abell 2199, and Abell 2151. In each case the lowest contour corresponds to 1.6×10^{-3} counts/sec/Arcmin ²	45
3.1	—Continued	46
3.2	Different power ratios plotted against one another for the clusters considered here.	48
3.3	Relationship between $(B - V)_T^0$ and $H\alpha + [\text{NII}]$ equivalent width for normal galaxies. The galaxies from Kennicutt & Kent (1983) and Romanishin (1990) are plotted as open diamonds, while those from Pogge & Eskridge (1993) are plotted as filled circles.	51
3.4	Relationship between Hubble type and $H\alpha + [\text{NII}]$ equivalent width for normal galaxies. The galaxies from Kennicutt & Kent (1983) and Romanishin (1990) are plotted as open diamonds, while those from Pogge & Eskridge (1993) are plotted as filled circles.	52
3.5	Fit to reference sample color equivalent width relation over plotted on the data.	55

3.6	Plot of r_{phot} versus r_{morp} for reference sample galaxies. The high r_{morph} tail at $r_{phot} \sim 1$ is due to early type galaxies with modest star formation.	56
3.7	Examination of the dependence of r_{phot} and r_{morp} on the $(B - R)_T^0$ colors of the reference sample galaxies.	58
3.8	Examination of the dependence of r_{phot} and r_{morp} on the morphological types of the reference sample galaxies.	59
3.9	Plot of r_{phot} versus r_{morp} for the reference sample galaxies. Galaxies with type Sab and later are plotted as open diamonds, and those with types Sa and earlier are plotted as filled circles.	61
3.10	Relation between $(B - R)_T^0$ color and $H\alpha + [NII]$ equivalent width for the different clusters, overlaid on the data for the reference sample. The reference sample data is plotted as diamonds, while the cluster galaxies are plotted as filled circles.	63
3.11	Relation between Hubble type and $H\alpha + [NII]$ equivalent width for the different clusters, overlaid on the data for the reference sample. The reference sample data is plotted as diamonds, while the cluster galaxies are plotted as filled circles.	64
3.12	Relation between Hubble type and $H\alpha + [NII]$ equivalent width for the more dynamically evolved clusters, overlaid on the data for the reference sample. The reference sample data is plotted as diamonds, while the cluster galaxies are plotted as filled circles.	66
3.13	Relation between Hubble type and $H\alpha + [NII]$ equivalent width for the less dynamically evolved clusters, overlaid on the data for the reference sample. The reference sample data is plotted as diamonds, while the cluster galaxies are plotted as filled circles.	67

3.14	Comparison of the $r_{phot}-r_{morph}$ distribution for the reference sample galaxies, plotted as open diamonds, and the galaxies in relaxed clusters, plotted as filled circles.	68
3.15	Comparison of the $r_{phot}-r_{morph}$ distribution for the reference sample galaxies, plotted as open diamonds, and the galaxies in unrelaxed clusters, plotted as filled circles.	69
3.16	A comparison of the distribution of concentration indices vs. morphological type for a sample of nearby galaxies (open diamonds) and cluster galaxies (closed circles).	74
4.1	Positions of all galaxies brighter than $O = 18.5$ from the APS catalog overlaid with contours of x-ray emission from the ROSAT PSPC for the Hercules cluster.	83
4.2	A comparison of the positions of optically identified substructures with x-ray identified substructures.	85
4.3	Comparison of total B magnitudes measured here with those from RC3 and the Lowell Observatory.	99
4.4	Comparison of total B magnitudes measured here with those from Buta & Corwin (1986).	100
4.5	Comparison of broad band colors measured here with those from other sources. The top panel compares the $(B - R)_T$ colors presented here, with those obtained at the Lowell Observatory. The bottom panel compares the $(B - R)_T$ colors with $(B - V)_T$ colors from RC3. The open symbols are galaxies from the reference sample, while the closed symbols are Hercules cluster galaxies. . .	101
4.6	B band surface brightness profiles of the candidate low surface brightness galaxies detected in HI. The straight lines are the best fit exponential profiles.	108

4.7	Transmission curves for the narrow band filters used during the Kitt Peak observing run.	112
4.8	Comparison of equivalent widths from different sources.	115
4.9	R band (left) and $H\alpha + [NII]$ (right) images of the 20 Hercules galaxies with the highest $H\alpha + [NII]$ fluxes.	116
4.9	—Continued.	117
4.9	—Continued.	118
4.10	Comparison of broadband color and $H\alpha + [NII]$ equivalent width for the galaxies brighter than $B_T = 18.0$ in the Hercules cluster. . .	120
4.11	Comparison of Hubble type and $H\alpha + [NII]$ equivalent width for the galaxies brighter than $B_T = 18.0$ in the Hercules cluster. . . .	121
4.12	The distribution of r_{phot} versus r_{morph} for the Hercules cluster galaxies.	123
4.13	The distribution of r_{phot} versus r_{morph} for the early type (upper panel), and late type (lower panel) Hercules cluster galaxies. . . .	124
4.14	Color magnitude relation for Hercules cluster galaxies.	128
4.15	Color magnitude relation for Hercules cluster galaxies, where the galaxies have now been segregated by morphological type.	130
4.16	The upper panel plots absolute blue magnitude against the galaxies HI mass. The bottom panel shows a plot of central surface brightness versus the HI mass to blue luminosity ratio of the galaxy.	132
4.17	Positions of all galaxies with normal $H\alpha$ emission over-plotted on the x-ray contours.	135
4.18	Positions of all $H\alpha$ non-detections over-plotted on the x-ray contours.	136
4.19	Positions of galaxies with excess $H\alpha$ emission over-plotted on the x-ray contours.	137

4.20	The $H\alpha$ flux from the cluster galaxies, shown in gray-scale, overlaid with contours of the x-ray emission. Both have been smoothed with a Gaussian with $\sigma = 1'$. The area of the cluster depicted is the same as that in the previous three plots.	138
5.1	Plots of R band versus $H\alpha$ surface brightness for galaxies of different morphological types in the field sample of Ryder & Dopita (1994).	150
5.1	—Continued.	151
5.2	Plots of R band versus $H\alpha$ surface brightness for galaxies of different morphological types for the Hercules cluster galaxies.	152
5.2	—Continued.	153
5.2	—Continued.	154
5.2	—Continued.	155
5.2	—Continued.	156
5.3	Histograms of the distributions of slopes for the different samples. The upper panel is for all Hercules cluster galaxies with measurable slopes, and the lower panel is for the galaxies in the sample of Ryder & Dopita (1994).	158
5.4	Examples of galaxies with high inner $H\alpha$ emission, low outer $H\alpha$ emission, and high inner/low outer $H\alpha$ emission. A galaxy with a normal slope is included for comparison.	161
6.1	Spectra of six of the $H\alpha$ excess galaxies in the Hercules cluster. The spectra have been smoothed with a three pixel boxcar to suppress noise. In some cases, residuals of poorly subtracted night sky lines have been repaired.	168
6.1	—Continued.	169
6.1	—Continued.	170

6.2	The color-magnitude diagram for the $H\alpha$ excess galaxies. The solid line is the best fit to the $H\alpha$ non-detections, and the dashed line is the Butcher & Oemler (1984) blue galaxy criteria.	182
6.3	Redshift histograms for the Hercules cluster galaxies with an $H\alpha$ excess (dashed line), and no $H\alpha$ excess (solid line).	185
7.1	Image of NGC 3312 reproduced from the IIIa-J plate of Smith & Weedman (1976). Notice the filaments emerging from the western edge of the disk. The arrow indicates the condensation for which the spectrum was obtained.	191
7.2	R band image of NGC 3312 taken with the 3.6m telescope at La Silla. The arrow indicates the condensation for which the spectrum was obtained.	192
7.3	Continuum subtracted $H\alpha$ image of NGC 3312 obtained with the 1.07m telescope at the Lowell Observatory. Notice the arc of star forming regions along the eastern edge of the disk. The image has been smoothed with a gaussian with $\sigma = 1$ pixel.	193
7.4	Spectrum of the emission line knot in NGC 3312. The spectrum has been interpolated across $\lambda = 5577 \text{ \AA}$, to remove residuals of the strong night sky line at that wavelength.	195
7.5	Calibration of the line ratios $(f_{[OIII]}(4959\text{\AA}) + f_{[OIII]}(5007\text{\AA}))/f_{H\beta}$ and $f_{[OIII]}(5007\text{\AA})/f_{[NII]}(6584\text{\AA})$ as a function of the metallicity of the HII region, from Edmunds & Pagel (1984).	198
7.6	Branch discriminate diagram for extragalactic HII regions. High metal branch objects are plotted as diamonds, while low branch objects are plotted as squares. The value for the NGC 3312 filament is plotted as a filled circle.	200

1 Introduction

Understanding the evolution of galaxies has been one of the central goals of modern astronomy. In its simplest form, galaxy evolution can be divided into two categories, secular and environmental. Secular evolution is change in a galaxy's properties (i.e. star formation or structure) due to the internal properties of the galaxy, such as gas content or mass distribution. Environmental evolution is any change in a galaxy's properties due to external causes, such as tidal interaction with other galaxies, accretion of gas from external sources, or removal of gas from the galaxy due to some external agent. It has become clear in the last 15 years that for galaxies in some environments, external sources of evolution are an important, and perhaps dominant source of the presently observed properties of these galaxies. One prime example of galaxies for which the environment seems to play an important role are galaxies that reside in rich clusters of galaxies.

Although we now have ample evidence that the galaxy cluster environment is affecting the evolution of cluster galaxies, the exact nature of the environmental effects that occur are still not well understood. This dissertation focuses on the effect of the cluster environment on the rate at which cluster galaxies are currently forming stars, compared to comparable galaxies in less dense environments.

1.1 Morphological Classification of Galaxies

The study of the star formation properties of cluster galaxies has traditionally depended upon knowing the morphological type of the galaxies being studied. For this reason a brief review of the common morphological classification systems in

use today is warranted. Particular note should be made of the similarities and differences between the criteria used by the different morphological systems.

1.1.1 The Hubble System

The first widely used system for morphologically classifying galaxies was developed by Hubble (1926, 1936), and later revised by Sandage (1961). The Hubble system divides galaxies into two basic classes, ellipticals and spirals. Elliptical galaxies (denoted with the symbol E) show a sharp central concentration in their light distribution, with a surface brightness that drops smoothly with radius. Besides this central concentration, elliptical galaxies typically show little other structural detail.

There are two distinct visible structural features common to spiral galaxies, a thin flat disk, and a central spheroidal bulge, which is similar in characteristics to a small elliptical galaxy. Spiral galaxies are further classified based on whether the galaxy has a central bar or not. Non-barred galaxies are denoted as S, while barred galaxies are denoted as SB. Spiral galaxies can be further divided into types, based on three criteria: the tightness of winding of the spiral arms, the degree to which the arms can be resolved into bright, young stars, and the relative prominence of the bulge as compared to the disk. In field galaxies it has been found that these separate properties are well correlated, in the sense that galaxies with the most open and well resolved arms have the smallest bulge to disk ratio, while galaxies with the most tightly wound arms also have the least well resolved arms and largest bulge to disk ratios. The different subtypes in the spiral sequence are denoted a,b,c,d; with Sa galaxies having the most tightly wound and poorly resolved arms, and Sd galaxies having the least tightly wound and most resolved arms.

Later revisions of the Hubble system by Hubble and Sandage also include an intermediate type between elliptical and spiral galaxies, denoted as S0 galaxies.

Like spiral galaxies, S0 galaxies have both a disk and a bulge, but in S0 galaxies the disk is relatively featureless, and shows no signs of either spiral arms or bright young stellar associations.

Many observational studies over the years have demonstrated that there is correlation between the current level of star formation in a galaxy and the Hubble type of a galaxy. Elliptical and S0 galaxies have little or no current star formation, and the level of star formation increases along the spiral sequence from little star formation in galaxies of type Sa, to higher levels at the later types of Sc and Sd.

1.1.2 The Revised Hubble System

De Vaucouleurs (1959) noted that galaxies show a much greater range of morphological features than is denoted by the original Hubble system. Because of this, he proposed a revision of the Hubble system that incorporated more classes. Transitional types were introduced, especially along the spiral sequence (e.g. S0a, Sab, etc.). An additional class for galaxies of intermediate bar strength was introduced, and the notation changed so that non-barred galaxies were denoted as SA, barred galaxies were denoted as SB, and galaxies with bars of intermediate strength were denoted as SAB. Additional notation was also introduced to describe the shape of a galaxy's arms, and the presence of any rings in the galaxy.

1.1.3 The Yerkes System

Noting the close connection between the stellar populations and forms of nearby galaxies, Morgan (1958) developed a morphological system devised to exploit this correlation. The fundamental parameter of Morgan's system is the degree of central concentration of the galaxy's light. Secondary parameters of the classification scheme are the form family of the galaxy, (e.g. spiral, barred spiral, etc.) and the inclination class of the galaxy.

1.1.4 The DDO System

Because of the classification criteria it uses, the Hubble type of a galaxy depends both on its structural properties (bulge to disk ratio) and its star formation properties (degree of resolution of spiral arms into stars). For field galaxies, these different parameters are fairly well correlated, so that both criteria give about the same classification for a given galaxy. Van den Bergh (1976) noted that there were some galaxies, which seemed to occur preferentially in clusters, that had small bulge to disk ratios, but rather anemic star formation. This meant that these galaxies do not fit naturally into the Hubble scheme. Because of this, Van den Bergh proposed a new classification system that explicitly separated the structural properties of disk galaxies from their star formation properties, a system commonly referred to as the DDO system (DDO stands for David Dunlap Observatory, the institution at which Van den Bergh developed the morphological system).

In the DDO system, the subtypes a-c were retained, but used to refer only to the bulge to disk ratio. The current state of star formation of galaxy was denoted by the symbols S0, A, and S; S0 galaxies having no current disk star formation, A (for anemic galaxies) having weak disk star formation, while and S having the highest levels of disk star formation.

1.1.5 Limitations of the Hubble System

The Hubble classification system is the most commonly used morphological system. In terms of studying the properties of cluster galaxies however, the Hubble system has a few drawbacks. The first is suggested by the inspiration for Van den Bergh's (1976) DDO system; there seem to be a class of disk galaxies that occur preferentially in clusters that are not well described by the Hubble system for spiral galaxies. This leads to a problem where different observers have assigned

radically different Hubble types to these galaxies, presumably due to different observers giving different weights to the classification criteria of arm properties or bulge to disk ratio when determining a galaxy's type. Note that this is a difficulty inherent to the Hubble scheme. The only remedy is to use another morphological system, such as the Yerkes or DDO system instead, which may not suffer from this difficulty.

A second problem with the use of the Hubble system involves the disparity between the distances to most galaxy clusters, and the galaxies that were used to define the Hubble system. The Hubble system was defined using relatively nearby galaxies, which allowed classification based upon what could be seen in these galaxies at relatively high spatial resolution. Most clusters are at much greater distances than the galaxies used to define the Hubble system. The corresponding reduction in spatial resolution means that the Hubble classification criteria for spirals of arm resolution and tightness of winding are often difficult to utilize for cluster galaxies. Therefore the Hubble types of cluster galaxies rely more and more heavily on the bulge to disk ratio in progressively more distant clusters.

1.2 Measuring the Star Formation Rate in Galaxies

Because only the most nearby galaxies are resolvable into individual stars, information about the star formation rate for most galaxies is obtained from their integrated spectra. The current star formation rate is most easily traced by the short lived, high mass, main sequence stars that radiate most of their energy in the blue and ultra-violet parts of the spectrum. This means that the flux in a galaxy's spectrum in the blue or ultra-violet gives a measure of the rate of massive star formation in the galaxy. Because star forming galaxies contain significant amounts of neutral hydrogen, ultra-violet photons with wavelengths less than $912 \text{ \AA}$ do not

escape the galaxy. Instead these photons are captured as they ionize the hydrogen, which later re-radiates the energy of the ultra-violet photon at longer wavelengths as the hydrogen atom recombines. This means that hydrogen recombination lines are also direct measures of the current rate of star formation. The most commonly used emission line for estimating the star formation rate in galaxies is the Balmer $H\alpha$ line.

1.3 Galaxy Clusters: Basic Properties

Galaxies are not spread evenly throughout the universe; rather they tend to clump together in groups with various numbers of members. A typical galaxy is a member of a group that contains from a few to a few tens of galaxies. Galaxies found in groups like these represent the majority of high surface brightness galaxies in the universe and will be referred to in this dissertation as field galaxies. A few percent of the galaxies in the universe reside in the richest of these groups, which are called clusters of galaxies. A typical rich cluster of galaxies will contain hundreds or even thousands of galaxies within a radius of $1-2h^{-1}$ Mpc ($h = H_0/100\text{km/s/Mpc}$). Clusters of galaxies probably represent the largest structures in the universe that have had a chance to virialize.

Measurements of the line of sight velocity dispersions of galaxy clusters yield values in the range 300-1300 km/sec (Zabludoff, Huchra, & Geller 1990). Clusters of galaxies have been found to be bright sources of x-ray emission, with typical luminosities in the range 10^{43-45} ergs/sec (for a review of cluster x-ray emission, see Sarazin [1988]). X-ray spectral measurements show that the x-ray emission is due to bremsstrahlung in a hot ($T \sim 10^{7-8}$ K) tenuous ($n \sim 10^{-3}\text{cm}^{-3}$) plasma that permeates the cluster. Analysis of velocity data, as well as x-ray data, suggests that the gravitating mass in clusters must greatly exceed the mass accounted for by the luminous material in the clusters (i.e. galaxies + x-ray gas).

Comparison of the morphological mix of galaxies in low redshift rich clusters with the field shows that clusters tend to be populated mainly by spheroid dominated galaxies (ellipticals and S0's), while the dominant population in the field are disk systems (spirals) (Gisler 1980; Dressler 1980a).

1.4 Environmental Effects in Cluster Galaxies

The high galaxy density, hot intra-cluster gas, and inferred large gravitating masses of galaxy clusters are all possible agents that can alter a galaxy's star formation history.

The presence of a hot intra-cluster medium (ICM) in clusters suggests the possibility that cluster galaxies that are rich in cool gas (i.e. spirals) can have their star formation altered by motion through and contact with the hot gas. Gunn & Gott (1972) suggested that cluster spirals should have their interstellar medium (ISM) stripped via ram pressure as the galaxy passed through the ICM. In Gunn & Gott's picture, the removal of the ISM would lead to significantly reduced star formation in the spiral, transforming the galaxy into an S0. The condition for ram pressure to effectively strip material from a galaxy's disk is

$$\rho_{icm}v^2 \geq 2\pi G\sigma_{grav}\sigma_{ism} \quad (1.1)$$

where ρ_{icm} is the mass density of the ICM, v is the component of the galaxy's velocity with respect to the ICM perpendicular to the galaxy's disk, σ_{grav} is the surface density of gravitating matter in the disk of the galaxy, and σ_{ism} is the surface density of the galaxy's ISM. Dressler & Gunn (1983) have suggested that ram pressure may temporarily compress a galaxy's ISM, and thus increase the rate of star formation, before the ISM of the galaxy is swept away.

Observations of pairs of galaxies show that, as a population, paired galaxies have elevated rates of star formation as measured by the galaxies' $H\alpha$ emission (Kennicutt, Keel, Van Der Hulst, Hummel, & Roettiger 1987), presumably

triggered by tidal interactions between the galaxies. Tidal interactions can also remove material from galaxies (Richstone 1975), which may over the long term diminish a galaxy's capacity for forming stars. Traditionally the effectiveness of galaxy-galaxy interactions for triggering star formation in cluster galaxies has been questioned, since the high velocity dispersions in clusters suggests that most encounters should occur with a high relative velocity, which should have little effect on the interacting galaxies (see e.g. Bothun & Dressler 1986).

The large concentration of mass inferred to be in cluster centers means that the tidal field due to the cluster as a whole may also be an effective agent in stripping material from the outer parts of galaxies that wander too close to the cluster center (Meritt 1983). N-body calculations of the effect of the tidal field on a disk orbiting in the cluster suggest that the structure of the galaxy will be altered as the disk is stretched by the cluster's tidal field, and may even lead to the thickening of the galaxy's disk (Byrd & Valtonen, 1990; Valluri 1993; Henriksen & Byrd 1996). Byrd & Valtonen (1990) have suggested that the tidal effect of the cluster may lead to enhanced nuclear star formation and nuclear activity in cluster disk galaxies, since they see a significant amount of gas flow into the center of their simulated galaxies.

Recently the question of what effect the high velocity encounters common in galaxy clusters would have on the evolution of disk galaxies has been reexamined (Moore, Katz, Lake, Dressler, & Oemler 1996; Moore, Lake, & Katz 1997). Based on models of disk galaxies orbiting in a cluster potential along with a population of perturber particles representing other cluster galaxies, Moore et al. (1996) find that high speed encounters, working in concert with the effects of the cluster potential, can drive the evolution (on the time-scales of 3-5 Gyr) of disk systems towards spheroid dominated systems, while at the same time stripping stars and gas from the galaxy. They coin the term "galaxy harassment" to distinguish this mechanism of multiple high speed encounters, which should be common in rich

clusters, from the more familiar low speed damaging encounters that occur in less dense galaxy environs.

1.5 Star Formation Properties of Cluster Galaxies

The fact that early type galaxies predominate in clusters means that overall, the current level of star formation in cluster galaxies is less than that in field galaxies. A more subtle and interesting problem is whether cluster galaxies of a particular type have enhanced, normal, or reduced star formation compared to similar field galaxies. This question has received much interest over the years, because of the diverse mechanisms that can operate in clusters, and may potentially trigger or truncate the star formation in cluster galaxies.

The impetus for Van den Bergh (1976) to develop the DDO system was the existence of spirals that he characterized as anemic, which occur preferentially in clusters. Van den Bergh suggested that these galaxies were systems that had their star forming disks truncated due to ram pressure stripping of their interstellar medium. $H\alpha$ observations of spiral galaxies in the Virgo Cluster by Kennicutt (1983a) showed a population of spirals that had low $H\alpha$ emission for their type, although their level of emission was normal for their broadband color. This reduction in $H\alpha$ emission was interpreted as being due to gas ablation within the cluster environment. Kennicutt, Bothun, & Schommer (1984) studied the broadband colors and $H\alpha$ emission of spiral galaxies in the clusters Abell 1367, Coma, and Cancer and concluded that the relationship between these parameters for the cluster galaxies was indistinguishable from that for field galaxies.

A great step forward in people's thinking about the star formation properties of cluster galaxies was prompted by Butcher & Oemler (1984), who used broadband color observations of clusters ranging in distance from the nearby Virgo cluster, to

clusters at redshifts of $z \approx 0.5$. Butcher & Oemler demonstrated two important points using this data. The first, and most often quoted, is that the fraction of galaxies significantly bluer than a typical early type galaxy rises from a typical value of 0.03 in low redshift clusters, to a typical value of 0.25 in clusters at redshifts of 0.5. The second result, which is generally not as well known, is that with few exceptions, nearby clusters, even those with high fractions of spiral galaxies, have low blue fractions. This second result again suggested that spiral galaxies in clusters were having their star formation reduced by the cluster environment.

Spectroscopic observations of galaxies in higher redshift clusters showed that many of blue galaxies observed in these clusters had strong Balmer absorption lines (Dressler & Gunn 1983; Couch & Sharples 1987; Dressler & Gunn 1992) that are characteristic of either an actively star forming galaxy that had its star formation truncated 1-2 Gyr ago, or of an early type galaxy that experienced a strong temporary burst of star formation 1-2 Gyr ago. Spectroscopic observations of red members of these same clusters showed that while some of the red galaxies had spectra characteristic of an old, passively evolving stellar population, others had strong Balmer absorption lines, suggesting that these systems were otherwise passively evolving systems that had undergone a burst of star formation 1-2 Gyr ago (Couch & Sharples 1987). Couch & Sharples (1987) called these red galaxies that show evidence for a recent burst of star formation $H\delta$ strong galaxies, because they used the strength of the $H\delta$ absorption line as a indication of past star formation.

Imaging of high redshift clusters with the Hubble Space Telescope (HST) shows that most of the blue cluster galaxies are late type spirals, many of which are interacting, but that the $H\delta$ strong galaxies are predominately elliptical and S0 galaxies, which show few signs of current or past interaction (Dressler, Oemler, Butcher, & Gunn 1994; Couch, Ellis, Sharples, & Smail 1994). The combination of the spectroscopic and imaging results suggest that some mechanism in clusters

must truncate the star formation in late type cluster spirals, and alter them beyond recognition by the current day. Dressler et al. (1994) and Couch et al. (1994) suggest that the high number of blue galaxies in interacting systems means that mergers between these galaxies are converting them to elliptical or S0 galaxies, leading to the greater fraction of early type galaxies in nearby clusters. The scenario for triggering the bursts in the $H\delta$ strong galaxies is not as clear as that for the spirals, since Couch et al. (1994) find little sign that the galaxies are interacting, or that they are merger remnants. This suggests that different mechanisms may be responsible for the blue post starburst and $H\delta$ strong galaxies.

Spectroscopic observations of E and S0 galaxies of modest luminosity ($-20.5 \lesssim M_B \lesssim -16.0$) in the Coma cluster by Caldwell, Rose, Sharples, Ellis, & Bower (1993) turned up a population of red galaxies with strong Balmer absorption lines, similar to the $H\delta$ strong galaxies observed in higher redshift clusters by Couch & Sharples (1987). This suggests that whatever mechanism operates to create $H\delta$ strong galaxies at higher redshift may still be operating today, although with lower amplitude. Caldwell et al. (1993) also found that these $H\delta$ strong galaxies occurred preferentially in a substructure about 2 Mpc to the southwest of the cluster core. Since the strong Balmer absorption lines are indicative of something that occurred 1-2 Gyr in the galaxies' past, and because a typical speed for a cluster galaxy is $1000\text{km/sec} \approx 1\text{Mpc/Gyr}$, this suggests one of two scenarios for the local environment where the event occurred. The first is that the activity could have been triggered further from the cluster center (3-4 Mpc), on the sub-clusters initial in-fall into the main cluster. A second alternative was suggested by Burns, Roettiger, Ledlow, & Klypin (1994), who modeled the merger of a large and small cluster and were able to reproduce the current morphology of the Coma cluster as a system where the smaller cluster had already passed through the center of the main cluster, and was currently emerging on the opposite side. In this picture, the activity was induced when the $H\delta$ strong galaxies were roughly coincident

with the core of the main cluster, possibly due to an interaction with the shock between the intra-cluster medium of the two clusters that occurs during the initial core passage of the smaller group.

The case for Butcher-Oemler type activity in galaxies to be associated with a galaxy's presence in a substructure was strengthened by observations of the cluster Abell 2125 at $z \approx 0.25$ by Owen, Dwarkanath, Smith, Ledlow, Keel, Morrison, Voges, & Burns (1996), who find a population of blue, radio bright, galaxies associated with a substructure 3-4 Mpc from the core of the cluster. Additionally, Wang & Ulmer (1997) have shown that there is a correlation between the blue fraction in Butcher-Oemler clusters and the ellipticity of the cluster x-ray emission on 3 Mpc scales. Since the ellipticity of the x-ray emission presumably reflects the dynamical state of the cluster, such that a higher ellipticity corresponds to the cluster being less dynamically relaxed, this result is suggestive of a connection between Butcher-Oemler type activity and the merging of sub-clusters as clusters grow.

Further imaging and spectroscopic observations of some of the $H\delta$ strong galaxies in Coma were presented by Caldwell, Rose, Franx, & Leonardi (1996). Based on analysis of their imaging and kinematic data for the galaxies, they find that the galaxies have significant disk components, consistent with the hypothesis that the galaxies may have evolved from later type spirals. Analysis of the spatial distribution of color and line strength in these galaxies suggests that the star formation activity was confined to a region of radius a few kilo-parsecs around the core of these systems.

Imaging and spectroscopic observations of additional galaxies in the Coma cluster, as well as for galaxies in four other clusters that were selected largely due to the presence of significant substructure in the cluster, were presented by Caldwell & Rose (1997). They find a significant population of $H\delta$ strong galaxies, and in one cluster, a population of early type galaxies with an excess of current

star formation. Based on their analysis of these clusters, they conclude that star formation is triggered in the $H\delta$ strong galaxies during the initial core crossing as the clusters merge, and not at greater distances from the cluster center.

In summary, the evidence for environmental alteration of the star formation rate in galaxy clusters is mixed. At low redshift, most cluster spiral galaxies seem to have star formation rates indistinguishable from comparable field spirals, although there may be a small population of galaxies with reduced star formation. At higher redshift, cluster spirals seem to show enhanced numbers of interacting systems, with current or recently truncated star formation. Finally, at both high and low redshifts there is a population of early type galaxies that show signs of star-bursts 1-2 Gyr in the past. The morphologies of the $H\delta$ strong galaxies suggest that they are not due to mergers or strong galaxy-galaxy interactions, and thus that they may be produced by a different mechanism than the blue galaxies in Butcher-Oemler clusters.

1.6 Purpose of Dissertation

The purpose of this dissertation is threefold. The first goal is to reexamine the global properties of currently star forming galaxies in nearby clusters, such as morphological type, broadband color, and $H\alpha$ equivalent width, to see whether they show any signs of environmental alteration. A part of this reexamination will be to separately consider clusters in different stages of dynamical evolution, in an attempt to determine whether cluster dynamics as a whole may drive accelerated galaxy evolution.

The second goal of this dissertation is to use a complete $H\alpha$ and broadband survey of the Hercules cluster, which is the best low redshift example of a unrelaxed, spiral rich cluster, in order to search for correlations between an excess of $H\alpha$ emission in galaxies and the presence of the galaxies in sub-clusters within

the cluster. An $H\alpha$ survey has a distinct advantage over earlier studies that used $H\delta$ strong galaxies to study the correlation of enhanced star formation with substructure, since the $H\alpha$ emission reflects the most recent star formation in galaxies, while the $H\delta$ absorption strength is due to star formation 1-2 Gyr in the past. This means that the local environment of an $H\alpha$ excess galaxy reflects as nearly as possible the environment in which the triggering event occurred. This removes the need to try to infer where the galaxy was 1-2 Gyr ago, as is necessary when studying $H\delta$ strong galaxies. In addition, the use of a spatially complete survey will allow a detection of all galaxies that are currently $H\alpha$ emitters, unlike earlier surveys that primarily concentrated on observing spiral galaxies.

The final goal of this dissertation is to use the spatial distribution of $H\alpha$ emission within individual Hercules cluster galaxies, in an attempt to constrain the nature of the interaction giving rise to the enhanced $H\alpha$ emission.

2 Sample Selection and Data Collection

This chapter describes the selection of the cluster and galaxy samples that were observed optically at the Lowell Observatory. Details of the basic image reductions are discussed, and basic data for the observed galaxies are presented.

2.1 Cluster Selection

An initial list of clusters was compiled based upon the morphology of the cluster's x-ray emission. Clusters were selected to represent as wide a range of x-ray morphology as possible, with the hope that the different morphologies would reflect different dynamical states for the clusters. Two sources of x-ray maps were used: the compilation of McMillan, Kowalski, & Ulmer (1989), who presented reprocessed maps from the EINSTEIN database for 49 clusters, and the EINSTEIN Observatory Catalog of IPC X-ray Sources (Harris, Forman, Gioia, Hale, Harneden, Jones, Karakashian, Maccacaro, McSweeney, Primini, Schwarz, Tananbaum, & Thurman 1993). Clusters south of declination -30° were discarded, since they were inaccessible from observatory sites in the northern hemisphere. Clusters were then restricted to have redshifts $z \leq 0.04$, since a typical far-infrared (FIR) bright spiral galaxy will in general not be detected by the Infra-Red Astronomical Satellite (IRAS) at distances greater than that. The clusters that met this criteria are given in Table 2.1 along with the Right Ascension and Declination of the cluster center (from Abell 1958), the redshift of the cluster (from the compilation of Andersen & Owen (1994)), and the two point correlation coefficient for each cluster

(B_{gg}), which is a measure of the cluster's richness (Andersen 1992; Andersen & Owen 1994). The two point correlation function, $\xi = B_{gg}r^{-1.8}$, measures the overdensity of galaxies within a certain volume. If the average number density of galaxies in the universe is n_o , the number of galaxies within a radius of a certain point can be written as $N = (4\pi/3)n_or^3 + 3.33\pi n_o B_{gg}r^{1.2}$. The first term is just the expected number of galaxies within that radius, so the second term is just the excess number of galaxies within that volume. Thus, B_{gg} is a direct measure of the richness of an aggregation of galaxies.

The list was further restricted to clusters where most of the brighter cluster members had measured redshifts, in order to ensure that most galaxies of interest had known velocities, and thus that the correct narrow band filter was selected to observe the galaxy. Preference was given to clusters with redshifts near the center of the available $H\alpha$ filters. This strategy allowed, where possible due to proximity on the sky, the imaging of multiple targets on a single frame. Clusters that have been extensively studied by other workers were avoided. A final constraint was due to the actual observing dates. Fortunately this constraint was not too stringent, given the times of the two observing runs (April and November). The results of all these selections led to the observing of three primary clusters (Abell 262, 569, and 2151), as well as a few galaxies in Abell 1367.

Table 2.1. Basic data for preliminary candidate clusters.

Cluster	$\alpha(1950.0)$	$\delta(1950.0)$	z	B_{gg}
S49-147	00 15.7	22 14	0.020	54
Abell 194	01 23.0	-01 46	0.0179	260
Abell 262	01 49.9	35 54	0.0161	146
Abell 400	02 55.0	05 50	0.0232	170
Abell 426	03 13.5	41 21	0.0183	378
Abell 569	07 05.6	48 42	0.0196	138
Abell 1185	11 08.1	28 57	0.0326	351
Abell 1314	11 32.1	49 19	0.0341	290
Abell 1367	11 41.9	20 07	0.0215	542
Virgo	12 24.0	13 00	0.0040	260
Abell 2052	15 14.3	07 12	0.0348	173
Abell 2063	15 20.6	08 49	0.0337	540
Abell 2147	16 00.0	16 02	0.0352	349
Abell 2151	16 03.0	17 53	0.0371	426
Abell 2199	16 26.9	39 38	0.0303	635
Abell 2634	23 35.8	26 45	0.0312	216

2.2 Galaxy Selection

An initial list of galaxies in each cluster was extracted from the University of Minnesota’s Automatic Plate Scanner (APS) catalog (Pennington, Humphries, Odewahn, Zumach, & Thurmes 1993). The APS catalog results from scans of copies of the first Palomar Sky Survey plates. All detected objects were classified as either stars or galaxies by a neural network (Odewahn, Stockwell, Pennington, Humphries, & Zumach 1992). Crude photometry for the objects is also presented in the catalog. In order to set a magnitude limit for galaxies in each cluster, a rough calibration between the blue (O) magnitudes in the APS catalog and the Johnson B band was derived by fitting a linear relation between the B_T magnitudes of the Third Reference Catalog of Bright Galaxies (RC3; de Vaucouleurs, de Vaucouleurs, Corwin, Buta, Paturel, & Fouqué 1991) and the APS magnitudes for galaxies in Abell 2151. Using this calibration, galaxies were selected in each cluster down to an approximate absolute magnitude of $B_T = -17.9$. This limit was selected by examining the B band luminosity function for Virgo cluster spirals (Sandage, Binggeli, & Tammann 1985). This limit, which is one half magnitude dimmer than the median value found by Sandage et al. should net most spirals of morphological types Sa through Sc, but will catch only the brightest of types Sd and Sm.

In order to target galaxies that are currently actively forming stars, data from the IRAS (Beichman, Neugebauer, Habing, Clegg, & Chester 1988) database was coadded in the 60 and 100 micron bands for each of the APS galaxies. The NASA Extra-galactic Database (NED)¹ was then searched to determine whether a redshift had previously been measured for the IRAS detected galaxies, for use in

¹The NASA/IPAC Extra-galactic Database (NED) is operated by the Jet Propulsion Laboratory, California Institute of Technology, under contract with the National Aeronautics and Space Administration.

Table 2.2. Observing log.

Date (1995)	Comments
April 26	Cirrus
April 27	Cirrus
April 28	Photometric
November 20	Cirrus
November 21	Cirrus
November 22	Photometric
November 23	Mostly photometric, some cirrus late?

narrow band filter selection. Target galaxies in the primary clusters were then prioritized based on the IRAS flux density at 60 microns, where galaxies were observed in order of decreasing flux density. Individual exceptions to this procedure were exercised in cases where the galaxy had no measured velocity, or when the cataloged velocity made that galaxy clearly unsuitable for the available narrow band filters.

2.3 Observations

Observations were carried out using the Lowell Observatory's 1.07m Hall reflector with a Loral 800² CCD at the telescope's f/8 focus. The output of the CCD was binned 2×2 on readout in order to reduce read noise, yielding a pixel size of 0.706 arcseconds; thus the useful field of view of each observation was about 4.5 arcminutes. A log of the observing conditions for each night is given in Table 2.2.

During the observing run of April 1995, B, R and $H\alpha$ +[N II] images were obtained for galaxies in the clusters Abell 1367 and Abell 2151. The nights that were not photometric were used to obtain the $H\alpha$ +[N II] images with accompanying R band images for use in continuum subtraction. Typical integration times were 30 minutes for the narrow band images and 10 minutes for the continuum images.

The photometric night of the run was used to obtain photometrically calibrated B and R images of galaxies previously observed in $H\alpha+[N II]$. Typical integration times for these observations were 10 minutes in B and 5 minutes in R.

During the November 1995 run, B, R, and $H\alpha+[N II]$ images were obtained for galaxies in Abell 262 and Abell 569. The procedure was similar to that used in the April run, with narrow band and accompanying continuum images taken on unphotometric nights, with typical integration times of 30 minutes and 10 minutes respectively. B and R images were collected during the photometric nights, with respective typical integration times of 15 and 5 minutes.

2.4 Image Reductions

All frames were reduced in a standard way. First the bias level was removed from each frame. Second, all frames were flat fielded, and finally, cosmic rays were removed.

All frames had their bias level removed in a 2-step process. First, a master bias frame was subtracted from each image, in order to remove pixel to pixel variations in the bias level. The master bias frame was constructed for each night's data from 20 bias frames that were collected at the beginning of the night's observing. The master frame is the result of averaging the 20 individual frames using a sigma clipping algorithm, to eliminate any cosmic rays from the averaging procedure. In order to account for any slow drift in the bias level throughout the night, the over-scan region of the CCD was fit with a low order polynomial, and this fit was subtracted from the images after the subtraction of the master bias frame.

Flat fielding of the images was also a multi-step process, consisting of flattening first with dome flats, and then in some instances, with sky flats. Dome flats were collected at the beginning of each night's observing for each filter. In the case of the broad band filters, ten individual dome flats were collected in each

filter, which were combined in a manner similar to that used for the bias frames. For the narrow band filters, 5 frames in each filter were collected and combined in the same manner. Data frames were then divided by the appropriate flat field image, which was first normalized by the mean pixel value in that flat. This procedure successfully removed all high frequency gain variations in the images. In certain nights' data, however, there remained some low spatial frequency structure. In these cases, the data frames were divided by sky flats, which removed this structure. The method of construction of the sky flat images varied between the different observing runs, and is discussed for each below.

During the April 1995 observing run, sky flats were constructed using a set of 6 images taken during times of fairly heavy cloud cover. The position of the telescope was shifted by a few arcminutes between each exposure. The images were first flattened with the dome flats, then combined using the sigma clipping algorithm. A surface was fit to the resulting image, in order to extract only the structure of low spatial frequency. This fit to the image (properly normalized of course) was used as the sky flat image for all the nights during the April run that required a sky flat (nights one and three).

For the fall 1995 run, a somewhat different procedure for constructing sky flats was followed. In this case, the flats were constructed from the entire set of data frames. All data frames were bias subtracted and flat fielded using the dome flats. Because of the natural propensity for placing the observed galaxy in the center of the CCD, removal of the galaxies from the observed frames was necessary in many of the frames before they were combined. This was achieved by fitting a surface across the galaxy area for each observation where the galaxy was near the center of the chip, and replacing the pixel values in that area with the fit values. After this, all the data frames in each filter for all four nights were combined into a single master sky flat for that filter using the sigma clipping algorithm. All data frames were then divided by the properly normalized flat field.

To check whether there were night to night variations in the flat field structure that would be missed by this procedure, flats for each night in the R band were constructed in the same manner as the master sky flats. Comparison of these individual flats showed no variation in structure over the four nights of the run. Another possible problem with the above procedure is that any structure in the sky flats that existed near the center of the chip would not be recovered. In order to check this, frames that had no galaxies near the chip center were examined, and no significant structure was found.

After flat fielding, cosmic rays were removed from all data frames. First, candidate cosmic rays were identified interactively using the IRAF task COSMICRAYS. This list of candidates was then removed from the image by fitting a surface to the pixels in an annulus surrounding the cosmic ray, and replacing the pixel values for the cosmic rays with the fit values. Comparison of the image before and after cleaning was used to verify that no cosmic rays had been missed, and that those that had been replaced had been replaced in an appropriate manner. In the few cases where the original replacement was inadequate, the procedure was re-applied, with appropriate changes in parameters.

2.5 Photometry

On all nights that were photometric, standard star fields from the compilation of Christian, Adams, Barnes, Butcher, Hayes, Mould, & Seigel (1985) were observed in order to put the observations on the standard system defined by Landolt (1983). Transformation to the standard system was achieved via the following set of equations:

$$(B - R) = a_1((b - r) - k_{BR}X + a_2) \quad (2.1)$$

$$B = b - k_B X + c_1 + c_2(B - R) \quad (2.2)$$

Table 2.3. Photometric transformation coefficients.

Date (1995)	a_1	a_2	c_1	c_2
April 28	0.883	-0.164	27.726	-0.094
November 22	1.127	-0.499	27.628	-0.002
November 23	1.057	-0.456	27.639	-0.003

where X is the airmass of the observation, and a_i and c_i are constants whose values are determined using the standard stars. Upper case letters refer to magnitudes and colors of the objects on the standard system, while lower case letters are magnitudes and colors on the “instrumental” system. The k ’s are extinction coefficients, which were not derived from the observed standard stars, but were instead fixed at the typical values found by Landolt for Kitt Peak (Pilachowski, Landolt, Massey, & Montani 1991), $k_B = 0.240$ and $k_{BR} = 0.130$. Fitted values for the coefficients in the transformation equations are given in Table 2.3, and are appropriate for integration times of 10 minutes in B and 5 minutes in R .

Magnitudes and colors for the galaxies were extracted in such a way as to put them on the total magnitude and color system of the RC3. These magnitudes and colors were then converted to the corrected face on system as prescribed in RC3 with the following exceptions. Since RC3 gives k-corrections in the U, B, and V bands only, the k-corrections given by Coleman, Wu, & Weedman (1980) were used instead. Axis ratios for the galaxies were derived by fitting ellipses to each galaxy’s isophotes in the B band. Because the imaging of the galaxies was not very deep, axis ratios were determined at the 23.5 magnitude per square arcsecond isophote, as opposed to the 25 magnitude per square arcsecond isophote as in RC3. Comparison of the axis ratios derived at this level with those tabulated in RC3 shows generally good agreement between the values derived at the different surface brightness levels. Color excesses were derived using the interstellar extinction curve of Reike & Lebofsky (1985), following Buta & Crocker (1992). The

foreground extinction due to material within our own galaxy was estimated as in RC3 using the technique of Burstein & Heiles (1984), which uses a combination of the observed HI column density within our galaxy, along with number counts of faint galaxies to derive the extinction and reddening in different directions. The resulting photometry is summarized in Table 2.4. Galaxy identifications are given by their designation in different catalogs. NGC/IC numbers are given for galaxies in the New General Catalog of Non-stellar Astronomical Objects and the accompanying Index Catalog (Dreyer 1888, 1895, 1908), UGC numbers for galaxies in the Uppsala General Catalog of Galaxies (Nilson 1973), CGCG numbers for galaxies in the Catalog of Galaxies and Clusters of Galaxies (Zwicky, Herzog, Karpowicz, Kowal, & Wild 1968), Mrk numbers for galaxies from the lists of Markarian, Lipovetsky, Stapanian, Eratsova, & Shapovalova (1989), and D numbers for galaxies from the morphological catalog of Dressler (1980b).

Uncertainties in the total magnitudes and colors were calculated following the procedure outlined in Newberry (1991) added in quadrature with the RMS of the standard stars around the photometric calibration. These uncertainty values were not tabulated for two reasons. First, because most of the galaxies cover a fairly small range in magnitude, and were observed with the same instrument with similar integration times, the derived uncertainty values spanned a relatively narrow range. Second, the errors calculated represent only internal errors, so are really only suitable as a rough guide to the quality of the photometry. The values for the uncertainties for the photometry obtained in this way were in the range 0.03-0.05 for B_T and 0.02-0.04 for $(B - R)_T$. A comparison of the photometry presented here with photometry from other sources is given in Figure 2.1. The upper panel is a plot of the total blue magnitudes from the RC3 versus those determined here, for galaxies that had available RC3 photometry. The straight line has a slope of one and intercept of zero. The fact that the line represents the distribution of the data well suggests that the photometry presented here has

been successfully transformed to the system used in RC3. The scatter of the data around the line of $\sigma = 0.13$ is what would be expected from the quoted uncertainties from RC3 ($\sigma \approx 0.10 - 0.15$) and in this work ($\sigma \approx 0.03 - 0.05$). The lower panel in Figure 2.1 compares the $(B - V)_T$ colors tabulated in RC3 with $(B - R)_T$ colors. Data from two sources are plotted; the diamonds are galaxies from this study, while the filled circles are galaxies from the $H\alpha$ studies of Kennicutt & Kent (1983) and Romanishin (1990) that had $(B - R)_T$ photometry published in Buta & Williams (1995). In general the data appear to follow the same correlation. There may be a small trend for the $(B - R)_T$ colors in this study to be slight redder at the bluest $(B - V)_T$ colors than the Buta & Williams data, but this perception is based on only a few data points. The scatter for the data in this study around the mean relation seems to be somewhat larger than that in the Buta & Williams study, which is somewhat disappointing, but the degree of scatter is more than adequate for the current purpose.

Table 2.4. Results of broad band photometry for cluster galaxies.

Galaxy	B_T	B_T^0	$(B - R)_T$	$(B - R)_T^0$
<i>Abell 262</i>				
NGC 753	12.91	12.49	1.26	0.78
NGC 688	13.54	13.10	1.16	0.96
NGC 710	14.13	13.82	1.14	0.99
UGC 1385	14.35	14.04	1.08	0.96
CGCG 522-062	15.33	14.80	1.04	0.78
CGCG 522-051	15.49	15.25	1.38	1.28
NGC 759	13.46	13.17	1.64	1.45
NGC 668	13.83	13.50	1.25	1.02
UGC 1460	14.69	14.16	1.62	1.29
<i>Abell 569</i>				
CGCG 234-071	15.49	14.56	1.32	0.84
CGCG 234-056	15.44	14.83	1.05	0.71
CGCG 234-090	15.31	14.24	1.29	0.71
CGCG 234-062	15.53	15.08	1.77	1.51
UGC 3638	14.79	13.92	1.56	1.09
UGC 3706A ^a	16.05	15.33	1.15	0.75
UGC 3706B ^a	16.41	15.61	1.56	1.12
UGC 3724	14.65	14.09	1.19	0.89
<i>Abell 1367</i>				
Mrk 181	14.42	14.14	1.11	0.95
<i>Abell 2151</i>				
NGC 6040A ^a	14.71	14.14	1.35	0.92
NGC 6040B ^a	15.58	15.30	1.63	1.42
NGC 6054	15.89	15.33	1.25	0.82
IC 1182	15.14	14.91	1.55	1.33
D079	16.98	16.75	1.14	1.06
D150	15.60	15.37	1.54	1.32
CGCG 108-108	15.50	15.10	1.12	0.88
CGCG 108-098	15.98	15.58	1.15	0.91

Table 2.4.—Continued

Galaxy	B_T	B_T^0	$(B - R)_T$	$(B - R)_T^0$
IC 1186	15.55	15.08	1.45	1.07
Mrk 299	16.74	16.60	0.95	0.80
IC 1189	15.09	14.86	1.37	1.15
a2151 018	16.29	15.70	1.25	0.91
a2151 088	16.51	15.65	1.39	0.92

^aGalaxies overlapping, total magnitudes uncertain.

Figure 2.1. Comparison of magnitudes and colors determined in this work with those from other sources.

2.6 H α Measurements

Two quantities related to the global H α + [N II] emission were extracted from the observed galaxies. The first is the H α + [N II] equivalent width, which is formally defined as the flux in the emission lines, divided by the flux density of the continuum near the base of the lines,

$$EW(H\alpha + [NII]) = F(H\alpha + [NII])/f(\lambda = 6600\text{\AA}). \quad (2.3)$$

In practice, the continuum is usually estimated using a filter (or filters) that sample the continuum level somewhere in the wavelength range 6000-7500 Å, which is a utilization of the fact that the spectra of most galaxies in this wavelength range is fairly flat, so that the exact wavelength that the continuum is estimated at is not crucial. For this work, the continuum level was estimated using an R band filter. Since the pass band of the R filter includes the lines of interest, the line fluxes will be underestimated by a factor determined by the relative equivalent widths of the R and narrow band filter. For the galaxies studied here, this will be less than 5%, so the tabulated values have not been corrected for this effect.

The exact procedure used to extract the H α + [N II] equivalent widths and fluxes is as follows. The sky level on both the narrow band and R frames was estimated from object free regions in the frame, and the mean sky level was subtracted from both frames. Four or five stars were selected and aperture photometry of these stars was used to derive a relative scale factor between the two frames. The R frame was then scaled to match the continuum level of the narrow band frame using this scale factor. The frames were registered, using the position of stars on both frames, and the scaled R band frame was subtracted from the narrow band frame to create an image that isolated the H α + [N II] emission of the galaxy. This procedure was applied in an iterative fashion, until both the scaling and registration of the R frame was found to be suitable. The H α + [N II] equivalent width

Table 2.5. Effective widths and peak transmissions for the narrow band filters.

λ_{center} (Å)	W_{eff} (Å)	T_{peak}
6563	71.3	0.600
6600	61.5	0.620
6675	62.8	0.612
6825	61.0	0.624

was then estimated for each galaxy using the formula

$$EW(H\alpha + [NII]) = W_{eff}(T_{peak}/T_{\lambda})(N_{H\alpha+[NII]}/N_{Rscale}). \quad (2.4)$$

W_{eff} is the effective width of the appropriate narrow band filter, which is defined as the width that a rectangular filter would have that would pass the same amount of continuum as the narrow band filter, if the rectangular filter had the same peak transmission of the narrow band filter. $N_{H\alpha+[NII]}$ is the number of ADU in the line image, and N_{Rscale} is the number in the scaled R band image. T_{peak} is the peak transmission of the filter, and T_{λ} is the transmission of the filter at the wavelength of $H\alpha$, redshifted appropriately for the galaxy in question. Values of W_{eff} and T_{peak} for the filters used in this work are given in Table 2.5, and the transmission curves are plotted in Figure 2.2.

Since most of the narrow band data was collected under non-photometric conditions, calibration of the $H\alpha+[NII]$ fluxes was accomplished by bootstrapping from the R band photometry collected on photometric nights.

The derived values of the equivalent widths and $H\alpha + [NII]$ fluxes are given in Table 2.6. Most of the galaxies listed have redshifts that put $H\alpha$ near the center of the narrow band filter used to observe them (i.e. on the “top” of the filter). However in a few cases, galaxies were observed whose redshift put them on the wings of the filter, but were still sufficiently strong $H\alpha$ emitters to be easily detected. Values are listed in the table for these galaxies, with a correction for

Figure 2.2. Transmission curves for the narrow band filters used during the observing runs at the Lowell Observatory.

the transmission of the filter at the galaxies redshift applied. Galaxies that had redshifts that put them on the wings of the filter are marked in the table, and though tabulated, were not used in any of the analysis presented in the following chapter.

Formal uncertainties for the equivalent widths and fluxes were calculated, and generally found to be in the range 5-15%. Because there may be systematic uncertainties that, particularly in the case of the fluxes, exceed those of the formal errors, the formal errors for the galaxies are not tabulated. For reference, the expected uncertainties in the equivalent widths are probably in the range 10-20%. The uncertainties in the fluxes are probably higher, in part due to the boot strapping from the broadband photometry to establish the flux scale. The expected uncertainties in the fluxes are around 20%, but may be as high as 50%. For comparison, one galaxy in each observing run of this study was observed that had been previously observed by other workers. Markarian 181 of the spring run was previously observed by Kennicutt, Bothun, and Schommer (1984), who found an equivalent width for the galaxy of $102\text{\AA}$, where a correction factor of 1.16 has been applied to Kennicutt et al.'s data, as outlined in Romanishin (1990). This is in reasonably good agreement with the value measured here of $116\text{\AA}$, especially considering that the redshift of $H\alpha$ for Mrk 181 lies near the edge of the filter, requiring a relatively large scale factor. The galaxy NGC 753 observed in the fall run was also observed by Romanishin (1990). He found an equivalent width of $29\text{\AA}$, again in good agreement with the value measured here of $33\text{\AA}$.

Table 2.6. $H\alpha+N[II]$ Equivalent widths and fluxes for cluster galaxies.

Galaxy	EW($H\alpha+NII$) ($\text{\AA}$)	$-\log(F(H\alpha + NII))$ (ergs/s/cm ²)
<i>Abell 262</i>		
NGC 753	33	11.79
NGC 688	22	12.26
NGC 710	34	12.33
UGC 1385	33	12.44
CGCG 522-062	6	14.00
CGCG 522-051	12	13.21
NGC 759	4	12.77
NGC 668	21	12.36
UGC 1460	2	13.57
<i>Abell 569</i>		
UGC 3706A	34	13.08
UGC 3706B	17	13.36
UGC 3638	10	12.94
UGC 3724	19	12.75
CGCG 234-056	43	12.77
CGCG 234-071	36	12.76
CGCG 234-090	25	12.86
CGCG 234-062	2	13.85
<i>Abell 1367</i>		
Mrk 181 ^a	116	11.91
<i>Abell 2151</i>		
NGC 6040A	14	13.20
NGC 6040B	14	13.45
NGC 6054	27	13.07
IC 1182 ^a	29	12.62
D079	48	13.30
D150	42	12.65
CGCG 108-108 ^a	19	13.12
CGCG 108-098	26	13.16

Table 2.6.—Continued

Galaxy	EW(H α +NII) ($\text{\AA}$)	$-\log(F(\text{H}\alpha + \text{NII}))$ (ergs/s/cm ²)
IC 1186	4	13.69
Mrk 299	38	13.38
IC 1189	16	12.93
a2151 018	38	13.08
a2151 088	26	13.28

^aH α +NII near edge of filter, uncertainty of EW and flux high.

2.7 Morphologies

Morphological information for the sample galaxies was obtained by two different methods. First, morphological types in the Revised Hubble System were found for each galaxy. The primary source of the morphological classifications was RC3. For galaxies that did not appear in RC3, morphological types were estimated by inspection of the B band images that had been obtained for each galaxy.

Second, concentration indices for each galaxy were measured using the technique of Doi, Fukugita, & Okamura (1993), with some of the modifications to the method suggested by Abraham, Valdes, Yee & Van den Bergh (1994). The basis of the Doi et al. (1993) technique is to characterize the central concentration of light of a galaxy by taking the ratio of the flux in an aperture centered on the galaxy to that in an annulus outside the central aperture. The radius of the inner aperture is chosen to be a fixed factor of the outer radius of the annulus (typically 0.3 times the outer radius). The outer radius of the annulus is selected to correspond to a selected surface brightness level. In practice the radius of the outer annulus r (measured in pixels) is determined from the condition

$$N = \pi r^2 \tag{2.5}$$

where N is the number of pixels in the galaxy image with a surface brightness that exceeds the surface brightness threshold. Rather than select a fixed surface brightness, Abraham et al. selected their surface brightness level to be a certain amount above the noise level in the background of the image. Following this work, a surface brightness level corresponding to a level of 2σ above the surface brightness of the background was adopted. The R band images were used to determine the concentration indices for the sample galaxies. Both the background level and the σ in the background were determined using galaxy free regions of the galaxy images.

The revised Hubble types and concentration indices for the sample galaxies are given in Table 2.7.

Table 2.7. Revised Hubble types and concentration indices for the sample galaxies.

Galaxy	Morp	CI
	<i>Abell 262</i>	
NGC 753	SABbc	0.545
NGC 688	SABb	0.484
NGC 710	Scd	0.371
UGC 1385	SB0/a	0.591
CGCG 522-062	Sc	0.353
CGCG 522-051	Sc	0.274
NGC 759	E	0.614
NGC 668	Sb	0.567
UGC 1460	Sa	0.469
	<i>Abell 569</i>	
CGCG 234-071	Sbc(pec)	0.356
CGCG 234-056	Sa:	0.486
CGCG 234-090	Sb	0.379
CGCG 234-062	S0/a	0.541
UGC 3638	SBab	0.526
UGC 3706A ^a	Sa	0.382
UGC 3706B ^a	Sa	0.517
UGC 3724	SBb	0.438
	<i>Abell 1367</i>	
Mrk 181	I	0.521
	<i>Abell 2151</i>	
NGC 6040A ^b	SABc	—
NGC 6040B ^b	S0(pec)	—
NGC 6054	SABb	0.446
IC 1182	S0(pec)	0.543
D079	E	0.616
a2151 007	S0	0.593
CGCG 108-098	SABc	0.375

Table 2.7.—Continued

Galaxy	Morp	CI
IC 1186	SBb	0.449
Mrk 299	Sm:	0.489
IC 1189	SB0/a	0.616
a2151 018	Sc	0.606
a2151 088	Sc	0.549

^aThe galaxies in UGC 3706 are interacting, concentration indices are uncertain.

^bThe galaxies in NGC 6040 are overlapping, so no concentration indices were determined for them.

3 The Relation Between Cluster Substructure and $H\alpha$ Emission in Galaxies

In this chapter the question considered is how the star formation properties of cluster galaxies depend on the dynamical state of the cluster. In order to determine the dynamical state of the cluster, x-ray data from the ROSAT PSPC data archive is used, along with a technique developed by Buote & Tsai (1995, 1996) to quantify the amount of substructure in the cluster. The current state of star formation in the cluster galaxies is quantified using $H\alpha$ data. A simple technique is developed to determine whether a galaxy has an excess or deficit of $H\alpha$ emission, compared to a normal, star forming galaxy of the same color or morphological type.

3.1 Cluster Selection

The selection and details of the observations of the clusters for which new data was obtained are described in Chapter 2. Data from the literature was used to form a reference sample, and to augment the data collected at the Lowell Observatory with data for other clusters that have been well observed in $H\alpha$ in the past. The details of the reference sample are given in section 3.4, so will not be discussed any further here. A few comments on the cluster data taken from the literature are appropriate at this point.

The reference sample included many galaxies that are members of the Virgo

cluster. Since the purpose of this work is to compare the properties of cluster and field galaxies, all members of the Virgo cluster were removed from the reference sample. The Virgo cluster is in fact a line of sight superposition of a large cluster and several smaller groups, many of which are at significantly different distances than the main cluster (Tully & Shaya 1984; Binggeli, Tammann, & Sandage 1987; Binggeli, Popescu, & Tammann 1993). In order to isolate the galaxies that are associated with the main condensation of the Virgo cluster for further study (the A cluster in the scheme of Binggeli et al. 1993), the cluster assignments of Binggeli et al. (1993) were used to pick out galaxies that belong to the A cluster. This sample of A cluster galaxies was then used in the analysis as cluster galaxies.

Two other clusters had extensive $H\alpha$ data published, and so were also included in this study, Abell 1367 and Abell 1656 (the Coma cluster). $H\alpha$ observations of galaxies in Abell 1367 and Abell 1656 have been compiled from several sources by Gavazzi, Randone, & Brachini (1995). This compilation was used to construct samples of galaxies in each of these clusters for use in this work.

3.2 Cluster Substructure

The dynamical state of a galaxy cluster is reflected in the spatial and velocity distribution of the cluster constituents that respond to the gravitational potential of the cluster, namely the cluster galaxies and the intra-cluster medium. The prevalent point of view fifteen years ago was that in general, clusters were dynamically relaxed entities, with centrally peaked and radially symmetric distributions of galaxies and ICM, and gaussian (or nearly gaussian) velocity distributions. Recent analysis of clusters, both in the distribution of galaxies (spatial as well as velocity distribution) (Bird 1994) and x-ray emitting intra-cluster medium (Mohr, Fabricant & Geller 1993) indicate that a large percentage of nearby clusters have significant deviations from spherical or elliptical symmetry that may indicate that

they are not currently in a state of dynamical equilibrium. It has been suggested that the ubiquity of substructure in clusters is the result of the merging of galaxy groups and clusters. Unfortunately, the assessment of whether a given cluster contains significant substructure has to date depended on the quality, quantity, and type of data used to make the determination. Different workers have generally used somewhat different definitions of what constituted significant structure, with a premium being placed on being able to detect even relatively minor deviations from a relaxed structure.

This work will require a fairly restrictive definition of what constitutes significant substructure, one that is sensitive to only major substructure. This definition is based on the distribution of the diffuse x-ray emission from the cluster, as observed by the ROSAT PSPC. Using this data, the strength of the sub-clustering is quantified using a multipole expansion technique developed by Buote & Tsai (1995,1996).

3.2.1 Multipole Expansion

Buote & Tsai (1995) begin by considering the relationship between gravitational potential and mass surface density in 2 dimensions,

$$\nabla^2 \Psi(R, \phi) = 4\pi G \sigma(R, \phi), \quad (3.1)$$

where ∇^2 is the 2-dimensional laplacian operator, $\Psi(R, \phi)$ is the gravitational potential, G is the gravitational constant, and $\sigma(R, \phi)$ is the projected mass surface density. The potential due to material internal to a radius R is then given by the expression

$$\Psi(R, \phi) = 2Ga_0 \ln R - 2G \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{mR^m} (a_m \cos(m\phi) + b_m \sin(m\phi)). \quad (3.2)$$

The coefficients a_m and b_m can be determined from the following relations

$$a_m = \int_{R' \leq R} \sigma(x') (R')^m \cos(m\phi') dx' \quad (3.3)$$

$$b_m = \int_{R' \leq R} \sigma(x')(R')^m \sin(m\phi') dx' \quad (3.4)$$

where $x' = (R', \phi')$. Buote & Tsai (1995) then define the quantity

$$P_{mm'} = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} \Psi_{m'}(R_{ap}, \phi) \Psi_m(R_{ap}, \phi) d\phi, \quad (3.5)$$

where Ψ_m is the m th term of the multipole expansion. All terms in this product except for those where $m = m'$ vanish, so we can write $P_m \equiv P_{mm'}$. P_m then measures the “power” within a radius R_{ap} of the m^{th} term of the multipole expansion. A convenient way to represent the different P_m 's is to take their ratio with the value of P_0 . Since P_0 is just a measure of the total enclosed mass, the ratios P_m/P_0 represent the relative contributions of the different moments to the total potential, independent of the total cluster mass. Since only ratios of the powers are being considered, the constant factors of $2G$ may be dropped, and the powers can be written (for $m = 0$)

$$P_0 = [a_0 \ln(R_{ap})]^2 \quad (3.6)$$

and for other values of m

$$P_m = \frac{1}{2m^2 R_{ap}^{2m}} (a_m^2 + b_m^2). \quad (3.7)$$

Buote & Tsai (1995) neglect contributions to the potential from radii greater than R_{ap} , which is reasonable as long as they are interested only in the state of the potential on scales less than R_{ap} .

Since, in general, maps of the mass surface density for clusters are not available, Buote & Tsai (1995,1996) instead use observations of the distribution of the x-ray emitting ICM to estimate the power ratios (i.e. they replace the mass surface density $\sigma(R, \phi)$ in equations 3.3 and 3.4 with the x-ray surface brightness distribution). Because the x-ray surface brightness is in general not linearly proportional to the mass surface density, the ratios P_m/P_0 in this case do not

strictly represent the power in different multipole components of the gravitational potential. However, since the qualitative properties of the mass surface density and x-ray surface brightness depend in similar ways on the structure of the gravitational potential, the P_m/P_0 still depend on the dynamical state of the cluster. Since all that is really desired is a measure of the cluster's state, relative to other clusters, Buote & Tsai's technique can be used as a method of comparing the relative dynamical states of different clusters.

3.2.2 Interpretation of Power Ratios

One of the important uses of power ratios is to distinguish between clusters that are unimodal (i.e. which are dominated by a single component), but may have elliptical isophotes, from bimodal clusters that have a second significant spatial component to their x-ray emission. Buote & Tsai (1995) have examined the response of power ratios to simulated unimodal and bimodal clusters. They find that the ratios P_2/P_0 and P_4/P_0 are high for both elliptical unimodal clusters and bimodal clusters. This is not unexpected, since both P_2/P_0 and P_4/P_0 are sensitive to the ellipticity of the surface brightness distribution, which is high for both elliptical unimodal and bimodal clusters. On the other hand, the ratio P_3/P_0 is sensitive to bimodal clusters where the components are of unequal surface brightness. This means that most bimodal clusters show a significant P_3/P_0 component, while elliptical unimodals do not. This means that an effective means of separating unimodal from bimodal clusters is to make plots of P_2/P_0 versus P_3/P_0 and P_3/P_0 versus P_4/P_0 . In these diagrams, the sequence of increasingly bimodal clusters lies on a locus from the lower left to upper right, while elliptical unimodal clusters lie near the P_2/P_0 or P_4/P_0 axis. This allows easy separation of clusters that have a significant bimodal component, and are thus presumably less dynamically evolved from primarily unimodal clusters, which are more dynamically evolved.

3.3 Measured Power Ratios

The power ratios for the clusters of interest in this study were measured on x-ray images obtained from the ROSAT PSPC archive of pointed observations, using the techniques outlined in Buote & Tsai (1996). First, hard band images were extracted from pulse-invariant (PI) channels 50 to 200, corresponding roughly to energies 0.5 to 2.0 KeV, and the images were rebinned to have 15 arcsecond pixels. Next the images were flat fielded using the SASS exposure map distributed with the archive data. Although the flat field correction for the PSPC depends on photon energy, the effective difference between the correct exposure maps and the SASS map is negligible for hard band images (Snowden, Plucinsky, Briel, Hasinger, & Pfeffermann 1992). Point sources were excised from the images by identifying prominent sources by eye. A surface was fit interactively to an annular region surrounding the source, and the pixel values within an aperture around the source were replaced with the fitted values. Fortunately the low order of the moments considered here means that the derived values of the power ratios are insensitive to the specifics of the point source removal. This has been verified by deriving power ratios on cluster images with no point sources removed. Even in this extreme case, the derived power ratios did not differ significantly from those found for the point source excised images.

Finally, the background level on the images was estimated using source free areas in an annular region between 45-50 arcminutes from the image center, and the background level was subtracted from the image. Contour plots of the point source excised images are presented in Figure 3.1. For the purpose of display only, the contour plots given in Figure 3.1 have been smoothed with a Gaussian with $\sigma = 1'$. The images used to derive the power ratios have not been smoothed at all.

Power ratios were then computed on these reduced images. In general the

Figure 3.1. Contour plots of x-ray images for Abell 262, Abell 754, Abell 1367, Abell 2199, and Abell 2151. In each case the lowest contour corresponds to 1.6×10^{-3} counts/sec/Arcmin².

Figure 3.1. —Continued

ratios were computed within an aperture with a projected radius of 0.533 Mpc ($H_0 = 75\text{km/sec/Mpc}$), which was chosen to match Buote & Tsai’s smallest aperture (0.5 Mpc for $H_0 = 80\text{km/sec/Mpc}$). The centers for the apertures were determined using a centroid based method. An aperture of the appropriate radius was used along with an initial guess for the aperture center. The position of the aperture was then changed iteratively until the center of the aperture and the centroid value corresponded to less than 0.01 pixel. The measured values of the power ratios are presented in Table 3.1.

In order to test whether the results of Buote & Tsai (1996) were successfully reproduced two of the clusters from their sample, Abell 754 and Abell 2199 were analyzed. These clusters were selected since they represented the 2 extremes of cluster dynamical state; Abell 2199 is a prototypically relaxed cluster, while Abell 754 is in the throes of a major cluster merger (Zabludoff & Zaritsky 1995; Henriksen & Markevitch 1996). The values of the various coefficients measured here are in good agreement with those from Buote & Tsai (1996).

Power ratios were not determined for Abell 569 and the Virgo cluster. The proximity of the Virgo cluster means that the field of view for PSPC pointed observations of the cluster center is too small to be useful for comparison with more distant clusters. Maps of the large scale x-ray emission from Virgo have been constructed from the ROSAT PSPC sky survey (Böhringer, Briel, Schwarz, Voges, Hartner, & Trümper 1994), but the sky survey data have never been released for public use. Abell 569 has a PSPC observation, but the cluster is not a particularly bright x-ray source, and the integration time for the PSPC observation is somewhat short (4181 seconds). The combination of these two factors means that after point source removal, there was insufficient signal in the x-ray image to extract reliable power ratios for Abell 569.

Figure 3.2 gives plots of P_2/P_0 versus P_3/P_0 and P_3/P_0 versus P_4/P_0 . Besides allowing verification of the technique, the measured values for Abell 754 and Abell 2199 also serve as excellent fiducial points, delineating the portion of the diagram inhabited by dynamically evolved clusters (the lower left on these diagrams), and dynamically young clusters (the upper right portion of the diagrams). From Figure 3.2 it is clear that the clusters observed here may be separated on this diagram according to the overall dynamical state of the cluster. Abell 262 and 1656 represent systems that are relatively dynamically relaxed, while Abell 1367 and 2151 are systems that are dynamically less evolved. This separation into dynamically relaxed and unrelaxed clusters will be used in analysis of the star formation properties of these clusters.

In order to utilize the existing optical data for the Virgo cluster and Abell 569 in examining the dependence of star formation properties on the dynamical state of the cluster, these two clusters were assigned to the dynamically relaxed or dynamically unrelaxed samples using other data. In the case of the Virgo cluster, visual examination of the large scale x-ray map constructed from the ROSAT sky survey data (Böhringer et al. 1994) shows that on 0.5 Mpc scales, the cluster is

Figure 3.2. Different power ratios plotted against one another for the clusters considered here.

Table 3.1. Measured power ratios, in units of 10^{-7} . The value for Abell 1656 is from Buote & Tsai (1996).

Cluster	R_{ap} (Mpc)	P_2/P_0	P_3/P_0	P_4/P_0
Abell 262	0.335	45.46	0.38	0.26
Abell 754	0.533	884.8	3.35	9.93
Abell 1367	0.533	253.2	15.6	3.27
Abell 1656	0.533	42.5	0.27	0.17
Abell 2151	0.533	183.9	5.73	3.33
Abell 2199	0.533	12.6	0.094	0.119

similar to the low power ratio clusters rather than the high power ratio clusters. For this reason the Virgo cluster was placed in the dynamically relaxed sample. In the case of Abell 569, the fact that the existing x-ray data was insufficient to calculate power ratios meant that the optical data must be used instead to determine the dynamical state of the cluster. Based on the analysis of galaxy positions and velocities in Abell 569, Beers, Forman, Huchra, Jones, & Gebhardt (1991) find that Abell 569 is a bimodal cluster, with 2 roughly equally sized clumps of galaxies. Therefore, in the upcoming analysis, Abell 569 is included in the dynamically unrelaxed subsample. None of the following results depend sensitively on the group to which Abell 569 is assigned.

3.4 Measuring Star Formation in Galaxies

In order to define what is meant by the star formation properties of “normal” galaxies, the $H\alpha+[N\ II]$ aperture photometry surveys of Kennicutt & Kent (1983) and Romanishin (1990) were used. Both of these papers present data for relatively large samples of nearby galaxies. Both papers contain representatives of galaxies of all morphological types, although the samples tend to be weighted heavily towards spiral galaxies, since most E and S0 galaxies have little or no detectable

$H\alpha$ emission. It should be noted that neither paper presents data for a complete sample of galaxies; however the samples should be representative of the properties of field galaxies at large. Most of the early type galaxies in these two samples show little sign of star formation, having $H\alpha+[NII]$ equivalent widths near zero. $H\alpha$ observations of gas rich S0 galaxies by Pogge & Eskridge (1993) suggest that at least some S0 galaxies do have modest rates of star formation. In order to allow for the existence of galaxies like these in the general galaxy population, the S0 galaxies from Pogge & Eskridge (1993) that don't have AGN but that were detected in $H\alpha$ are also included as part of the reference sample.

The equivalent widths from Kennicutt & Kent (1983) have been increased by a factor of 1.16, in accordance with Romanishin's finding that their equivalent widths were lower than his by this factor, probably due to a slight overestimation of the continuum level in their galaxies on the part of Kennicutt & Kent (1983). Because the reference sample is being used to define the star formation properties of normal galaxies, all galaxies that have Seyfert nuclei have been removed from the reference sample, since the active nucleus in these systems can contribute significantly to the total $H\alpha+[N II]$ emission. Three star-bursting systems and two low surface brightness galaxies were also removed, since they deviated significantly from the properties of "normal" galaxies. Finally, since the ultimate interest is in studying the difference between cluster and non-cluster galaxies, all Virgo cluster galaxies have been removed from the sample, as well as NGC 753, which is a member of Abell 262.

Figure 3.3 shows a plot of $B-V$ color from RC3 versus $H\alpha$ equivalent width for the 153 galaxies left in the reference sample. Figure 3.4 shows the dependence for the same set of galaxies of equivalent width upon morphological type (also from RC3). In these figures, the Kennicutt & Kent (1983) and Romanishin (1990) galaxies are plotted as open diamonds, and the Pogge & Eskridge (1993) galaxies are plotted as filled circles. A noteworthy point is that the Pogge & Eskridge

Figure 3.3. Relationship between $(B - V)_T^0$ and $H\alpha + [\text{NII}]$ equivalent width for normal galaxies. The galaxies from Kennicutt & Kent (1983) and Romanishin (1990) are plotted as open diamonds, while those from Pogge & Eskridge (1993) are plotted as filled circles.

Figure 3.4. Relationship between Hubble type and $H\alpha$ + [NII] equivalent width for normal galaxies. The galaxies from Kennicutt & Kent (1983) and Romanishin (1990) are plotted as open diamonds, while those from Pogge & Eskridge (1993) are plotted as filled circles.

(1993) S0's fall along the same locus as the galaxies from Kennicutt & Kent (1983) and Romanishin (1990) in the color-equivalent width plane. In what follows the locus defined by this set of galaxies on either of these two diagrams will be considered to be representative of that followed by normal galaxies, any deviation from that locus by a population of galaxies will be considered due to a difference in star forming properties of that population as a whole, à la Kennicutt, et al. (1987).

In order to be able to directly compare galaxies with existing $B - V$ data (e.g. the reference sample, as well as galaxies in Abell 1367, 1656, and the Virgo cluster) with the $B - R$ data collected at the Lowell Observatory, the $B - V$ colors have been converted to $B - R$ colors using the following relation

$$(B - R) = 0.245 + 1.329(B - V) \quad (3.8)$$

that is the result of a fit between the $B - V$ and $B - R$ colors of galaxies in the photometric compilation of Buta & Williams (1995).

3.4.1 Parameterization of Star Formation in Normal Galaxies

Since the purpose of this dissertation is to study significant departures on the part of cluster galaxies from either the color-equivalent width or Hubble type-equivalent width relation, parameters that are a measure of these deviations are now defined. The first of these was defined by Kennicutt et al. (1987), and is simply the ratio of the equivalent width for the galaxy to the median equivalent width for galaxies of the same morphological type as the galaxy in question, which they denote as r . Because they had no E-S0 galaxies in their sample, Kennicutt et al. (1987) had no problems with the fact that the median equivalent width for E-S0 galaxies is very close to zero. Since there are several E-S0 galaxies in the sample with significant emission, the definition of Kennicutt et al. (1987) has

Table 3.2. Median values of $H\alpha+[NII]$ equivalent width for the reference sample as a function of Hubble type.

Hubble Type	$EW(\text{\AA})$
S0/a-Sa	1.2
Sab-Sb	11.6
Sbc-Sc-Scd	27.9
Sd-Sm-Im	29.5

been modified by assigning the median for these morphological types the value for S0/a-Sa galaxies. The median values derived for the different morphological types are given in Table 3.2. In order to distinguish this parameter from a similar parameter for comparing broadband colors and equivalent widths (which is defined below), this parameter is denoted as r_{morp} .

In order to have a parameter for comparing the deviation of the equivalent width from the typical value for a normal star forming galaxy with the same broadband color, the parameter r_{phot} is defined as the ratio of the galaxy's equivalent width to the value for a galaxy with the same broadband color, found by fitting the color equivalent width relation for the reference sample. A quadratic provides a good fit over the range of colors of interest, with the best fit quadratic being

$$EW = 132.44 - 143.57(B - R)_T^0 + 35.38((B - R)_T^0)^2 \text{\AA}, \quad (3.9)$$

which is shown over plotted on the reference data in Figure 3.5. In defining r_{phot} for galaxies with colors $(B - R)_T^0 > 1.39$, the fit equivalent width is set to 1 instead of using the value predicted from the fit, in order to avoid values near zero.

A plot of r_{phot} versus r_{morp} for the reference sample galaxies is shown in Figure 3.6. In general these parameters show a good correlation with one another, although with a scatter of about a factor of 2 around the mean. There seem to be a few outliers in the sense of a few galaxies that have fairly normal values of

Figure 3.5. Fit to reference sample color equivalent width relation over plotted on the data.

Figure 3.6. Plot of r_{phot} versus r_{morph} for reference sample galaxies. The high r_{morph} tail at $r_{\text{phot}} \sim 1$ is due to early type galaxies with modest star formation.

r_{phot} , but that have large values of r_{morph} . Since early type galaxies generally have low global rates of star formation, a relatively modest increase in an early type galaxies global star formation rate can easily increase the *differential* star formation rate as reflected in the $H\alpha$ equivalent widths by a factor of 5 to 10. It might be suspected that these outliers may be early type galaxies that have increased $H\alpha$ emission.

In order to examine the nature of these galaxies, a plot of r_{morph} and r_{phot} versus the $(B - R)_T^0$ colors of the reference sample galaxies is given in Figure 3.7. In these diagrams it can be seen that the outliers in both these parameters have red colors, suggesting that these galaxies have predominantly older stellar populations, consistent with the hypothesis that they are largely early type galaxies. The dependence of r_{morph} and r_{phot} on the morphological type of the galaxy is shown in Figure 3.8. In this figure the galaxies have been binned in morphological type in accordance with the way the galaxies were binned when determining the median equivalent widths used in determining r_{morph} . Again, the galaxies with the earliest morphological type show the largest scatter in these parameters. It therefore seems likely that this larger scatter is due to the fact that the low global star formation rates in these galaxies can leave them fairly sensitive to rather small fluctuations in the star formation rate. On the other hand, the fairly substantial star formation rates of later type spirals means that star formation indicators in these galaxies are relatively less sensitive to fluctuations in the global star formation rates of these galaxies.

In summary, the current global star formation in field galaxies is well correlated with both broadband color and morphological type, although with a scatter of a factor of 2 around the mean. The scatter for the earliest type galaxies is larger than for later types, because the low average star formation for these types makes the fractional star formation rate in these systems fairly sensitive to modest fluctuations in the global star formation rate.

Figure 3.7. Examination of the dependence of r_{phot} and r_{morp} on the $(B - R)_T^0$ colors of the reference sample galaxies.

Figure 3.8. Examination of the dependence of r_{phot} and r_{morp} on the morphological types of the reference sample galaxies.

3.4.2 Definitions of $H\alpha$ Excess and Deficit

The fact that early type galaxies have a larger scatter in r_{phot} and r_{morph} suggests that some caution must be taken in defining what is meant by a galaxy having an excess or deficit of $H\alpha$ emission. This point is clearly illustrated in Figure 3.9, which shows the distribution of early and late type galaxies in the r_{phot} - r_{morph} plane. In this diagram, galaxies with types Sab and later (plotted as open diamonds) lie in a fairly tight band between 0.5 and 2.0 in both parameters. Galaxies of type Sa and earlier (plotted as filled circles) show significantly greater scatter in both parameters, suggesting that different limits be used to define what is meant by an $H\alpha$ excess galaxy for early and late type galaxies.

3.4.2.1 $H\alpha$ Excess

Definition of what is meant for a galaxy of type Sab and later to have an $H\alpha$ excess is achieved using Figure 3.9. Few of these galaxies have either r_{phot} or r_{morph} in excess of 2.0, so galaxies of type Sab and later will be considered to have an $H\alpha$ excess if they have either r_{phot} or r_{morph} in excess of 2.

The larger scatter for galaxies of type Sa and earlier makes selecting a criteria for these galaxies more difficult. Roughly 90% of the early type galaxies in the reference sample have values of $r_{phot} < 4.0$ and $r_{morph} < 10.0$, so these limits are adopted to define what constitutes an $H\alpha$ excess for an early type galaxy. This adopted criteria for r_{morph} is consistent with the constraint on [OII] equivalent width used by Caldwell & Rose (1997) in identifying early type galaxies in their sample that they considered to have a significantly high rate of star formation for their type.

3.4.2.2 $H\alpha$ Deficit

The definition of what constitutes an $H\alpha$ deficit for galaxies of type Sab and later is as straightforward as defining what an $H\alpha$ excess is for these systems.

Figure 3.9. Plot of r_{phot} versus r_{morp} for the reference sample galaxies. Galaxies with type Sab and later are plotted as open diamonds, and those with types Sa and earlier are plotted as filled circles.

Figure 3.9 shows that there are few late type galaxies that have r_{phot} and r_{morp} less than 0.5. On the other hand, few of the early type systems meet this criteria. This is not surprising considering the low median equivalent width in these systems. Further, the fact that most early type systems have little sign of either current or recently ended star formation suggests that the idea of an $H\alpha$ deficit for these systems is not a meaningful one. Therefore, the criteria adopted for both early and late type systems to have an $H\alpha$ deficit is $r_{phot} < 0.5$ or $r_{morp} < 0.5$.

3.5 Cluster Data

The relationship between the $H\alpha + [NII]$ equivalent width and $B - R$ color for galaxies in the various clusters is shown in Figure 3.10, and between Hubble type and equivalent width in Figure 3.11. These plots show that at least some galaxies in each cluster show significant departures from the mean relation for normal field galaxies. For some, the departure is in the sense of having too much $H\alpha$ emission for their color/morphological type, while for others there is too little $H\alpha$ for the morphological type or color.

Another impression gained from examining Figures 3.10 and 3.11 is that there is a preference for galaxies in a particular cluster to have excursions in the same sense. For example, there are several galaxies in the Virgo cluster that seem to have low equivalent widths for their type or color, while in Abell 2151, there are 3 galaxies with high $H\alpha$ emission for their type and color. This result in itself is not unexpected, since Kennicutt (1983a) had previously reported that Sc galaxies in the Virgo cluster had low equivalent widths for their type, while Gavazzi, Boselli, & Kennicutt (1991) reported a population of high equivalent width galaxies in Abell 1367. A question that has not been addressed before is whether galaxies in different clusters with a similar dynamical state tend to have deviations in the same sense. Wang & Ulmer (1997) report a correlation between

Figure 3.10. Relation between $(B-R)_T^0$ color and $H\alpha + [\text{NII}]$ equivalent width for the different clusters, overlaid on the data for the reference sample. The reference sample data is plotted as diamonds, while the cluster galaxies are plotted as filled circles.

Figure 3.11. Relation between Hubble type and $H\alpha + [\text{NII}]$ equivalent width for the different clusters, overlaid on the data for the reference sample. The reference sample data is plotted as diamonds, while the cluster galaxies are plotted as filled circles.

x-ray ellipticity and blue fraction in a sample of 10 Butcher Oemler clusters with redshifts 0.17-0.54, suggesting that there may be a link between the dynamical state of a cluster and the star formation properties of the galaxies in that cluster. To see whether such a link can be established for low redshift clusters, the power ratios measured from the ROSAT images were used to divide the available clusters into two samples, those that seem to be more dynamically evolved (Virgo, Abell 262, and Abell 1656), and those that are less dynamically evolved (Abell 569, Abell 1367, and Abell 2151).

Plots of the colors and morphological types versus equivalent widths are given in Figure 3.12 for the dynamically relaxed clusters, and for the dynamically unrelaxed clusters in Figure 3.13. Examination of these figures suggests that there may indeed be a difference between the two samples, with the dynamically relaxed clusters having several galaxies with low equivalent widths for their colors, while the dynamically younger clusters have several red, early type galaxies with stronger than normal $H\alpha$ emission.

Comparison of the distribution of the cluster galaxies and reference sample galaxies in the $r_{phot}-r_{morp}$ plane are given for the dynamically relaxed clusters in Figure 3.14, and for the dynamically unrelaxed clusters in Figure 3.15. In both figures separate plots are given for galaxies of type Sab and later and galaxies of type Sa and earlier.

Examination of Figure 3.14 suggests that the distribution of relaxed cluster early type galaxies in the $r_{phot}-r_{morp}$ plane is not significantly different from that of early type reference sample galaxies. Although many of the late type relaxed cluster galaxies seem to be indistinguishable from the reference sample late type galaxies, there also seem to be an excess number that have low r_{phot} or r_{morp} values. The fraction of galaxies in the reference sample and relaxed cluster sample that meet the criteria for being either $H\alpha$ excess or deficit galaxies are given in Table 3.3, along with uncertainties for these fractions, calculated using Poisson

Figure 3.12. Relation between Hubble type and $H\alpha + [\text{NII}]$ equivalent width for the more dynamically evolved clusters, overlaid on the data for the reference sample. The reference sample data is plotted as diamonds, while the cluster galaxies are plotted as filled circles.

Figure 3.13. Relation between Hubble type and $H\alpha+[NII]$ equivalent width for the less dynamically evolved clusters, overlaid on the data for the reference sample. The reference sample data is plotted as diamonds, while the cluster galaxies are plotted as filled circles.

Figure 3.14. Comparison of the $r_{\text{phot}}-r_{\text{morp}}$ distribution for the reference sample galaxies, plotted as open diamonds, and the galaxies in relaxed clusters, plotted as filled circles.

Figure 3.15. Comparison of the $r_{\text{phot}}-r_{\text{morp}}$ distribution for the reference sample galaxies, plotted as open diamonds, and the galaxies in unrelaxed clusters, plotted as filled circles.

Table 3.3. Fractions of galaxies in the reference, relaxed cluster, and unrelaxed cluster samples showing $H\alpha$ excesses and deficits.

Sample	Late		Early
	Excess	Deficit	Excess
Reference	0.067 ± 0.024	0.12 ± 0.03	0.20 ± 0.10
Relaxed Cluster	0.089 ± 0.044	0.31 ± 0.08	0.63 ± 0.28
Unrelaxed Cluster	0.23 ± 0.09	0.23 ± 0.09	0.83 ± 0.17

statistics. This shows that the fraction of late type $H\alpha$ excess galaxies in the relaxed clusters is not significantly different than that in the reference sample. The high fraction of early type $H\alpha$ excess galaxies in these clusters is not statistically significant, because of the small number of early type galaxies in the sample. The 31% of late type, relaxed cluster galaxies is greater than the 12% of reference sample galaxies with a deficit, at the marginally significant 2.2σ level. Running a two dimensional Kolmogorov-Smirnov test for the late type galaxies in the relaxed clusters and the reference sample suggests that the probability that the two distributions are drawn from the same parent population is less than 1%. Therefore there is significant but not overwhelming evidence for galaxies in relaxed clusters to have a deficit of $H\alpha$ emission when compared to field galaxies.

Examination of Figure 3.15 shows that for the unrelaxed clusters, the distribution of early type galaxies in the $r_{phot}-r_{morp}$ plane is much different than that of the reference sample galaxies, with most of the cluster galaxies having high r_{morp} and r_{phot} values. The distribution of unrelaxed cluster late type galaxies in the $r_{phot}-r_{morp}$ plane is very similar to that of the reference sample galaxies, with the possible exception that a few more cluster galaxies may have an excess or deficit of $H\alpha$ emission. The fractions of unrelaxed cluster galaxies with excesses or deficits of $H\alpha$ emission are given in Table 3.3. The only significant difference between the unrelaxed clusters and reference sample is that early type galaxies in the

unrelaxed clusters have an $H\alpha$ excess 83% of the time, compared to 20% of the time for the reference sample galaxies. This difference is significant at greater than the 3σ level. A two dimensional Kolmogorov-Smirnov test for the early type galaxies in the unrelaxed cluster and reference sample suggests that the probability that two distributions would be drawn from the same parent population is only 0.3%. The evidence for a population of late type $H\alpha$ excess galaxies in the unrelaxed clusters is much less strong. While the observed fraction of 23% is higher than the 6.7% observed in the reference sample, this is only a 1.75σ difference. The fraction of $H\alpha$ deficit galaxies in the unrelaxed clusters is also higher than that in the reference sample, but is different only at the 1σ level, so is not at all significant.

In summary, there is evidence for population differences between galaxies in relaxed and unrelaxed clusters and the field, but the evidence is not overwhelming. In relaxed clusters, the difference is due to a population of $H\alpha$ deficit galaxies. In the unrelaxed clusters, the difference is due to a population of $H\alpha$ excess galaxies, primarily of early type. Finally, although population differences have been detected, it is important to note that the majority of cluster galaxies seem to have $H\alpha$ properties indistinguishable from comparable field galaxies.

3.6 The Nature of the Discordant Galaxies

The above analysis finds two classes of galaxies in relaxed and unrelaxed clusters that seem to have star formation properties different than those of normal field galaxies. The first are galaxies that show reduced star formation compared to what would be expected, both for their color and morphological type. These galaxies occur preferentially in the more dynamically relaxed clusters, although the less relaxed clusters do show a higher, though not statistically significant, fraction of these galaxies than in the field. The second type are galaxies that

show excess $H\alpha$ emission for their color and type, which occur almost exclusively in the less dynamically relaxed clusters. The question is, what is the nature of these galaxies?

The first possibility is that the morphological types or colors of the discordant galaxies are incorrect, and thus that the inferred level of $H\alpha$ emission for these galaxies is in error. In the same vein is the possibility that the measured equivalent widths are in error. The uncertainties in the photometric measurements made at the Lowell Observatory are discussed in Chapter 2. In general the expected uncertainties in the measured quantities are much smaller than would be required to account for the observed effect. Similarly, the data collected from the literature has quoted uncertainties of the same magnitude. In fact, since most of the literature data for the clusters was collected by the same people that collected the reference sample data (and in fact the data for the Virgo cluster galaxies was taken from the same papers as the reference data), it seems highly unlikely that photometric errors are to blame for the observed discrepant galaxies.

The reliability of the morphological types of the galaxies is more difficult to address than that of the photometry. First, there exists a scatter of approximately one full type between the morphological types of the same set of galaxies determined by different people (Naim, Lahav, Buta, Corwin, de Vaucouleurs, Dressler, Huchra, van den Bergh, Raychaudhury, Sodre & Storrie-Lombardi 1995). However the intrinsic scatter in morphological types is unlikely to account for the observed effect, since it should be equally well present in both the reference and cluster samples. A more serious problem is that the typical distance to the clusters studied in this work is much greater than the distance to the reference sample galaxies. This means that pixelization and seeing effects can lead to a loss of information in the images of the galaxies in the more distant clusters. Since one important determinant of morphological type is the structure and texture of spiral arms, the loss of high spatial frequency information in galaxy images can lead to a

systematic morphological mistyping, presumably in the sense of typing late type galaxies as earlier type galaxies. Short of obtaining images of cluster galaxies in excellent seeing with a small pixel scale, it is difficult to directly assess how significant this effect is.

One indirect way to examine whether there is a major problem with morphological mistyping is to measure some other property that is also used in determining morphological types for galaxies, but which is less effected by distance, such as the bulge to disk ratio of the galaxy. In this case the dependence of Hubble type on the concentration index (Doi et al. 1993) for a sample of nearby field galaxies is compared to the same parameters for cluster galaxies for which images have been obtained. The field sample concentration indices were calculated for galaxies in the imaging survey of nearby galaxies by Frei, Guhathakurta, Gunn, & Tyson (1996), who collected images both at the Lowell and Palomar observatories. The method used to derive concentration indices for the Frei et al. (1996) galaxies was identical to that used for the cluster galaxies (see section 2.7). Images in Gullixson's R band (extremely similar to Cousins R for galaxies) were used to derive the concentration indices. The size of apertures used was again selected to correspond to a surface brightness level 2σ above that for the sky. Indices were calculated only for galaxies with Lowell images. The smaller number of galaxies observed using the 48 inch Schmidt telescope at the Palomar Observatory were not used, because the centers of several of these galaxies were saturated making them unsuitable for calculating concentration indices. This gave a sample of 82 field galaxies for which concentration indices were calculated.

A plot of concentration index against Hubble type is given in Figure 3.16. Examination of the distribution of points for the Frei et al. (1996) galaxies shows that there is a correspondence between the two parameters; however, the large spread in concentration index at a given Hubble type means that using a single galaxy's concentration index to predict an accurate Hubble type is impossible. We

Figure 3.16. A comparison of the distribution of concentration indices vs. morphological type for a sample of nearby galaxies (open diamonds) and cluster galaxies (closed circles).

can, however, examine the distribution of points in the Hubble type-concentration index plane for the different samples to see whether they trace the same distribution. Doing this for the Frei et al. (1996) and cluster galaxies suggests that while one or two early type cluster galaxies may be misclassified late type spirals, in general the two distributions are identical. Therefore, there is no evidence that there has been any *systematic* mistyping of cluster galaxies. This in turn implies that simple morphological misidentification cannot be used to account for the trends seen in the clusters of different dynamical states.

3.6.1 $H\alpha$ Deficient Galaxies

The $H\alpha$ deficient galaxies appear preferentially in the dynamically relaxed clusters. Morphologically the $H\alpha$ deficient galaxies are later type spirals (type Sb and later), which as noted earlier is due to the fact that many early type galaxies have relatively little star formation, so that it is essentially impossible for an early type galaxy to have an $H\alpha$ deficit. Of the five $H\alpha$ deficient galaxies that have DDO types in Van den Bergh, Pierce, & Tully (1990), two are typed as anemic, two as normal spirals, and one is typed as a transition object between spiral and anemic. On the other hand, of seventeen galaxies (mostly in the Virgo cluster) considered here that had normal $H\alpha$ properties and types in Van den Bergh et al. (1990), sixteen were typed as spirals and the last was typed as a transition object. This suggests that the $H\alpha$ deficient galaxies probably represent another manifestation of Van den Bergh's (1976) anemic spirals. On the surface at least, this suggests that a simple model where the star forming capability of disk galaxies is slowly eroded due to extended exposure to the cluster environment, either through gas dynamical or tidal removal of gas from the galaxy, can account for the data. In support of this idea, Koopmann (1997) presents an $H\alpha$ imaging study of 65 spiral galaxies in the Virgo cluster, and finds that several of the later type spirals in her sample have a deficit of $H\alpha$ emission, attributable to

a truncation of $H\alpha$ emission in their outer disks. If this model is correct, the presence of some $H\alpha$ deficient galaxies in the less dynamically relaxed clusters is not unexpected, since the expected source of the substructure in these systems is the merger of two or more (presumably relaxed) clusters or groups. The few $H\alpha$ deficient galaxies in the dynamically unrelaxed sample may represent galaxies that have had their star forming capabilities eroded by prolonged exposure to the pre-merger cluster environment in these systems.

3.6.2 $H\alpha$ Excess Galaxies

An overabundance of $H\alpha$ excess galaxies in the dynamically relaxed clusters is indicated by the previous analysis. The majority of the $H\alpha$ excess galaxies are of early type, although there is marginal evidence for a greater number of late type, $H\alpha$ excess galaxies than found in the reference sample. This is in agreement with the earlier findings of Moss & Whittle (1993), who found a population of early type $H\alpha$ excess galaxies, but no enhanced late type spirals in an objective prism survey of eight nearby clusters. It also suggests that these systems represent the counterparts of the $H\delta$ strong galaxies found in nearby clusters by Caldwell et al. (1993) and Caldwell & Rose (1997), observed during their phase of active star formation. This result is somewhat difficult to reconcile with the simple picture where the enhanced population would all be late type spirals falling into the cluster for the first time, during which some environmental interaction (either gas dynamical or tidal) temporarily enhances the rate of star formation in the galaxies disks.

An important point regarding these early type $H\alpha$ excess galaxies is that although they demonstrate an excess of star formation compared to galaxies of similar type, the total rate of star formation in most of these systems is unimpressive when compared to a typical Sc galaxy. To demonstrate this point quantitatively, all the $H\alpha$ excess galaxies in the unrelaxed clusters (early as well as late type) are

tabulated in Table 3.4, along with several parameters related to the star formation activity in these systems. The absolute blue magnitudes (M_B) of the galaxies was calculated for each galaxy using B_T^0 along with the clusters mean recession velocity assuming $H_0 = 75\text{km/sec/Mpc}$ and $q_0 = 0$. The two parameters of the greatest importance in discussing the rate star formation in these galaxies are the $H\alpha + [NII]$ equivalent width and luminosity. The equivalent width gives a measure of the star formation rate per unit mass for a galaxy. For comparison, the mean equivalent width for Sc galaxies is $\approx 28 \text{ \AA}$. Examining the equivalent widths for the $H\alpha$ excess shows that most of the late type galaxies have impressively high equivalent widths, suggesting star formation rates per unit mass of 2-6 times that of a typical Sc galaxy. On the other hand, the early type $H\alpha$ excess galaxies have equivalent widths about the same as that of a typical Sc galaxy,

In order to examine the global star formation rates for the $H\alpha$ excess galaxies, their $H\alpha + [NII]$ luminosities are given in Table 3.4. For comparison, the total number of $M_B^* = -20.2$ Sc galaxies required to produce the same amount of $H\alpha$ luminosity was calculated and is given in the final column of the table. For an M^* Sc galaxy, $\log(L(H\alpha + [NII]))$ was taken to be 41.28, which corresponds to a star formation rate of $\approx 3.5M_\odot/\text{yr}$, using the calibration of Kennicutt (1983b). The values show that most of the late type $H\alpha$ excess galaxies have star formation rates 1-2 times that of a large Sc galaxy. The early type $H\alpha$ excess galaxies have star formation rates corresponding to ≈ 0.5 that of a large Sc galaxy. Therefore, although these systems show a definite enhancement in their star formation rates over what is seen in comparable field galaxies, this level of star formation is unspectacular when compared to that in normal, actively star forming systems.

Table 3.4. Basic data for the H α excess galaxies.

Galaxy	Hubble Type	r_{phot}	r_{morph}	M_B	EW Å	$\log(L_{H\alpha+[NII]})$ ergs/sec	# Sc's
CGCG 097-068	Sbc	2.70	1.83	-20.49	51	41.43	1.41
UGC 6697	I(pec)	1.97	2.39	-21.08	70	41.72	2.75
CGCG 097-073	I	1.75	3.14	-19.26	93	41.19	0.81
CGCG 097-079	I	3.49	5.71	-19.26	168	41.28	1.00
Mk 181	I	2.48	3.46	-20.60	102	42.03	5.62
UGC 6614	Sa	2.51	12.50	-20.56	17	41.16	0.76
UGC 6876	Sab	3.02	1.00	-20.30	12	40.80	0.33
NGC 3840	Sa	19.17	1.06	-20.38	23	41.20	0.83
NGC 6040B	S0(pec)	14.00	11.67	-20.85	14	40.97	0.49
NGC 6054	SABb	0.70	2.33	-20.82	27	41.35	1.17
IC 1189	SB0a	1.13	13.33	-21.29	16	41.21	0.85
D 150	S0	10.31	35.00	-20.49	42	41.77	3.09
D 079	E	7.11	40.00	-19.11	48	41.13	0.71
CGCG 234-056	S0a	0.71	35.83	-19.14	43	41.15	0.74
UGC 3706A	Sa	0.77	28.60	-18.89	34	40.84	0.36
UGC 3706B	Sa	1.03	14.08	-18.61	17	40.56	0.19

3.7 Summary and Discussion

This chapter has presented a study of how the excess or deficit of H α emission in cluster galaxies depends on the dynamical state of the cluster. The major conclusions are as follows:

1. Galaxies in clusters that are in relatively dynamically relaxed clusters show a deficit of H α emission (and thus presumably star formation) compared to a sample of normal, star forming field galaxies.
2. Galaxies that reside in less dynamically relaxed clusters have normal to excess H α emission. The H α excess galaxies in these clusters tend to be galaxies of type Sa and earlier.

3. The star formation rates in the early type $H\alpha$ excess galaxies are modest, generally being comparable to those in Sc galaxies of similar mass. Therefore, the $H\alpha$ excess systems currently account for a minority of the star formation occurring in the dynamically unrelaxed clusters.
4. The majority of cluster spirals, in both relaxed and unrelaxed clusters are indistinguishable in their star formation properties from similar field galaxies.

The fact that most cluster spirals seem to be fairly normal when compared to field spirals is a result that has been well documented in previous studies (Kennicutt 1983a; Kennicutt et al. 1984; Gavazzi et al. 1991), and suggests that whatever mechanisms operate in current day clusters to create the $H\alpha$ deficient galaxies are not catastrophic in nature. In particular, rapid stripping by the cluster environment is ruled out, since we do not see a population of blue, strongly $H\alpha$ deficient systems. This suggests that the observed $H\alpha$ deficient population is due to a process that more slowly strips the material from the galaxies.

Evidence for populations of early type $H\alpha$ excess galaxies in clusters had also been found previously by Moss & Whittle (1993). These systems probably represent the analogs of the $H\delta$ strong galaxies found by Caldwell et al. (1993) and Caldwell & Rose (1997), caught during their bursts of star formation. The combination of these galaxies with modest but enhanced rates of star formation, along with the large number of normal cluster spirals, suggests that like the mechanism that operates to produce the $H\alpha$ deficient galaxies, the mechanism responsible for the early type $H\alpha$ excess galaxies is also not catastrophic in nature. This is different than the situation for the most energetic star bursts, which usually seem to occur in strongly interacting or merging systems (Kennicutt et al. 1987). The typically low rates of star formation in early type galaxies probably makes them more sensitive tracers of such a mechanism than late type spirals, since a mild

burst of star formation will be more easily detected in the early type systems than in the late type systems.

Finally, note should be made of the shortcomings of the data used here, in particular the possibility of biases being introduced because, in the case of the data from the literature, no complete sample of galaxies has been observed. A particularly worrisome point in this regard is that the observers may have been selectively drawn to observing peculiar galaxies at the expense of more normal seeming galaxies. The observed difference between galaxies in different clusters suggests that this probably can't explain the observed effect, since there are systematic differences between different clusters, observed by the same people.

Another problem with the nature of the data used here is that they are not useful for answering some interesting questions regarding the nature of the galaxies and their immediate environment. First, because of the lack of uniform spatial sampling, it is impossible to look for correlations of the H α deficient or excess galaxies with position in the cluster, or with known substructures. Second, the serendipitous discovery of a compact elliptical in Abell 2151 with intense star formation (D 079) suggests that the current data may have missed other star forming galaxies that would not have been selected to be observed on the basis of their morphology.

Clearly all these difficulties could be resolved using an imaging survey that sampled the entire area of the cluster. In the following chapter the results of such a survey for one of the dynamically unrelaxed clusters studied in this chapter, Abell 2151 (the Hercules cluster), is presented.

4 An $H\alpha$ Survey of the Hercules Cluster

This chapter presents the results of an $H\alpha$ and broadband survey of the Hercules cluster (Abell 2151). The Hercules cluster was selected for observation since it represents the local prototype of an irregular, spiral rich cluster. The blue fraction of the Hercules cluster is 0.14, approaching that of Butcher-Oemler clusters at $z \gtrsim 0.2$ (Butcher & Oemler 1984). The data presented here represent the largest sample ever studied within a single galaxy cluster, and are spatially complete. Therefore, unlike previous work, this study is unbiased with respect to the morphological type of the galaxies observed. Basic photometric parameters were derived for a sample of cluster galaxies (both broadband and $H\alpha$ photometry) in order to search for galaxies that have either an excess or deficit of $H\alpha$ emission, compared to what would be expected for a field galaxy of similar color or morphological type. An additional goal is to search for any correlations between the emission properties of the galaxies and any of the identifiable substructures in the Hercules cluster.

4.1 Cluster Structure and Dynamics

The Hercules cluster is one of the best known examples of an irregular, unrelaxed cluster. The most comprehensive study to date of the current dynamical state of the cluster is that by Bird, Davis, & Beers (1995), which uses both x-ray data from the ROSAT PSPC as well as position and velocity data for cluster galaxies. The analysis of Bird et al. (1995) was extended by Huang & Sarazin

(1996) who combined ROSAT HRI data with the Bird et al. (1995) PSPC data, as well as positional data for cluster galaxies. A contour plot of the x-ray emission observed in the cluster by the PSPC, overlaid with the positions of cataloged galaxies in the direction of the cluster is given in Figure 4.1. Bird et al. (1995) find three diffuse x-ray sources associated with the cluster. The brightest is centered near the bright elliptical galaxy NGC 6041A, several arcminutes west of the classical core of the cluster. The second, centered near the classical cluster core and the bright elliptical NGC 6047, is only half as bright as the first. The third is located 15-20' east of the second, and is about 100 times less luminous than the brightest component.

Using position and velocity data for cluster galaxies, Bird et al. (1995) demonstrated that there was significant substructure in the galaxy distribution in the Hercules cluster, as well as in the x-ray distribution. They then applied an objective partitioning algorithm to the optical data, in order to infer more about the properties of the individual sub-clusters. Initially they allowed the partitioning algorithm to find three groups in the cluster, inspired by the presence of the 3 diffuse x-ray sources. The center of the first of the three sub-clusters found by the partitioning algorithm corresponds closely to the classical center for the cluster. The second corresponds to the eastern x-ray source, while the third corresponds to an obvious optical grouping in the northern part of the cluster that has no identifiable diffuse x-ray emission associated with it. Rerunning their statistical substructure tests on the partitioned data, Bird et al. (1995) find that there is still significant substructure in the central subcluster. The interpretation given the data by Bird et al. (1995) is that the subcluster corresponding to the classical center of the cluster represents the main body of the cluster. The eastern subcluster is suggested to be a smaller cluster that has recently passed through the center of the main cluster. The northern substructure is inferred not to be a distinct group of galaxies, but simply a region where galaxies are currently falling

Figure 4.1. Positions of all galaxies brighter than $O = 18.5$ from the APS catalog overlaid with contours of x-ray emission from the ROSAT PSPC for the Hercules cluster.

into the main cluster from the Hercules super-cluster. These results suggest that many galaxies are being introduced to the cluster environment for the first time.

Using x-ray data collected with the ROSAT HRI, in concert with a contour map of the galaxy surface density (weighted by luminosity), Huang & Sarazin (1996) were able to split the galaxy distribution in the central regions into two components, one centered near the brighter central x-ray peak, which they denote as C(B), and one associated with the fainter x-ray peak, which they denote C(F). They also identify a galaxy peak to the south-south-west of the brightest x-ray peak that has no associated x-ray emission, which they identify as the S subcluster.

The positions of the five sub-clusters identified by both Bird et al. (1995) and Huang & Sarazin (1996) (indicated by the symbols CB, CF, E, N, and S) are shown in Figure 4.2, overlaid on the x-ray contours from the ROSAT PSPC. The borders of the fields imaged at Kitt Peak are shown overlaid as dashed lines. These subcluster identifications will be used later in studying the spatial distribution of galaxies in the Hercules cluster with different $H\alpha$ emission properties.

4.2 Kitt Peak Observations

Observations of the Hercules cluster were obtained using the 0.9m telescope at Kitt Peak National Observatory over the nights of June 30 to July 2 1997. The detector was Kitt Peak's T2KA 2048² CCD used at the f/7.5 focus. This yielded a pixel scale of 0.688 arcseconds, giving a useful field of view of approximately 23 arcminutes.

Images were obtained for seven fields on the cluster in Johnson's B, Cousin's R, and with narrow band filters covering the spectral region of the $H\alpha + N[II]$ lines. Two narrow band filters were used on each field (Kitt Peak filter numbers 1497 and 1498) in order to cover the entire velocity range of the cluster. Two images were obtained in each filter, in order to facilitate cosmic ray removal. Typical

Figure 4.2. A comparison of the positions of optically identified substructures with x-ray identified substructures.

integration times for a single image were 10 minutes in B, 7.5 minutes in R, and 15 minutes in the narrow band filters. Because two frames in each filter were obtained, the total integration time in each filter was twice that for the single exposures.

4.2.1 Image Reductions

The CCD used in the observations had no significant bias structure across the chip. Therefore, although bias frames were collected and examined for each night's observing, they were not used in the removal of the bias level. Instead the bias level was removed from all frames using a polynomial fit to the over-scan region of the chip. Twilight flats were collected in each band at the beginning of each night. Because of the number of filters used, combined with the relatively long readout time of the CCD (≈ 2.5 minutes), it was impossible to obtain nightly flats for all the filters. Fortunately, the response of the observing setup on the 0.9m is fairly stable from night to night. Because of this, it was possible to combine the twilight images obtained over the three nights to construct master twilight flats for each filter, for the entire observing run. After flat fielding, the two images of each field in each filter were combined using an algorithm designed to remove cosmic rays by using the noise characteristics of the CCD.

4.3 Galaxy Selection

Cluster galaxies were selected for further study in three ways. First, the continuum subtracted $H\alpha$ images were visually searched to identify $H\alpha$ sources associated with the cluster. This search gave a list of approximately 80 $H\alpha$ sources in the cluster. Galaxies that had $B_T < 18.0$ were selected from this list for further study, yielding a sample of 66 galaxies, which are listed in Table 4.1, along with the galaxy's right ascension and declination, morphological type on the revised

Hubble system (a type of G means that no type was assignable to the galaxy), and where available, the galaxy's redshift, taken from NED. Galaxy identifications are given by their designation in different catalogs. NGC/IC numbers are given for galaxies in the New General Catalog of Non-stellar Astronomical Objects and the accompanying Index Catalog (Dreyer 1888, 1895, 1908), UGC numbers for galaxies in the Uppsala General Catalog of Galaxies (Nilson 1973), CGCG numbers for galaxies in the Catalog of Galaxies and Clusters of Galaxies (Zwicky et al. 1968), Mrk numbers for galaxies from the lists of Markarian et al. (1989), D numbers for galaxies from the morphological catalog of Dressler (1980b), BO numbers for galaxies in the photometric catalog of Butcher & Oemler (1985), PGC numbers for galaxies in the Catalog of Principle Galaxies (Paturel, Fouque, Bottinelli, & Gouguenheim 1989), mcg numbers for galaxies in the Morphological Catalog of Galaxies (Vorontsov-Velyaminov, Archipova, & Krasnogorskaja 1974). Finally, galaxies that did not appear in any catalog were given a two letter designation for the field in which the galaxy was observed, followed by a sequence number (for example sc1).

A second list of galaxies for further study was compiled, which constituted all galaxies in NED that had redshifts that indicated the galaxies were Hercules cluster members, but were not detected in $H\alpha$. This list was also restricted to galaxies brighter than $B_T = 18.0$, giving a list of 37 galaxies that are tabulated in Table 4.2, along with the galaxy's right ascension, declination, morphological type, and redshift. One fact is immediately notable from the examination of Tables 4.1 and 4.2; virtually all the spiral galaxies in cluster with $B_T \leq 18.0$ were detected in $H\alpha$, and the few spirals that were not detected were of type Sa.

Third, all galaxies that were detected by Dickey (1997) in his VLA HI survey of the cluster were included, in order to provide basic data such as magnitudes and colors for the galaxies in this sample. Unfortunately, the spatial coverage in the current survey is somewhat more restricted than that achieved by Dickey

(1997), so only those galaxies that overlap between both study areas are considered further. Most of the high surface brightness galaxies detected by Dickey (1997) in HI are also part of the $H\alpha$ detected sample, so there is considerable overlap between the two samples. All the galaxies in the Dickey (1997) survey that are within the current study area are tabulated in Table 4.3, along with their right ascension, declination, recession velocity determined from the HI data, total HI mass, and a notation as to whether the galaxy was detected in $H\alpha$. The following HI detections deserve comment at this point.

4.3.1 Notes on HI Detections

IC 1189. Based on the image of this galaxy on the Palomar Sky Survey, Dickey (1997) believed that this galaxy is a highly inclined system whose HI distribution is perpendicular to its disk. The deeper images obtained at Kitt Peak show that the presumed disk is actually this galaxy's central bar, and that its disk is oriented in a manner consistent with its HI distribution.

CE-060. This HI cloud is near the edge of the disk of the Sab galaxy IC 1185, and has an optical condensation associated with it. The HI and associated optical emission are probably not actually physically associated with IC 1185, since the HI velocity and optical velocity measured for IC 1185 differ by around 700km/sec.

CE-061 and CE-086. Both of these HI clouds are associated with the peculiar S0 galaxy IC 1182. IC 1182 is a merger remnant (Bothun, Stauffer, & Schommer 1981), showing two tidal tails; a narrow tail projecting to the east of the galaxy, and a broader, more fan-like tail projecting to the northwest. As is common in the later stages of a merger (see e.g. Hibbard & Van Gorkom 1996), the HI is associated with the tidal tails and not the main body of the merger remnant. ce-061 is associated with the narrow eastern tail, while ce-086 is associated with the more fan-like western tail. Based on the the structural differences in the two tails, Bothun et al. (1981) suggested that IC 1182 may represent a merger between a late

type spiral and an S0 or elliptical galaxy, since dynamically cold systems like the disks of late spirals give rise to narrow tidal tails, while broad tidal tails originate in hotter dynamical systems, such as early type galaxies. However, the fact that there is considerable HI associated with the fan-like tail may instead suggest that both galaxies were gas rich spirals, but that the merger was retrograde, giving rise to the broader tail (Hibbard & Van Gorkom 1996).

NGC 6050 + IC 1179. These late type galaxies are overlapping, but there is little sign of interaction, suggesting that they may simply be a line of sight projection. The optical velocities of the two galaxies are significantly different, with NGC 6050 having a recession velocity of $v = 9528\text{km/sec}$, and IC 1179 having a optical recession velocity of $v = 11129\text{km/sec}$. The detected HI appears to be associated with IC 1179 since it appears to be spatially centered on that galaxy and has a velocity of $v_{HI} = 11034\text{km/sec}$ that agrees well with the optically measured velocity. The non-detection of NGC 6050 is almost assuredly due to the fact that its recession velocity lies below the velocity cutoff in Dickey's HI data.

CE-143. Dickey (1997) notes that although the early type spiral D 091 is nearby ce-143, the HI is probably not associated with this galaxy, and instead may be associated with either the nearby galaxy BO 176, or another nearby dwarf galaxy. Examination of the optical images collected for this study show that there are actually 2 dwarfs in the region. The close proximity to one another on the sky of BO 176, the two dwarf galaxies, and a bright star make it difficult to derive photometric parameters for these systems.

CE-137 and CE-155. As Dickey (1997) notes, these two detections are probably just two parts of the same HI cloud, which were split in two by his detection algorithm. There is no obvious optical counterpart to the HI cloud on the CCD frames.

NGC 6047. This galaxy is a somewhat peculiar elliptical, located near the fainter diffuse x-ray peak associated with the cluster center. NGC 6047 was not

detected in $H\alpha$ in the current survey. The HI has a velocity over 2000km/sec higher than that measured optically for the galaxy, suggesting that it may be a line of sight superposition of of the bright elliptical and a lower surface brightness, HI rich galaxy.

Table 4.1. All H α detections brighter than $B_T = 18.0$.

Galaxy	RA (B1950)	Dec (B1950)	Morphology	z
D 084	16 01 01.1	17 56 00	Sa(pec)	0.03759
D 042	16 01 07.0	17 43 18	Sc	—
BO 102	16 01 53.0	17 57 59	G	—
D 005	16 01 54.7	17 20 28	Sdm	0.03484
D 025	16 02 04.8	17 34 19	S	0.03604
D 122	16 02 07.8	18 16 28	Sc	0.03625
PGC 56936	16 02 08.1	18 00 50	SB0a	0.03726
NGC 6040B	16 02 11.4	17 52 40	S0(pec)	0.04115
D 103	16 02 11.5	18 07 24	S0a	—
NGC 6040A	16 02 11.8	17 53 11	SABc	0.04208
CGCG 108-098	16 02 15.2	17 36 16	SABc	0.03970
sc1	16 02 16.9	17 23 05	S0	—
D 021	16 02 23.3	17 29 07	S(pec)	—
BO 128	16 02 24.3	18 10 17	G	—
CGCG 108-108	16 02 30.1	17 35 01	Sc	0.03547
D 020	16 02 32.0	17 29 00	Sc	0.03539
sc2	16 02 41.4	17 22 58	S0	—
D 129	16 02 44.5	18 19 22	S	0.03788
NGC 6044	16 02 44.9	18 07 17	S0	0.03314
mcg+03-46-085	16 02 49.3	17 42 57	G	—
D 049	16 02 52.0	17 47 02	Sc	0.03398
NGC 6045	16 02 53.1	17 53 35	SBc	0.03331
BO 119	16 02 55.7	17 59 21	Sc	0.03304
BO 107	16 02 57.3	17 33 29	Sc	—
IC 1173	16 02 57.4	17 33 28	SABc	0.03482
PGC 57042	16 03 00.2	17 40 28	G	0.04102
D 061	16 03 00.8	17 50 35	S0	0.03146
BO 076	16 03 01.0	17 44 21	S0a	—
IC 1179	16 03 07.3	17 53 15	SBcd	0.03712
NGC 6050	16 03 08.0	17 53 32	Sc	0.03178
UGC 10190	16 03 11.4	17 49 54	Scd	0.03679
D 098	16 03 11.8	18 02 41	SBb	0.04128
D090	16 03 12.7	17 57 54	Sc?	0.03420
D 097	16 03 14.6	18 03 47	S0a	0.03971

Table 4.1.—Continued

Galaxy	RA (B1950)	Dec (B1950)	Morphology	z
NGC 6054	16 03 15.6	17 54 10	SABb	0.03716
NGC 6056	16 03 16.6	18 05 54	SB0	0.03898
D 079	16 03 19.1	17 54 17	E	0.03413
sc4	16 03 20.4	17 30 36	S0	—
Mk 299	16 03 21.4	17 26 29	S(pec)	0.03699
IC 1182	16 03 21.9	17 56 12	S0(pec)	0.03378
IC 1186	16 03 28.8	17 29 49	SBb(pec)	0.03683
IC 1185	16 03 24.6	17 51 04	Sab	0.03466
D 038	16 03 30.3	17 42 59	Sc	0.04072
CGCG 108-135	16 03 31.6	18 09 04	SBb	0.03704
D 119	16 03 34.6	18 15 16	S0	0.03658
D 018	16 03 38.5	17 28 29	Sc	0.03424
CGCG 108-139	16 03 45.6	18 19 48	SABbc	0.03842
CGCG 108-138	16 03 47.4	18 14 47	SABbc	0.03683
D 108	16 03 51.0	18 10 12	Sb	0.04066
IC 1188A	16 03 52.1	17 35 35	SABa	0.03569
BO 129	16 03 55.5	17 50 10	Sbc	—
D 012	16 03 56.6	17 26 08	SBb	0.03346
D 100	16 03 59.2	18 05 07	SABcd	0.03849
IC 1189	16 04 00.4	18 19 01	SB0a	0.03890
IC 1193	16 04 17.0	17 50 47	SAB0	0.04014
IC 1192	16 04 18.2	17 54 32	Sb	0.03852
CGCG 108-149	16 04 20.4	18 01 33	SABb	0.03685
D 054	16 04 21.0	17 49 47	S	0.03992
D 089	16 04 23.5	17 59 00	E	—
IC 1195	16 04 25.3	17 19 29	SBbc	0.03990
D 036	16 04 25.6	17 43 31	Sdm	0.04078
CGCG 108-154	16 04 33.0	17 37 32	Sb	0.03723
D 045	16 04 33.2	17 46 53	Irr	0.03736
D 087	16 04 42.2	17 59 22	Sb	0.03842
ce1	16 04 45.8	17 41 59	Scd	—
PGC 57214	16 05 09.2	17 47 39	Sb	0.03855

Table 4.2. All cluster galaxies brighter than $B_T = 18.0$ and known redshifts, but with no H α detections.

Galaxy	RA (B1950)	Dec (B1950)	Morphology	z
D 069	16 01 03.2	17 52 10	E	0.03505
PGC 56919	16 01 52.1	17 43 04	S0	0.03852
D 104	16 01 55.4	18 07 02	SB0	0.03875
PGC 56945	16 02 13.7	17 47 03	S0	0.03787
NGC 6041A	16 02 20.8	17 51 24	E	0.03481
NGC 6042	16 02 24.6	17 50 11	S0	0.03529
D 110	16 02 25.4	18 10 04	S0	0.03756
BO 064	16 02 27.2	17 49 08	Sa	0.03479
D 051	16 02 27.7	17 46 27	SB0a	0.03373
PGC 57000	16 02 34.0	17 46 46	S0a	0.03892
NGC 6043A	16 02 46.5	17 54 37	SAB0	0.03340
PGC 57020	16 02 47.0	17 57 57	S0	0.03601
NGC 6047	16 02 54.0	17 51 54	E	0.03154
PGC 57047	16 03 03.6	17 47 25	E	0.03166
PGC 57052	16 03 07.3	18 06 18	S0	0.03953
PGC 57055	16 03 07.8	17 59 22	SB0a	0.03614
PGC 57071	16 03 14.7	17 48 56	Sa	0.03698
NGC 6055	16 03 18.1	18 17 38	SAB0	0.03762
IC 1183	16 03 23.2	17 54 04	SAB0	0.03348
NGC 6053	16 03 25.1	18 17 55	E	0.03480
CGCG 108-129	16 03 25.4	18 11 25	SBa	0.03934
PGC 57092	16 03 26.4	18 14 33	E	0.03792
PGC 57106	16 03 34.8	17 36 49	E	0.03421
PGC 57112	16 03 37.7	17 26 31	E	0.03245
PGC 57115	16 03 41.3	17 49 40	S0	0.03849
PGC 57119	16 03 45.9	18 12 57	E	0.03760
PGC 57123	16 03 48.1	17 50 08	E	0.03612
PGC 57133	16 03 59.2	18 12 42	S0	0.03670
PGC 57143	16 04 05.9	17 55 17	S0	0.03986
D 096	16 04 07.8	18 03 45	S0	0.03500
D 055	16 04 21.0	17 51 22	S0	0.03667
PGC 57162	16 04 21.5	17 55 45	E	0.03923
IC 1194A	16 04 23.7	17 54 58	SAB0a	0.03733
IC 1194	16 04 24.4	17 53 40	S0(pec)	0.03883

Table 4.2.—Continued

Galaxy	RA (B1950)	Dec (B1950)	Morphology	z
PGC 57183	16 04 33.1	17 55 22	E	0.04190
PGC 57198	16 04 51.3	17 58 55	S0	0.03863
D 053	16 05 02.1	17 49 44	S0	0.03662

Table 4.3. All HI detections in the Dickey (1997) survey that fall within the current study area.

Galaxy	RA (B1950)	Dec (B1950)	v (km/sec)	M_{ext}	H α ?
ne-142	16 04 07.9	18 08 04	11711	10.4	n
IC 1189	16 04 00.1	18 19 05	11822	14.1	y
D 100	16 03 59.2	18 05 13	11556	26.4	y
mct 14	16 03 51.5	18 17 23	11467	20.0	n
CGCG 108-138	16 03 47.1	18 14 41	11035	23.0	y
CGCG 108-139	16 03 45.2	18 19 49	11179	28.1	y
D 129	16 02 44.8	18 19 23	11334	16.6	y
(FGC237A) D 122	16 02 06.5	18 16 33	10868	30.5	y
ce-042	16 03 45.3	17 53 56	11919	19.4	n
ce-048	16 03 40.8	17 50 41	11145	10.5	n
ce-060	16 03 29.7	17 50 23	11100	11.7	n
ce-061 (i1182)	16 03 26.3	17 56 03	10104	99.1	y
ce-070	16 03 27.2	17 53 06	11654	15.4	n
ce-086 (i1182)	16 03 18.3	17 56 53	10458	10.9	n
NGC 6054	16 03 15.6	17 54 08	11189	68.5	y
UGC 10190	16 03 11.2	17 50 06	11100	53.7	y
NGC 6050 + IC 1179	16 03 07.4	17 53 22	11034	28.3	y
ce-137	16 03 06.9	17 36 33	11632	26.5	n
ce-143	16 03 05.8	18 00 07	11587	8.9	n
ce-155	16 03 06.4	17 36 30	11620	29.3	n
D 033 (PGC 57042)	16 03 00.0	17 40 51	11410	24.9	y
IC 1173	16 02 59.7	17 33 53	10281	19.9	y
BO 119	16 02 55.1	17 59 26	9905	14.7	y
NGC 6047	16 02 53.6	17 51 46	11698	22.8	n
NGC 6045	16 02 51.3	17 53 27	10204	12.2	y
ce-200	16 02 51.8	17 55 06	9927	4.8	y
ce-224	16 02 43.3	17 38 05	11941	15.1	n
CGCG 108-108	16 02 29.9	17 34 56	10635	87.3	y
CGCG 108-098	16 02 15.2	17 36 23	11875	23.4	y
D 020	16 02 32.5	17 29 03	10535	26.6	y
D 005	16 01 54.5	17 20 35	10446	33.6	y

4.3.2 Broadband Photometry

All three nights of the Kitt Peak observing run were photometric. In order to photometrically calibrate the data, observations of Landolt (1992) standard star fields were obtained each night.

Total magnitudes and colors were extracted for the samples of $H\alpha$ detected and non-detected galaxies. Face on total magnitudes and colors were calculated using the k corrections of Coleman et al. (1980) and color excesses derived using the interstellar extinction curve of Reike & Lebofsky (1985). The foreground extinction due to material within our own galaxy was estimated as in RC3 using the technique of Burstein & Heiles (1984), which uses a combination of the observed HI column density within our galaxy, along with number counts of faint galaxies to derive the extinction and reddening along different lines of sight. Axis ratios were derived for the galaxies by fitting elliptical isophotes to the galaxies in the B band. Instead of determining the axis ratio at a prescribed surface brightness level, areas in the outer part of the galaxy where the run of ellipticity with radius was fairly constant were used to determine the axis ratios. Galaxies that were morphologically typed only as S were given internal extinction corrections and k corrections appropriate for an Sc galaxy (i.e. they were given the maximum internal extinction correction). Galaxies that were typed only as G (i.e. no morphological type was assignable) were given no internal extinction correction, but were k corrected as if they were early type galaxies.

The derived magnitudes and colors are presented in Table 4.4 for the $H\alpha$ detected sample, and in Table 4.5 for the $H\alpha$ non-detections. Two overlapping pairs of galaxies (NGC 6040A+B and IC 1179+NGC 6050) in the $H\alpha$ detected sample have colors reported, but no total magnitudes. In both systems, the photometry was performed within apertures that minimized the contamination due to the other member of the pair. In both cases the paired galaxies had similar

colors, so that the extracted colors should be fairly reliable. The difficulty in cleanly separating the systems for the purpose of determining total magnitudes is the reason no total magnitudes are quoted for these systems. Total magnitudes derived from the Lowell data for NGC 6040A+B are quoted in Chapter 2, because the lower quality images derived at Lowell suggested that a fairly clean separation was possible. The deeper images taken in better seeing conditions at Kitt Peak show that NGC 6040B possesses an extensive, low surface brightness disk that overlaps that of NGC 6040A. This suggests that the total magnitudes for this system presented in Chapter 2 be treated with appropriate caution.

A comparison of the total magnitudes derived here with those from RC3 and those presented in Chapter 2 from observations taken at the Lowell Observatory is given in Figure 4.3. This figure reveals that there seems to be a systematic offset between B_T 's derived here and those from other sources, primarily RC3. The relationship between the different sources of photometry is linear and has a slope of one, but with a zero point offset of 0.11 mag, in the sense that the magnitudes presented here are fainter than those presented in RC3. The scatter around the mean relation is consistent with the estimated errors in the photometry. Buta & Corwin (1986) presented photometry of galaxies in the Hercules cluster derived from surface photometry of film copies of plates collected at Kitt Peak. Both Buta & Corwin (1986) and RC3 note that the photometry derived from the films is fainter than that derived from photo-electric aperture photometry of Hercules cluster galaxies by approximately 0.1 magnitude. Because the photometric system of RC3 is determined by the photo-electric aperture photometry, this suggests that the difference between the photometry presented here and that in RC3 may be due to a zero point error in the RC3 photometry for galaxies in the Hercules cluster of 0.1 magnitudes. In order to test the idea, a plot of the photometry in common between this study and that derived from the Kitt Peak films by Buta & Corwin (1986) is presented in Figure 4.4. This plot shows no zero point offset between

the data from the two sources, suggesting that the observed offset is indeed due to a zero point error in the aperture photometry presented in RC3.

A comparison of the $(B - R)_T$ colors derived here with other photometry is given in Figure 4.5. The derived colors are compared with two sources, the $(B - R)_T$ colors derived from the Lowell Observatory data presented in Chapter 2, and with the relationship between $(B - V)_T$ and $(B - R)_T$ colors found using the data presented in RC3 and Buta & Williams (1995). There is generally good agreement between the colors presented here and those from other sources.

Figure 4.3. Comparison of total B magnitudes measured here with those from RC3 and the Lowell Observatory.

Figure 4.4. Comparison of total B magnitudes measured here with those from Buta & Corwin (1986).

Figure 4.5. Comparison of broad band colors measured here with those from other sources. The top panel compares the $(B - R)_T$ colors presented here, with those obtained at the Lowell Observatory. The bottom panel compares the $(B - R)_T$ colors with $(B - V)_T$ colors from RC3. The open symbols are galaxies from the reference sample, while the closed symbols are Hercules cluster galaxies.

Table 4.4. Broadband Photometry of bright Abell 2151 H α detected galaxies derived from Kitt Peak data.

Galaxy	B_T	B_T^0	$(B - R)_T$	$(B - R)_T^0$
D 084	16.27	15.96	1.17	0.93
D 042	17.02	16.73	0.91	0.72
BO 102	17.54	17.26	1.43	0.87
D 005	17.42	16.50	1.45	0.96
D 025	16.98	15.96	1.35	0.79
D 122	17.07	15.93	1.29	1.07
PGC 56936	16.39	16.11	1.33	1.11
NGC 6040B	—	—	1.42:	0.99:
D 103	16.88	16.60	1.55	1.33
NGC 6040A	—	—	1.53:	1.41:
CGCG 108-098	16.07	15.60	1.15	0.87
sc1	17.70	17.42	1.41	1.19
D 021	17.25	16.91	1.32	1.11
BO 128	17.81	17.37	1.14	0.92
CGCG 108-108	15.63	15.30	1.15	0.94
D 020	16.63	16.04	1.28	0.94
sc2	17.96	17.68	1.46	1.24
D 129	17.16	16.12	1.47	1.25
NGC 6044	15.29	15.01	1.58	1.36
MCG+03-46-085	17.62	16.96	1.20	0.84
D 049	17.16	16.86	1.28	1.10
NGC 6045	15.05	13.89	1.55	0.92
BO 119	17.25	16.78	1.01	0.73
BO 107	17.35	16.76	0.75	0.41
IC 1173	15.60	14.91	1.48	1.09
PGC 57042	16.62	15.49	1.36	0.74
D 061	17.01	16.73	1.66	1.44
BO 076	17.19	16.91	1.41	1.19
IC 1179	—	—	1.18:	0.97:
NGC 6050	—	—	1.31:	1.09:
UGC 10190	16.89	15.89	1.30	0.75
D 098	16.03	15.14	1.57	1.04
D 090	16.72	15.80	1.45	0.94
D 097	16.52	16.24	1.62	1.40

Table 4.4.—Continued

Galaxy	B_T	B_T^0	$(B - R)_T$	$(B - R)_T^0$
NGC 6054	15.87	15.34	1.25	0.90
NGC 6056	14.98	14.70	1.57	1.35
D 079	16.96	16.68	1.10	0.88
sc4	17.56	17.28	1.24	1.02
Mk 299	16.51	16.32	0.88	0.76
IC 1182	15.27	14.99	1.53	1.31
IC 1186	15.59	15.02	1.48	1.11
IC 1185	15.16	14.69	1.55	1.13
D 038	17.18	16.92	0.92	0.75
CGCG 108-135	16.20	15.76	1.50	1.18
D 119	17.15	16.87	1.26	1.04
D 018	16.79	16.46	1.07	0.86
CGCG 108-139	15.63	15.03	1.48	0.88
CGCG 108-138	15.58	15.28	1.06	0.89
D 108	16.82	16.18	1.33	1.18
IC 1188A	15.73	15.29	1.55	1.25
BO 129	17.84	17.16	1.28	0.91
D 012	16.09	15.26	1.44	0.94
D 100	16.42	16.21	0.91	0.76
IC 1189	15.37	15.09	1.41	1.19
IC 1193	15.72	15.44	1.83	1.61
IC 1192	16.06	15.22	1.69	1.18
CGCG 108-149	16.25	15.53	1.46	1.16
D 054	17.08	16.17	1.59	1.05
D 089	17.91	17.63	1.38	1.16
IC 1195	15.72	15.33	1.42	1.20
D 036	16.79	16.47	0.73	0.54
CGCG 108-154	15.84	15.49	1.15	0.87
D 045	16.69	15.86	1.37	0.92
D 087	16.96	15.94	1.49	1.27
ce1	16.88	16.43	0.97	0.72
PGC 57214	15.94	15.38	1.39	1.03

Table 4.5. Broadband Photometry of bright Abell 2151 galaxies with no H α detections derived from Kitt Peak data.

Galaxy	B_T	B_T^0	$(B - R)_T$	$(B - R)_T^0$
D 069	16.40	16.12	1.59	1.37
PGC 56919	17.22	16.94	1.59	1.37
D 104	16.86	16.58	1.50	1.28
PGC 56945	17.05	16.77	1.74	1.52
NGC 6041A	14.14	13.86	1.65	1.43
NGC 6042	15.01	14.73	1.60	1.38
D 110	16.81	16.53	1.69	1.47
BO 064	16.79	16.13	1.53	1.12
D 051	16.98	16.70	1.70	1.48
PGC 57000	17.46	17.18	1.57	1.35
NGC 6043A	15.38	15.10	1.63	1.41
PGC 57020	16.56	16.28	1.67	1.45
NGC 6047	14.60	14.32	1.65	1.43
PGC 57047	17.61	17.33	1.59	1.37
PGC 57052	17.17	16.89	1.59	1.37
PGC 57055	16.38	16.10	1.62	1.40
PGC 57071	16.16	15.78	1.64	1.41
NGC 6055	14.82	14.54	1.60	1.38
IC 1183	15.22	14.94	1.60	1.38
NGC 6053	15.70	15.42	1.60	1.38
CGCG 108-129	15.72	15.35	1.57	1.31
PGC 57092	16.44	16.16	1.51	1.29
PGC 57106	17.00	16.72	1.54	1.32
PGC 57112	16.90	16.62	1.45	1.23
PGC 57115	17.50	17.22	1.59	1.37
PGC 57119	16.86	16.58	1.62	1.40
PGC 57123	17.39	17.11	1.52	1.30
PGC 57133	17.36	17.08	1.59	1.37
PGC 57143	17.17	16.89	1.70	1.48
D 096	16.58	16.30	1.63	1.41
D 055	16.37	16.09	1.51	1.29
PGC 57162	17.22	16.94	1.76	1.54
IC 1194A	16.31	16.03	1.68	1.46
IC 1194	15.31	15.03	1.74	1.52

Table 4.5.—Continued

Galaxy	B_T	B_T^0	$(B - R)_T$	$(B - R)_T^0$
PGC 57183	16.99	16.71	1.52	1.30
PGC 57198	16.47	16.19	1.73	1.51
D 053	16.52	16.24	1.63	1.41

4.3.2.1 Low Surface Brightness Galaxies

While the majority of the HI detections in Dickey's (1997) survey that were also observed in this work have fairly high surface brightness, there are eight systems that seemed to meet the description of low surface brightness galaxies (Bothun, Impey, & McGaugh 1997). In order to facilitate comparison of these galaxies with other low surface brightness galaxies, basic photometric parameters for these galaxies were extracted using the same techniques used by workers who study low surface brightness galaxies (O'Neil, Bothun, & Cornell 1997a; O'Neil, Bothun, Schombert, Cornell, & Impey 1997b).

Surface brightness profiles were derived for the galaxies by fitting ellipses to the surface brightness distribution of the galaxies as a function of radius, where the ellipticity and position angle were allowed to vary in the fit, but not the center of the ellipse. The fixed position of the center for each galaxy was determined from a centroid of the pixel values around the brightness peak of that galaxy. The fits were used to determine a best value for the ellipticity and position angle for the galaxy. Surface brightness profiles were then extracted by fixing the ellipse parameters at the determined best values. An exponential surface brightness profile was then fit to each galaxy, in order to derive the central surface brightness and scale length for the galaxy. When expressed in magnitudes/arcsecond², the exponential profile reduces to

$$\mu(r) = \mu(0) + \left(\frac{1.086}{\alpha}\right)r \quad (4.1)$$

where $\mu(r)$ is the surface brightness at radius r , $\mu(0)$ is the central surface brightness, and α is the exponential scale length. Six of the eight candidate low surface brightness galaxies had sufficient extent for surface brightness profiles to be obtained. The profiles for these galaxies are plotted in Figure 4.6, along with the best fit exponential profile in each case. For the remaining two galaxies (ce-060 and ce-224) there is a faint optical object near the center of the region of HI

emission; however, in each case the region is compact and shows no sign of diffuse structure.

Total magnitudes for each galaxy were determined from integration of the fit surface brightness profiles. Functionally, this means that the the magnitude was deduced from the fit parameters using

$$m(\alpha) = \mu_B(0) - 2.5 \log(2\pi\alpha^2) \quad (4.2)$$

where $\mu_B(0)$ is the central surface brightness in the B band in magnitudes/arcsecond², and α is the exponential scale length, in arcseconds. Inclinations for the galaxies were determined from the minor to major axis ratios q determined from the ellipse fitting using

$$i = \cos^{-1} q. \quad (4.3)$$

Inclination corrected central surface brightness were calculated using

$$\mu_B(0)_c = \mu_B(0) - 2.5 \log(\cos i). \quad (4.4)$$

Notice this is only a geometric projection correction and does not include any correction for internal extinction, which is expected to be negligible in low surface brightness galaxies (O'Neil et al. 1997a). Examination of the derived $\mu_B(0)_C$ values shows that five of the six galaxies fit the definition of low surface brightness galaxies, in having central surface brightness of 23 mag/arcsec² or fainter (Bothun et al. 1997).

The radius of the galaxies at the $\mu_B = 27.0\text{mag/arcsec}^2$ isophote (r_{27}) was determined from the exponential fit. Colors for the galaxies were extracted using apertures with a radius of r_{27} , centered on the galaxy center used in the ellipse fitting. For the 2 objects with no obvious spatial extent, the magnitudes and colors were determined using an aperture of radius approximately 4 arcseconds. The magnitudes and colors for the two compact objects are also given in Table 4.6.

Figure 4.6. B band surface brightness profiles of the candidate low surface brightness galaxies detected in HI. The straight lines are the best fit exponential profiles.

Table 4.6. Measured properties of the low surface brightness galaxies.

Galaxy	$\mu_B(0)$	α (kpc)	i ($^\circ$)	r_{27} ($''$)	$m(\alpha)$	$\mu_B(0)_c$	B-R
NE-142	23.59	2.94	46	12.8	18.54	23.99	0.86
MCT 14	23.89	3.75	46	15.0	18.31	24.29	0.77
CE-042	23.48	3.39	37	15.3	18.11	23.72	0.66
CE-048	22.37	1.30	53	7.3	19.07	22.92	0.44
CE-060	22.99	2.52	64	13.0	18.26	23.89	1.07
CE-070	—	—	—	—	21.16	—	0.66
CE-200	22.02	1.92	46	12.3	17.88	22.41	0.86
CE-224	—	—	—	—	21.21	—	2.35

Examination of the colors for the six galaxies with extended structure shows that they are fairly blue, which is normal for HI rich low surface brightness galaxies.

The nature of the two faint, compact objects associated with ce-070 and ce-224 is unclear. They may simply be faint stars superposed along the line of sight to the HI clouds. Alternatively, they may represent the small portion of otherwise extremely low surface brightness galaxies that have high enough surface brightness to be detected. Optical spectroscopy of the objects will be necessary to decide between these two possibilities.

4.3.3 H α Observations

The H α images were continuum subtracted using the R band frames. The first step in continuum subtraction was to register the two images. Because the focus position for the R and narrow band filters was slightly different, there is a slight scale difference between the on and off band images. To correct for this, a geometric transformation between the two frames was calculated using 20-25 unsaturated stars common to both frames. The frames were registered by applying this geometric transformation to the R band frame. Sky values were then estimated and subtracted from both frames using several source free regions

on the registered frames. After background subtraction, scale factors between the two frames were determined using aperture photometry of stars on both frames. This scale factor was applied to the R frame, which was then subtracted from the narrow band frame. Continuum subtraction was an iterative process, which proceeded until the determined scale factor was judged to be adequate, using the stellar residuals in the continuum subtracted frames.

$H\alpha$ sources were identified by eye on the continuum subtracted images. This technique has the disadvantage of being somewhat subjective in terms of the threshold at which an object is determined to be detected, but this is more than made up for by the ability of human eye and mind to spot and discard from consideration the many spurious sources present in any such continuum subtracted image, due to such things as saturated stars, etc.

Two parameters were extracted from the narrow band data, $H\alpha$ equivalent widths (as defined in Chapter 2), and $H\alpha + [NII]$ fluxes. In order to photometrically calibrate the $H\alpha + [NII]$ data, nightly observations were obtained of 2-3 spectrophotometric standards from the listing of Massey et al. (1988). Flux calibration was accomplished using the procedure presented in Jacoby, Quigley, & Africano (1987). The basic parameters of the narrow band filters used in this study are given in Table 4.7, and the transmission curves for the filters are plotted in Figure 4.7. The derived $H\alpha$ parameters for the detected galaxies that were brighter than $B_T = 18.0$ are given in Table 4.8. The data for the overlapping galaxy pairs NGC 6040A+B and IC 1179+NGC 6050 are marked with colons in Table 4.8 because of the inevitable contamination of the quoted values with emission from the other member of the pair. The fluxes are more affected by this problem than the equivalent widths; however, the uncertainties in both quantities for these systems are undoubtedly higher than that for the other galaxies for which data is presented.

The equivalent widths measured here were examined in two ways for any signs

Table 4.7. Central wavelength, effective widths, and peak transmissions for the Kitt Peak narrow band filters.

Filter number	λ_{center} (Å)	W_{eff} (Å)	T_{peak}
1497	6786	79.4	0.650
1498	6832	77.0	0.674

of systematic errors. The first comparison is with the equivalent widths derived in Chapter 2 from the Lowell Observatory data, which are shown plotted versus the equivalent widths derived from the Kitt Peak data in Figure 4.8 as open diamonds. The quantities follow a line with slope one, and have the expected scatter around that line of 10 to 20%. Since the fields observed from Kitt Peak were overlapped with one another by 1 to 2 arcminutes, this allowed a second check on the derived equivalent widths, by comparing equivalent widths for galaxies that occurred near the border of two fields. Galaxies for which measurements were possible on two different frames are also plotted in Figure 4.8 as filled circles, and also follow the line of slope one with a scatter of only 5% around the mean.

Images in both R and continuum subtracted $H\alpha + [NII]$ for the galaxies with the twenty highest $H\alpha + [NII]$ fluxes are given in Figure 4.9. The image intensities have been scaled for each image to show the greatest range in detail. Each image has been reproduced to the same pixel scale, where a linear scale of one arcminute is indicated at the top of each page of images. For $H_0 = 75\text{km/sec/Mpc}$ and $q_0 = 0$, one arcminute corresponds to a physical scale of 43 kpc at the distance of the Hercules cluster.

Figure 4.7. Transmission curves for the narrow band filters used during the Kitt Peak observing run.

Table 4.8. $H\alpha$ measurements for bright galaxies in Abell 2151.

Galaxy	EW($H\alpha$ + $[NII]$)	$-\log(f(H\alpha + [NII]))$
D 084	40.8	13.10
D 042	31.6	13.60
BO 102	27.2	13.64
D 005	47.4	13.36
D 025	22.3	13.55
D 122	35.9	13.46
PGC 56939	7.4	13.80
NGC 6040B	18.0:	13.20:
D 103	19.9	13.51
NGC 6040A	16.0:	13.12:
CGCG 108-098	30.8	13.13
sc1	23.4	13.79
D 021	20.4	13.71
BO 128	20.1	14.05
CGCG 108-108	26.8	13.01
D 020	23.9	13.41
sc2	52.8	13.93
D 129	28.0	13.60
NGC 6044	3.2	13.73
mcg+03-46-085	52.2	13.51
D 049	13.6	13.87
NGC 6045	20.3	12.72
BO 119	23.8	14.11
BO 107	57.4	13.57
IC 1173	12.0	13.22
PGC 57042	45.3	13.12
D 061	15.0	13.63
BO 076	24.3	13.59
IC 1179	23.6:	13.55:
NGC 6050	24.6:	13.18:
UGC 10190	21.4	13.67
D 098	13.8	13.40
D 090	30.0	13.31
D 097	13.0	13.53

Table 4.8.—Continued

Galaxy	EW($H\alpha$ + $[NII]$)	$-\log(f(H\alpha + [NII]))$
NGC 6054	26.4	13.10
NGC 6056	6.0	13.28
D 079	59.8	13.15
sc4	22.3	13.83
Mk 299	51.4	13.19
IC 1182	39.4	12.60
IC 1186	8.5	13.36
IC 1185	7.5	13.29
D 038	42.3	13.55
CGCG 108-135	7.0	13.68
D 119	47.3	13.35
D 018	25.6	13.52
CGCG 108-139	14.1	13.16
CGCG 108-138	27.9	13.22
D 108	13.2	13.72
IC 1188A	7.8	13.43
BO 129	53.6	13.59
D 012	15.8	13.31
D 100	29.2	13.39
IC 1189	17.1	13.00
IC1193	8.5	13.27
IC 1192	12.9	13.30
CGCG 108-149	18.6	13.28
D 054	3.3	14.36
D 089	19.0	14.01
IC 1195	17.3	13.13
D 036	26.9	13.71
CGCG 108-154	27.0	13.10
D 045	17.7	13.55
D 087	6.1	14.05
ce1	19.4	13.75
PGC 57214	12.8	13.36

Figure 4.8. Comparison of equivalent widths from different sources.

Figure 4.9. R band (left) and $H\alpha + [NII]$ (right) images of the 20 Hercules galaxies with the highest $H\alpha + [NII]$ fluxes.

Figure 4.9. —Continued.

Figure 4.9. —Continued.

4.4 Photometric Results

The broadband, $H\alpha$, and morphological properties for the different subsamples of galaxies are examined in this section, primarily to search for galaxies that have either an excess or deficit of $H\alpha$ emission. The basic properties of the HI detected galaxies are also briefly discussed.

4.4.1 The $H\alpha$ Bright Galaxies

The $H\alpha$ equivalent width is plotted against the broadband color in Figure 4.10, and against morphological type in Figure 4.11. The open diamonds are galaxies from the field reference sample, as discussed in section 3.4, while the filled circles are the Hercules cluster galaxies. Examination of Figure 4.10 reveals two notable points. First, the majority of $H\alpha$ emitting galaxies in Hercules follow the relation for normal field galaxies, suggesting that they are normal, star forming systems. Second, although the majority of galaxies on this plot are normal star forming galaxies, there is a population of galaxies with excess $H\alpha$ emission for their colors. Examination of Figure 4.11 shows several early type systems with exceptional $H\alpha$ emission for their type. On the other hand, the later type spirals show distributions that are consistent with their field counterparts.

There are two galaxies in the cluster sample with exceptionally blue colors, fully 0.2 magnitudes bluer than the bluest galaxies in the field sample, which are apparent in Figure 4.10. Both galaxies are late type spirals; BO 107 and D 036. BO 107 is highly inclined to the line of sight, and thus according to the recipe of RC3 for internal extinction correction required a fairly substantial correction to its $(B - R)_T$ color. If this galaxy contained significantly less dust than assumed by the RC3 inclination correction, it would require a less severe correction, making its color more consistent with the bluest field galaxies. On the other hand, the $H\alpha$ equivalent width of this galaxy is very high, so the observed color may well be

Figure 4.10. Comparison of broadband color and $H\alpha + [NII]$ equivalent width for the galaxies brighter than $B_T = 18.0$ in the Hercules cluster.

Figure 4.11. Comparison of Hubble type and $H\alpha + [NII]$ equivalent width for the galaxies brighter than $B_T = 18.0$ in the Hercules cluster.

correct. The correction due to internal extinction in D 036 is only 0.11 magnitudes, suggesting it truly represents an exceptionally blue system.

In order to examine the dependence of the cluster galaxies $H\alpha$ emission on both color and morphological type simultaneously, the parameters r_{phot} and r_{morp} (as defined in subsection 3.4.1) were again calculated, and are plotted against one another in Figure 4.12, using the same symbols as in the previous plots. Galaxies for which a reliable morphological type was not assignable (those with types S and G) were assigned r_{morp} values of zero, and so their data points appear along the r_{phot} axis in Figure 4.12. To examine the distribution of galaxies of different morphological type in the r_{phot} - r_{morp} plane, separate versions of Figure 4.12 were plotted in Figure 4.13 for early type (Sa and earlier) and late type galaxies (Sab and later).

Examination of Figure 4.13 shows that most of the $H\alpha$ detected early type galaxies have an excess of $H\alpha$ emission. A two dimensional Kolmogorov-Smirnov test shows that the distribution of Hercules cluster and field galaxies would be drawn from the same parent population only one time in one thousand. In contrast, the diagram for the late type galaxies shows that as a population, the late type Hercules cluster galaxies are indistinguishable from similar field galaxies, having neither a population of $H\alpha$ excess or $H\alpha$ deficient systems. This is a strong confirmation of the results found in Chapter 3, that unrelaxed clusters such as the Hercules cluster have spiral galaxies that are normal when compared to field galaxies, but do possess a population of early type galaxies with significant $H\alpha$ excesses.

4.4.2 The $H\alpha$ Excess Galaxies

Basic data for all the galaxies that meet the definition of having an $H\alpha$ excess of r_{phot} or $r_{morp} > 2.0$ for Sab and later type galaxies, and of $r_{phot} > 4.0$ or $r_{morp} > 10.0$ for types Sa and earlier, are given in Table 4.9. The absolute magnitudes have

Figure 4.12. The distribution of r_{phot} versus r_{morp} for the Hercules cluster galaxies.

Figure 4.13. The distribution of r_{phot} versus r_{morp} for the early type (upper panel), and late type (lower panel) Hercules cluster galaxies.

been calculated from B_T^0 , assuming $H_0 = 75\text{km/sec/Mpc}$ and $q_0 = 0$, and a mean redshift for the Hercules cluster of $z = 0.370$. As in Chapter 3, the $H\alpha + [NII]$ equivalent width and the logarithm of the $H\alpha + [NII]$ luminosity are tabulated, since the equivalent width gives a measure of the star formation rate per unit mass in the galaxy, while the luminosity gives a measure of the global star formation rate. The number of M^* Sc galaxies needed to produce the equivalent $H\alpha + [NII]$ luminosity has been calculated, and is given in the final column of the table. The values for NGC 6040B and IC 1182 should be treated as upper limits on the star formation rates in these systems, since both of them have signs of containing AGN that contribute significantly to their $H\alpha$ emission.

Examination of the $H\alpha$ parameters for the early type $H\alpha$ excess systems shows that they have equivalent widths comparable to normal Sc galaxies, suggesting that they are forming stars at the same rate as an Sc galaxy of similar mass. The $H\alpha + [NII]$ luminosities of these systems shows that their global star formation is modest, roughly 10-50% of that of a large Sc galaxy. This means that while these galaxies have significantly high star formation rates for their types, they are contributing only a minor fraction of the total star formation in the cluster.

4.4.3 The Color-Magnitude Diagram

Sandage & Visvanathan (1978) pointed out that the small intrinsic scatter of the colors of early type galaxies around the color-magnitude relation constrains the formation and evolution of early type galaxies. The low scatter of the color-magnitude relations of E and S0 galaxies in the Virgo and Coma clusters suggests that these galaxies evolved in a synchronized fashion (Bower, Lucey, & Ellis 1992). Indeed, Butcher & Oemler (1984) used the fraction of galaxies 0.2 magnitudes bluer than the early type galaxy color-magnitude relation to first show that there was evolution of the cluster galaxy population as a function of redshift. More recently, Van Dokkum, Franx, Kelson, Illingworth, Fisher, & Fabricant (1998)

Table 4.9. Basic data for the H α excess galaxies in the Hercules cluster.

Galaxy	Hubble Type	r_{phot}	r_{morph}	M_B	EW Å	$\log(L_{H\alpha+[NII]})$ ergs/sec	# Sc's
D 084	Sa(pec)	1.38	34.00	-20.13	40.8	41.32	1.10
NGC 6040B	S0(pec)	17.0	14.17	—	17.0	41.22	0.79
D 103	S0a	4.88	16.58	-19.49	19.9	40.91	0.43
sc1	S0	2.00	19.50	-18.67	23.4	40.63	0.22
sc2	S0	5.99	44.00	-18.41	52.8	40.49	0.16
D 129	S	3.39	—	-19.97	28.0	40.82	0.35
BO 107	Sc	0.72	2.06	-19.33	57.4	40.85	0.37
D 061	S0	15.00	12.50	-19.36	15.0	40.79	0.32
BO 076	S0a	2.08	20.25	-19.18	24.3	40.83	0.35
D 097	S0a	13.00	10.83	-19.85	13.0	40.89	0.41
NGC 6054	SABb	0.83	2.28	-20.75	26.4	41.32	1.10
D 079	E	1.79	49.83	-19.41	59.8	41.27	0.98
sc4	S0	0.98	18.58	-18.81	22.3	40.59	0.20
IC 1182	S0(pec)	7.76	32.83	-21.10	39.4	41.82	3.47
D 119	S0	2.21	39.42	-19.41	47.3	41.07	0.62
IC 1189	SB0a	1.46	14.25	-21.00	17.1	41.42	1.38
IC 1193	SAB0	8.50	7.08	-20.65	8.5	41.15	0.74
D 089	E	1.41	15.83	-18.46	19.0	40.41	0.13
CGCG 108-154	Sb	0.79	2.33	-20.60	27.0	41.32	1.10

have used the scatter in the color-magnitude relation in a cluster at $z = 0.33$ to argue for the evolution of cluster S0 galaxies at higher redshift.

Inspired by these works, a color magnitude diagram for the Hercules cluster was constructed, and is plotted in Figure 4.14. The $H\alpha$ detections are plotted as open diamonds, and the $H\alpha$ non-detections are plotted as filled circles. The early type galaxy color-magnitude relation was derived in two ways from the data. First a straight line was fit to the $H\alpha$ non-detections, and is plotted on Figure 4.14 as a solid line. The dashed line on the plot corresponds to the Butcher & Oemler (1984) selection criteria for blue galaxies using the $H\alpha$ non-detections fit to characterize the early type galaxy ridge-line. The best fit relation for the $H\alpha$ non-detections was found to be

$$(B - R)_T = 1.7998 - 0.01146B_T \quad (4.5)$$

with a scatter of $\sigma = 0.078$ around the fit.

The most common practice in deriving the color magnitude relation for early type galaxies is to select galaxies morphologically (typically all E and S0 galaxies for example), and use these galaxies to derive the color magnitude relation, with the caveat that all galaxies that are “too blue” are not included in the fitting process. Following this practice, the color magnitude relation for Abell 2151 was also derived using all the E and S0 galaxies for which photometry is presented in this chapter. The four bluest galaxies were excluded from the fit, resulting in the relation

$$(B - R)_T = 1.7131 - 0.006127B_T \quad (4.6)$$

with a scatter (among the points used in the fit only) of $\sigma = 0.087$. The color-magnitude diagram is re-plotted in Figure 4.15 with the spiral galaxies plotted as open diamonds, and the elliptical and S0 galaxies plotted as filled circles. The fit color-magnitude relation is over-plotted as a solid line, and the dashed line is again the Butcher & Oemler (1984) criteria for a galaxy to be considered to be

Figure 4.14. Color magnitude relation for Hercules cluster galaxies.

blue. Although the coefficients to this fit seem significantly different than those found for the $H\alpha$ non-detections, examination of Figure 4.15 where the fit derived using the $H\alpha$ non-detections is over-plotted as a dot-dashed line show that over the range of magnitudes considered here, the difference is negligible.

It is worthwhile at this point noting a few of the advantages of using an $H\alpha$ survey over just broadband photometric data to study the history of star formation in galaxy clusters. The first is evident when examining Figure 4.14; estimation of the number of currently star forming galaxies is much more accurate using the $H\alpha$ data. This is because a star forming galaxy may appear red due to internal dust absorption, but will normally still have detectable $H\alpha$ emission (notice all of the $H\alpha$ detections red-ward of the Butcher & Oemler [1984] blue galaxy line). The $H\alpha$ data is also useful for analyzing galaxies with no current star formation, because these systems are easily identified by their lack of $H\alpha$ emission. This is evidenced by the fact that the color-magnitude ridge-line is recovered using the $H\alpha$ non-detections, without the necessity of excluding any galaxies.

The main purpose of studying the $H\alpha$ non-detections is to search for any signs of recent star-bursts or truncated star formation in these galaxies. With this in mind, there are two points to be taken from the color-magnitude diagram in Figure 4.14. The first is that there are no galaxies that are blue according to the definition of Butcher & Oemler (1984) that were not also detected in $H\alpha$. The second is that there is relatively low scatter in the color magnitude relation of the $H\alpha$ non-detections, comparable to what Sandage & Visvanathan (1978) found in their study of nearby early type galaxies. This suggests that there is not a significant population of post starburst galaxies or galaxies with recently truncated star formation in the Hercules cluster.

Figure 4.15. Color magnitude relation for Hercules cluster galaxies, where the galaxies have now been segregated by morphological type.

4.4.4 $H\alpha$ Deficit Galaxies

The analysis of the $H\alpha$ detected galaxies on the $r_{phot}-r_{morph}$ diagram indicates that there is not an over abundance of $H\alpha$ deficient galaxies in the Hercules cluster, when compared to the field sample. In fact, only one $H\alpha$ detected galaxy shows a significant deficiency of $H\alpha$ emission, D 054. The analysis of the $H\alpha$ non-detections via the color magnitude diagram shows that none of those galaxies have colors blue enough to indicate that they have had their star formation recently truncated. Therefore, out of the 103 galaxies considered, only one seems to have suffered a recent diminution in its star formation. This is a dramatic confirmation of the result found in Chapter 3, that dynamically un-relaxed clusters such as the Hercules cluster have relatively few galaxies with truncated star formation, while clusters that are more relaxed have significant populations of $H\alpha$ deficient galaxies. In the Hercules cluster there is no evidence of a catastrophic truncation in the star formation in the cluster galaxies.

4.4.5 HI Detections: Basic Properties

In this section, the properties of the HI detected galaxies are briefly considered. The most relevant comparison of the HI properties of low and high surface brightness galaxies to date was presented by De Blok, McGaugh, & Van Der Hulst (1996). They find that at a given absolute magnitude, low surface brightness galaxies have significantly higher HI masses than galaxies of higher surface brightness. In order to examine this relationship for the Hercules cluster galaxies, two diagrams have been plotted, both of which are presented in Figure 4.16.

The upper plot is simply a plot of absolute blue magnitude against the logarithm of the HI mass. The low surface brightness galaxies have been plotted as open diamonds, while the higher surface brightness galaxies have been plotted as filled circles. Two lines are over-plotted on this diagram. The solid line is the fit

Figure 4.16. The upper panel plots absolute blue magnitude against the galaxies HI mass. The bottom panel shows a plot of central surface brightness versus the HI mass to blue luminosity ratio of the galaxy.

by De Blok et al. (1996) to the relation for their low surface brightness galaxies. The dashed line is also from a fit by De Blok et al. (1996), but this time to the field sample of higher surface brightness galaxies presented by De Jong (1995). The HI detected galaxies appear to be well represented by the relations found for galaxies of similar surface brightness by De Blok et al. (1996).

The bottom panel of Figure 4.16 is a plot of the HI mass to blue luminosity ratio versus the inclination corrected central surface brightness for the Hercules cluster galaxies, where all galaxies are now plotted with the same plotting symbol. In order to determine the central surface brightnesses for the higher surface brightness galaxies, radial profiles were extracted for these galaxies using the orientation parameters derived for use in correcting the total magnitudes and colors for internal extinction. Points in the outer part of the surface brightness profiles were selected and an exponential fit was performed using these points. Selecting points in the outer parts of the disk avoids contaminating the fits with the bulges of spirals, or in the case of nearly edge on systems, the effects of seeing in the inner parts of the disk. Using these fits, the central surface brightnesses were corrected for inclination in the same way as for the low surface brightness galaxies. The solid line on the plot is a fit to the galaxies presented here, while the dashed line is a plot of a the relation fit by De Blok et al. (1996). Again it appears that the trends seen in the Hercules cluster HI galaxies are similar to those seen in field galaxies.

The result that the HI properties of the galaxies in the Hercules cluster are the same as a sample of field galaxies seems to suggest that as a whole, these galaxies are not suffering any gross reduction in their HI content, as galaxies in some other clusters have (Giovanelli & Haynes 1985; Cayatte, Kotanyi, Balkowski, & Van Gorkom 1994). This may not mean that the environment in the Hercules cluster is having no effect on the HI content of its galaxies, since Dickey (1997) notes that there are no HI detected galaxies in the vicinity of the brightest x-ray peak

in the cluster. This may imply that initially HI rich galaxies are stripped of their HI in this region of the cluster. If this is true, the HI detected galaxies represent a population that have not yet encountered the harsher regions of the cluster, and so thus far have been able to retain their HI.

4.5 The Spatial Distribution of Galaxies

One of the purposes of conducting this survey was to look for any connection between the $H\alpha$ emission properties of cluster galaxies, and their membership in different substructures in the cluster. In this section, this question is considered by comparing three different populations: the set of all bright, $H\alpha$ emitting galaxies, the set of bona-fide cluster members that show no $H\alpha$ emission, and the subset of $H\alpha$ emission galaxies that show an excess of $H\alpha$ emission for their color or morphological type. A plot of the positions of the $H\alpha$ emitting galaxies is shown overlaid on the PSPC x-ray contours in Figure 4.17, of the $H\alpha$ non-detections in Figure 4.18, and of the sample of $H\alpha$ excess galaxies in Figure 4.19. Finally, a plot showing the positions of all the galaxies in the $H\alpha$ detected sample brighter than $B_T = 18.0$, overlaid with contours of the x-ray emission is given in Figure 4.20. The $H\alpha$ emitters have been weighted by their $H\alpha$ flux, and then the $H\alpha$ map has been smoothed with a Gaussian with $\sigma = 1'$, in order to enhance the viewability of the image. The qualitative impressions gained from examining these various maps are first discussed, followed by an attempt to statistically evaluate the significance of any perceived features in the maps.

4.5.1 Qualitative Impressions

Examination of Figures 4.17, 4.18, and 4.20 shows that only two of the 66 $H\alpha$ detections lie within the area of the main x-ray peak of the cluster, while there are at least 6 $H\alpha$ non-detections that could reasonably be identified with the

Figure 4.17. Positions of all galaxies with normal $H\alpha$ emission over-plotted on the x-ray contours.

Figure 4.18. Positions of all $H\alpha$ non-detections over-plotted on the x-ray contours.

Figure 4.19. Positions of galaxies with excess $H\alpha$ emission over-plotted on the x-ray contours.

Figure 4.20. The $H\alpha$ flux from the cluster galaxies, shown in gray-scale, overlaid with contours of the x-ray emission. Both have been smoothed with a Gaussian with $\sigma = 1'$. The area of the cluster depicted is the same as that in the previous three plots.

main x-ray peak. There is also a tendency for the $H\alpha$ non-detections to avoid the southern areas of the cluster, although this may simply be due to a bias against measuring the redshifts of galaxies in this part of the cluster. Otherwise, both the $H\alpha$ emitters and non-emitters seem to occur in all other parts of the cluster with roughly the same frequency. The avoidance of the main x-ray peak by the $H\alpha$ emitters may simply be a consequence of the morphology-density relation (Gisler 1980; Dressler 1980a) where late type spirals, which are typically bright $H\alpha$ emitters, avoid high density regions, while early type galaxies that typically have little $H\alpha$ emission preferentially inhabit high density regions. A similar effect has been noted by Dickey (1997) in his HI survey, where there are no HI detections in the area of the brightest x-ray peak, although there are many other HI detections throughout the cluster.

Figure 4.19 shows that the $H\alpha$ excess galaxies seem to be spread throughout the cluster, similar to the $H\alpha$ galaxies that show no enhancement. This is somewhat surprising if the early type $H\alpha$ galaxies represent the star formation burst phase of the $H\delta$ strong galaxies in the Coma cluster, since Caldwell et al. (1993) find that these systems occur preferentially in a substructure on the outskirts of the main cluster.

4.5.2 Statistical Analysis

In order to determine if there are any statistically significant differences between the distributions of $H\alpha$ emitting and non-emitting galaxies, or between the $H\alpha$ normal and excess galaxies, a two dimensional Kolmogorov-Smirnov test was again employed. The test suggests that there is a 15% chance that the distribution of $H\alpha$ emitting and non-emitting galaxies are drawn from the same distribution, and thus that the perceived segregation is not statistically significant. The test also suggests that the distribution of $H\alpha$ excess and normal galaxies would be drawn from the same parent population 88% of the time, and thus that there is

no evidence for a spatial segregation of the $H\alpha$ excess galaxies from galaxies with normal $H\alpha$ emission.

There are three possible ways to reconcile the observed spatial segregation of the $H\delta$ strong galaxies in the Coma cluster, and the lack of spatial segregation in the early type $H\alpha$ excess galaxies in the Hercules cluster, which seem to be ideal candidates for galaxies that will become $H\delta$ strong galaxies in 1-2 Gyr. The first is that the $H\alpha$ excess galaxies in Hercules are not related to the $H\delta$ strong galaxies, but are instead an unrelated phenomenon. The early type morphologies of both populations, along with the similar distribution of current star formation in the $H\alpha$ excess systems (which is discussed in the next chapter), and past star formation in the $H\delta$ strong galaxies suggests that the two populations are related. A second possibility is that the observed correlation of the $H\delta$ strong galaxies with the substructure in the Coma cluster is the result of a statistical fluctuation. Only observations of several other clusters will be able to decide if this is the case or not. Finally, it may be that the Hercules cluster is so dominated by substructure that most of the galaxies are associated with some sort of substructure. The identification of no less than five distinct components to the cluster (Bird et al. 1995; Huang & Sarazin 1996) makes this possibility difficult to discount, but equally difficult to demonstrate.

4.6 Summary

A spatially complete $H\alpha$ and broadband survey of the Hercules cluster has been presented. Approximately 80 $H\alpha$ sources have been detected in the cluster. Analysis of the $H\alpha$ detections brighter than $B_T = 18.0$ shows that the majority of the $H\alpha$ detections are normal, star forming galaxies. About 25% of the $H\alpha$ detections show a significant excess of emission over what would be expected for galaxies of their color or morphological type. Additionally, the $H\alpha$ excess galaxies

are almost exclusively early type galaxies (type Sa and earlier). These systems have $H\alpha$ equivalent widths typical of normal Sc galaxies, suggesting that these systems are undergoing significant amounts of star formation, although nowhere near the level of that exhibited in extreme star bursting systems. There is no evidence in the cluster for galaxies with recently truncated star formation. The combination of the large population of normal star forming galaxies, modestly enhanced star formation in some early type galaxies, and lack of galaxies with recently truncated star formation suggest that whatever mechanism is operating is subtle in its manifestations, and does not lead to catastrophic, wholesale changes in the properties of cluster galaxies.

Basic photometric data has also been presented for galaxies that were detected in the HI survey of Dickey (1997). A preliminary analysis of the HI properties of the high and low surface brightness galaxies detected in the cluster in HI compared to field samples of similar galaxies shows no gross systematic differences between the HI contents of galaxies in different environments. This does not necessarily mean that galaxies in Hercules are not suffering losses of HI due to the cluster environment. Dickey (1997) notes that there are no HI detections in the area of the cluster corresponding to the main x-ray peak in the cluster, suggesting that galaxies that enter that region of the cluster may quickly suffer HI ablation. In addition, Dickey (1997) notes several examples of galaxies whose individual HI distributions seem peculiar, suggesting that they are currently undergoing environmental alteration of their HI content.

Analysis of the spatial distribution of galaxies with different $H\alpha$ emission properties within the cluster suggests that there is no significant difference in the distribution of the $H\alpha$ normal, excess, or non-emitting galaxies. This means either that any environmental mechanism that affects the rate of star formation in Hercules cluster galaxies works on a cluster wide scale and does not restrict itself to the subcluster environment, or that the high incidence of substructure in the

Hercules cluster is masking the association of $H\alpha$ excess galaxies with subcluster membership.

While the results presented in this chapter show that the Hercules cluster contains a significant population of early type galaxies with an $H\alpha$ excess, it has not addressed the question of how the $H\alpha$ excess arises in these galaxies. The following chapters present an analysis of the spatial distribution of $H\alpha$ emission in Hercules cluster galaxies, as well as an in depth examination of the properties of the $H\alpha$ excess galaxies. These results will be used to attempt to assess the most likely source of the excess $H\alpha$ emission in these systems.

5 The Distribution of Star Formation in Hercules Cluster Galaxies

Until this point in this dissertation, the search for the effect of the cluster environment on cluster galaxies has been conducted using only the global properties of the galaxies. While this produces valuable information regarding whether or not a galaxy is suffering an interaction with the cluster environment, it does have limitations. The first is that while relatively dramatic environmental interactions may be reflected in the global properties of a galaxy, less dramatic interactions may produce more subtle manifestations in a galaxy that may not be reflected in its global properties. The second is that by themselves, global properties of galaxies are insufficient to diagnose the exact nature of the interaction that a galaxy is suffering. For these reasons, this chapter presents an examination for Hercules cluster galaxies of the relationship between their $H\alpha$ surface brightness, which is directly related to the rate of current massive star formation, and their R band surface brightness, which reflects the emission of long-lived stars on the lower main sequence, and thus the history of star formation.

Studies of interacting galaxies that have enhanced star formation (Bushouse 1987; Kennicutt et al. 1987) show that the star formation is preferentially enhanced in the center of many (but not all) of these galaxies. These results suggest that the inflow of gas triggered by the interaction leads to enhanced central star formation. It also suggests that a central enhancement in $H\alpha$ emission may be indicative of recent tidal interactions in a galaxy.

In a recent study of the $H\alpha$ and R band surface brightness distributions of a sample of Virgo cluster disk galaxies, Koopmann (1997) finds 10% of the galaxies she studied have truncated $H\alpha$ disks. In a VLA study of bright Virgo cluster spirals, Cayatte, Kotanyi, Balkowski, & Van Gorkom (1994) had earlier found evidence for truncated HI disks. These two results suggest that ram pressure due to the intra-cluster medium in the cluster has removed the outer gas disks from these galaxies, reducing their ability to form stars in their outer parts.

In order to define the expected relationship between the $H\alpha$ and R band surface brightness, the study of a set of field galaxies of types S0a-Sdm presented by Ryder & Dopita (1994) will be utilized. Ryder & Dopita (1994) find that there is a linear correlation between the I band surface brightness and the logarithm of the $H\alpha$ surface brightness for their galaxies, considered as an ensemble. Although Ryder & Dopita (1993) find a single slope characterizes the relation for their galaxies as a group, they find considerable offsets in the intercept of the relation for different galaxies. They show that these offsets are a function of Hubble subtype, such that early type spirals have lower $H\alpha$ surface brightnesses than later type spirals, consistent with the overall lower rates of massive star formation in these systems. They further demonstrate that this trend is probably due to lower gas surface densities in the early type galaxies.

5.1 Star Formation Models

The major purpose of Ryder & Dopita's (1994) survey was to attempt to constrain the dependence of the local rate of star formation on other physical properties of the galaxy, such as gas content, mass surface density, or disk kinematics. The most common parameterization for the star formation rate $d\sigma_*/dt$ is the Schmidt law (Schmidt 1959), which parameterizes the star formation rate as

some power of the local gas surface density σ_g , that is

$$\frac{d\sigma_*}{dt} \sim \sigma_g^n. \quad (5.1)$$

Another model that has been considered by several people (Wyse 1986; Wyse & Silk 1989; Silk 1997; Elmegreen 1997) is one where the star formation rate depends on both the gas surface density and the local orbital frequency, Ω , as

$$\frac{d\sigma_*}{dt} \sim \sigma_g \Omega. \quad (5.2)$$

Quirk (1972) suggested that star formation might be mediated by the local stability of the gas in a galaxy's disk, such that star formation would only occur in regions of a galaxy where the gas was unstable to collapse, and be essentially zero where the gas was stable.

Kennicutt (1989) presented an observational study of the dependence of massive star formation, as measured by $H\alpha$ emission, on the local gas surface density, measured by the HI and CO emission. He finds that in the inner parts of late type spirals, where the gas is unstable to collapse, the dependence of the star formation rate on the gas surface density is well represented by a Schmidt law with $n \approx 1.3$. He also finds a sharp truncation in the radius at which star formation occurs in these galaxies. This radius corresponds well to the radius at which the gas goes from being unstable, to being stable. This suggests that the local stability of the gas does indeed mediate the formation of stars.

Dopita & Ryder (1994) consider models for the observed correlation between $H\alpha$ and I band surface brightness in Ryder & Dopita (1994) where the star formation rate depends on powers of both the gas surface density and total mass surface density σ_T

$$\frac{d\sigma_*}{dt} \sim \sigma_g^n \sigma_T^m \quad (5.3)$$

which they suggest may be considered formally equivalent to equation 5.2. In their models, Dopita & Ryder (1994) allow for the loss of gas due to star formation, as

well as replenishment from in-fall from the galaxy's halo and due to stellar mass loss, but do not allow for any radial flow of gas in the galaxy's disk. Dopita & Ryder (1994) run models for 13 Gyr using different values of m and n , and a range of mass and gas densities that span the range observed in galaxies. The results of these models are then compared to the dependence of I band on $H\alpha$ surface brightness observed by Ryder & Dopita (1994). From these comparisons, Dopita & Ryder (1994) derive constraints on the exponents of the surface densities of $1.5 < (n + m) < 2.5$ with $m \neq 0$, suggesting that a Schmidt law is inadequate to fully explain the observed correlation.

5.2 Comparison Sample

Ryder & Dopita (1994) present $H\alpha$, V, and I band surface photometry of 34 field galaxies, which they use to demonstrate a tight correlation between the azimuthally averaged surface brightness at a given radius in $H\alpha$ and the broadband filters. In order to directly compare the data collected for the Hercules cluster with the field galaxies of Ryder & Dopita (1994), two conditions must be met. The first is that the Hercules data must be reduced in the same manner as that used by Ryder & Dopita (1994). The second is that, because of differences in the observing bands used by Ryder & Dopita (1994) and this study, appropriate conversions between the different data sets must be derived. To this end, the methods used by Ryder & Dopita (1994) are discussed in the following sections, along with the methods used to convert the data onto a common system.

5.2.1 Surface Brightness Extraction

Ryder & Dopita (1994) began their analysis with the broadband data. They first fit ellipses to the surface brightness distributions of the galaxies as a function of radius. Initially, the ellipticity and position angle of the ellipse (but not the

center) were allowed to vary at each radius. The best fit values in the outer parts of the galaxy were then used to determine the orientation parameters of the galaxy's disk. The ellipticity and position angle were then fixed at these values, and a radial profile was extracted for the V, I, and continuum subtracted $H\alpha$ images. These profiles were then corrected for two effects. The first was simply to deproject the galaxy's surface brightness to produce face on surface brightness profiles, by subtracting a geometrical factor of $2.5 \log(\cos(i))$, where i is the inclination of the galaxy's disk. Disk inclinations were derived using the minor to major axis ratios q found by the ellipse fitting, and treating the disk as an oblate spheroid with intrinsic axis ratio $q_o = 0.2$ using

$$\cos^2 i = \frac{q^2 - q_o^2}{1 - q_o^2}. \quad (5.4)$$

(Hubble 1926). The second correction Ryder & Dopita (1994) apply is to increase the $H\alpha$ surface brightness of each galaxy by a factor of 2.75 in order to correct for dust extinction within the HII regions of the galaxy being observed.

5.2.2 Broadband Data

In order to convert the V and I data presented by Ryder & Dopita (1994) to the R band in which the Hercules cluster galaxies were observed, the survey of global V, R, and I galaxy photometry presented by Buta & Williams (1995) was employed. Fitting a relation between the R photometry and the V and I photometry for the galaxies in Buta & Williams (1995) yields the relation

$$R = -0.03 + 0.466I + 0.534V. \quad (5.5)$$

This relation was used to produce an R band radial profile from the V and I surface brightness profiles for each of the galaxies in Ryder & Dopita (1994).

5.2.3 $H\alpha$ Data

Unlike the narrow band filters used to study the galaxies in the Hercules cluster, which were broad enough to pass both the $H\alpha$ line and the [NII] lines at $\lambda\lambda 6548, 6584\text{\AA}$, Ryder & Dopita (1994) used filters that isolated just the $H\alpha$ line. This means that a correction must be applied to take into account the difference in flux due to the different lines included in their band pass. Fortunately, the flux ratio between the $H\alpha$ line and those of [NII] are close to constant in the disks of galaxies, so that only a single factor is required to correct the data from one survey to the system of the other. The data from Ryder & Dopita (1994) was thus increased by a factor of 1.5 to take into account the lack of the [NII] lines in their band pass. The other correction necessary was due to the correction of a factor of 2.75 made by Ryder & Dopita (1994) to account for extinction due to dust within the HII regions of the galaxies being observed. Although the Hercules data could also be corrected for this effect, it was instead decided to remove this correction from the Ryder & Dopita (1994) data, since what was being sought was to study the empirical relation between surface brightnesses, and not to derive star formation rates via the $H\alpha$ luminosity. The combination of these two corrections means that the $H\alpha$ surface brightnesses presented in Ryder & Dopita (1994) were reduced by a factor of 0.545 for comparison with the Hercules cluster galaxies.

5.2.4 Results for Field Galaxies

Plots of the converted R band versus $H\alpha$ surface brightnesses for the Ryder & Dopita (1994) galaxies are presented in Figure 5.1. The plots are segregated by morphological type, in order to account for the intercept shifts as a function of morphological type noted by Ryder & Dopita (1994). The line on each plot is the best fit to the relation for all the galaxies of that type, confined to surface

brightnesses fainter than $\mu_R = 21.0\text{mag/arcsec}^2$, in order to avoid the inner parts of the galaxies where the scatter in the relation is higher. In accordance with the findings of Ryder & Dopita (1994), the slope of the fit for galaxies in each morphological bin is found to be essentially identical, although with different intercepts.

Fits to the relation for each individual galaxy shows that there is a moderate scatter around the slopes found by fitting the galaxies as an ensemble of $\sigma = 0.164$, again in accordance with the finding of Ryder & Dopita (1994). The distribution of slopes in the Ryder & Dopita (1994) sample will be used in a comparison of those derived for the Hercules cluster galaxies.

5.3 Cluster Galaxies

Radial profiles for the cluster galaxies in R and continuum subtracted $H\alpha + [NII]$ were extracted in the same manner as those presented in Ryder & Dopita (1994). Fits to the R band data were used to determine the disk orientation parameters, which were then used to extract the R and $H\alpha$ profiles. The galaxies were corrected for the geometric effects of inclination using equation 5.4. Plots of the relation between surface brightness in each band at a given radius for each galaxy that had at least five points with detectable $H\alpha$ emission are given in Figure 5.2. On each plot, the line indicates the fit to the Ryder & Dopita (1994) galaxies of the same morphological type as the cluster galaxy.

A linear fit was made to the relation between R band and $H\alpha$ surface brightness for each galaxy, subject to the following restrictions. First, only points with $\mu_R \geq 21.0\text{mag/arcsec}^2$ were included in the fit, as was done when fitting the Ryder & Dopita (1994) galaxies. This meant that several galaxies that had centrally condensed emission were not fit, as they lacked sufficient points in the required surface brightness range. These galaxies are tabulated in Table 5.1, along with

Figure 5.1. Plots of R band versus $H\alpha$ surface brightness for galaxies of different morphological types in the field sample of Ryder & Dopita (1994).

Figure 5.1. —Continued.

Figure 5.2. Plots of R band versus $H\alpha$ surface brightness for galaxies of different morphological types for the Hercules cluster galaxies.

Figure 5.2. —Continued.

Figure 5.2. —Continued.

Figure 5.2. —Continued.

Figure 5.2. —Continued.

Table 5.1. Galaxies with centrally condensed $H\alpha$ emission.

Galaxy	$H\alpha$ excess?	$\log(f_{center}(H\alpha + [NII]))$ ergs s ⁻¹ cm ⁻² asec ⁻²
BO 128	no	-15.64
D 089	yes	-15.24
sc2	yes	-14.72
D 038	no	-15.61
D 061	yes	-14.66

a notation as to whether they are an $H\alpha$ excess galaxy, and the $H\alpha$ surface brightness measured in their innermost ellipse. In the cases where galaxies were highly inclined, the several innermost ellipses were affected by seeing. In these cases, only points that were clearly uncontaminated by seeing effects were used in the fits. Examination of the surface brightness plots in Figure 5.2 shows that in some cases, the outermost point or two is significantly below the trend of the other points. This is due to the rather generous criteria used to select points to be plotted. These outer points were not used in the fits. Finally, several Hercules

cluster galaxies were overlapping with other galaxies (NGC 6050 + IC 1179 and NGC 6040 A+B), or had bright superposed stars (IC 1185) and thus were not fit due to the difficulty of cleanly separating the galaxy's emission from that of the contaminating object.

Histograms of the individually fit slopes for the Hercules cluster and Ryder & Dopita (1994) galaxies are given in Figure 5.3. Examination of the histograms show that the general features seen in the field galaxy's histogram are reproduced by the Hercules cluster galaxies, notably the peak around slopes in the range -0.25 to -0.30 , as well as a tail toward steeper (more negative) slopes. There are also differences, notably somewhat fewer galaxies with shallow slopes, and significantly more with steep slopes in the Hercules cluster galaxies. A Kolmogorov-Smirnov test indicates that there is only a 3% chance that the two distributions were drawn from the same parent distribution.

The immediate question is whether this difference in the distributions is real, or simply a result of differences in the way the data for the two samples was treated, or possibly due to some error in the reduction of the data for the Hercules cluster galaxies. The first possibility seems unlikely, since some care was taken to place the data on a common photometric system, and to extract the data from the Hercules cluster galaxies in the same way as that for the field galaxies, as well as to fit the surface brightness relation for the galaxies in a consistent manner.

The most likely reduction error that could give rise to systematically incorrect slopes is an error in the scaling of the continuum image used for continuum subtracting the $H\alpha$ images. To produce slopes that are too steep would require an oversubtraction of the continuum image. In order to assess how significant this effect might be, the continuum subtraction process was modeled for a range $H\alpha$ equivalent widths. This modeling suggests that in order to produce slopes that are steep by 0.1, the continuum level would have to be overestimated by at least 50%. Experience with the continuum subtraction process shows that a mis-estimation

Figure 5.3. Histograms of the distributions of slopes for the different samples. The upper panel is for all Hercules cluster galaxies with measurable slopes, and the lower panel is for the galaxies in the sample of Ryder & Dopita (1994).

of the continuum scaling factor of even 5% leads to unacceptably large residuals for objects that have no $H\alpha$ emission, such as stars or non-emitting galaxies. This suggests that any error in the scale factor is no more than 5%, even in a worst case scenario.

Another possible error related to the continuum level is the use of the R band filter for continuum subtraction. Because the R pass band includes the $H\alpha + [NII]$ lines, this means that the amount of continuum subtracted from a line emitting object will be high, resulting in line fluxes that are underestimated by a factor $1 - W_{NB}/W_R$, where W_{NB} and W_R are the effective widths of the narrow band and R filters. For the filters used in this work, this factor is 0.95, which will cause the slopes to steep by the negligible amount of 0.02.

5.4 Discussion

Since neither differences between the reduction procedures for the different data sets or errors in the reduction of the Hercules cluster data can account for the observed steeper slopes in the Hercules cluster galaxies, we must conclude that they are an intrinsic property of Hercules cluster galaxies. Examination of the surface brightness plots for Hercules cluster galaxies with steep slopes reveals three characteristic profile morphologies. The first is a profile that is asymptotic to the field galaxy fit at large radius, but in the inner portion rises well above the fit line. The second is asymptotic to the fit at small radius, but drops well below the field galaxy fit at large radii. The third are profiles that are high in the inner parts, but drop significantly below the field galaxy fit at large radius. Examples of each type of profile are given in Figure 5.4, along with an example of a galaxy with normal slope for comparison. The profiles of all Hercules cluster galaxies with slopes steeper than -0.45 were classified as being in one of these three categories, which from here on are referred to as inner (type i) profiles, outer

(type o) profiles, or combination (type io) profiles. These galaxies are tabulated in Table 5.2, along with the slope of the galaxies profile, its morphological type, the classification of its profile, and a notation as to whether the galaxy is an $H\alpha$ excess galaxy or not.

Examination of Table 5.2 shows that there is a strong correlation between the profile type and morphological type of the galaxy. Type i profiles are almost exclusively found in early type galaxies, while the type o profiles occur almost exclusively in late type spirals. Type io profiles seem to occur in both early and late type galaxies, consistent with these profiles being a transition class.

5.4.1 Type I Profiles

The type i profiles suggest an increase in the central star formation in some early type cluster galaxies. This is consistent with the results of Caldwell et al. (1996), who find that the $H\delta$ strong galaxies in the Coma cluster seem to have had star-bursts in the past that were confined to their central few kiloparsecs. This over abundance of central star formation is probably due to an increase in the central surface density of gas in these systems, either due to radial flows of gas within the galaxy, or accretion of gas from an external source.

Differentiating between these two possibilities based upon the surface brightness profiles may be difficult. On the one hand, one might expect that the radial transport of gas within in a galaxy might give rise to a type io profile, since the inner gas surface density is being enhanced by reducing the outer gas surface density. This would presumably lead to a reduction on the rate of star formation in the galaxy's outer parts as the rate of star formation in the inner parts is enhanced. Ryder (1993) finds examples of barred galaxies that exhibit this property, presumably due to bar driven gas inflow from the outer regions of the galaxy. On the other hand, the fact that most of the type i profile galaxies are S0's suggests caution, since the lower gas surface density in early type galaxies means that over

Figure 5.4. Examples of galaxies with high inner $H\alpha$ emission, low outer $H\alpha$ emission, and high inner/low outer $H\alpha$ emission. A galaxy with a normal slope is included for comparison.

Table 5.2. Hercules galaxies with steep R/ $H\alpha$ surface brightness relations.

Galaxy	Slope	Morph	Profile	$H\alpha$ excess
CGCG 108-098	-0.756	SABc	o	n
sc4	-0.726	S0	i	y
IC 1189	-0.703	SB0a	i	y
BO 119	-0.681	Sc	o	n
ce1	-0.643	Scd	o	n
D 087	-0.619	Sb	i	n
D 045	-0.606	I	io	n
IC 1182	-0.571	S0	i	y
D 100	-0.564	SABcd	io	n
Mk 299	-0.561	S	io	n
D 097	-0.554	S0a	io	y
sc1	-0.517	S0	i	y
D 020	-0.517	Sc	o	n
IC 1195	-0.503	SBbc	o	n
CGCG 108-154	-0.488	Sb	o	y
D 129	-0.488	S	o	y
D 021	-0.479	S	o	n
CGCG 108-139	-0.471	SABbc	o	n
CGCG 108-108	-0.467	Sc	o	n
NGC 6056	-0.465	SB0	i	n
D 012	-0.459	SBb	i	n
D 079	-0.452	E	i	y
IC 1188A	-0.451	SABa	i	n

most of these galaxies' disks, the gas may be stable against collapse (Pogge & Eskridge 1993). This means that transporting gas from an outer area where it is stable against collapse, to the center of the galaxy may increase central star formation, but not noticeably reduce the outer star formation, since the gas is coming from a region that has no star formation.

An interesting question regarding the galaxies with type i profiles is what correspondence they have with the $H\alpha$ excess galaxies observed in the Hercules cluster. Examination of Table 5.2 shows that five of the type i galaxies are also $H\alpha$ excess galaxies. One type io galaxy is an $H\alpha$ excess galaxy, as is one of the type o galaxies. Therefore a good fraction, but by no means all of the $H\alpha$ excess galaxies have type i profiles. An interesting point is that most of $H\alpha$ excess galaxies do have a central enhancement, with six of them having either type i or io profiles, and three having only central $H\alpha$ emission. Therefore nine of the fifteen early type $H\alpha$ excess galaxies in the Hercules cluster have a central excess of $H\alpha$ emission, suggesting that the excess star formation in these systems is concentrated in the central few kiloparsecs of these galaxies.

One point worth noting is that the five S0a and Sa galaxies in the Ryder & Dopita (1994) sample all have a central excess of $H\alpha$ emission, although the fit slopes for these systems are not steeper than for the later type spirals in the sample. This could mean that an inner excess with respect to the outer disk is a common feature of early type galaxies.

Regardless of whether the central $H\alpha$ enhancement is due to a radial flow of gas within the galaxies, or external accretion of gas, the central enhancement suggests some sort of tidal interaction or merger event in the galaxy, and seems to rule out a ram pressure compression of the gas. The lack of the presence of nearby companions, and with the exception of IC 1182, of other signs of obvious interaction in the type i galaxies means that the source of this interaction must be such that it leaves little evidence besides the central $H\alpha$ enhancement. This

suggests either cluster tidal interactions (Byrd & Valtonen 1990; Valluri 1993), which tend to distort a galaxy symmetrically and thus leave less tangible clues than galaxy-galaxy interactions, or interaction with/accretion of dwarf galaxies, which also are expected to leave only subtle imprints on the more massive galaxy (Walker, Mihos, & Hernquist 1996).

5.4.2 Type O Profiles

As noted previously, type o profiles seem to occur almost exclusively in later type spirals. It is tempting given the normal inner star formation, and seeming deficit of outer star formation, to conclude that these galaxies have been stripped in their outer parts by ram pressure, leading to a drop in the star formation in their outer disks. Several of the type o galaxies were detected by Dickey (1997) in his HI survey, and most show extensive HI disks that are significantly larger than the optical disks of the galaxies. These HI observations show that it is highly unlikely that the type o profiles are due to stripping. Examination of the profiles of late type spirals in Ryder & Dopita (1994) show that several of their galaxies also show similar profiles. Perhaps these galaxies are systems where the gas density has dropped below the stability threshold, and are thus not forming stars in their outer parts (Kennicutt 1989).

5.4.3 Whence the Steep Slopes?

Since the presence of steep slopes in Hercules cluster galaxies is a statistical result, a particularly pertinent question is whether the excess of steep slopes can be associated with galaxies of a particular profile type or not. In order to address this question, all the galaxies in the Ryder & Dopita (1994) sample with slopes steeper than -0.45 were classified in the same way as the Hercules cluster galaxies were. With only eight galaxies with steep slopes, any statistical comparison of the frequency of different profile types is not possible, but it appears that the

different types occur with about equal frequency in the Ryder & Dopita (1994) sample. This suggests that effect may not be due to an over abundance of a particular profile type. On the other hand, the seeming connection between an $H\alpha$ excess and steep slopes in early type galaxies suggests that the same mechanism is responsible for both phenomena.

5.5 Summary

An examination of the relation between the $H\alpha$ and R band surface brightness for Hercules cluster galaxies has been presented. When compared to a sample of field galaxies, the $H\alpha$ to R band surface brightness relation shows an excess of steep slopes compared to the relation for field galaxies. Roughly equal numbers of cluster galaxies with steep slopes show central enhancements in their $H\alpha$ emission, and outer deficits in their $H\alpha$ emission. The central enhancements are probably due to tidal interactions or minor mergers/accretion events. The deficit of outer $H\alpha$ emission in some of the galaxies does not seem to be due to stripping in the outer disks of the galaxies, since many of the galaxies possess extended HI disks (Dickey 1997).

6 The Nature of the $H\alpha$ Excess Galaxies in the Hercules Cluster

This chapter pulls together all available data, both from this dissertation and the literature, for the nineteen $H\alpha$ excess galaxies discovered in the Hercules cluster survey, along with the Hercules cluster galaxy D150 for which data was collected at the Lowell Observatory. The purpose of doing this is to as fully as possible characterize the properties of these galaxies with an eye towards constructing a plausible scenario for the source of their $H\alpha$ excess. In addition to already existing data, this chapter presents new long slit optical spectroscopy for five of the twenty galaxies considered in this chapter.

6.1 Optical Spectroscopy

Long slit spectroscopic observations of five of the twenty known $H\alpha$ excess galaxies, as well as NGC 6056, were obtained as the part of two different observing runs for other scientific programs. Spectra of D 150 and D 079 were obtained on February 10, 1997 by C. Liu using the University of Arizona's 2.3m Bok Reflector. The integration time on each source was 500 seconds. Observations of D 084, D 119, D 097, and NGC 6056 were obtained on May 29, 1998 by W. Keel, F. Owen, and M. Ledlow using the Kitt Peak National Observatories' 4m Mayall reflector. The integration time during these observations was 300 seconds for each galaxy. The reduction procedures for the data from both runs was very similar, so the following discussion of the image reductions pertains to both sets of observations.

An average bias frame was first subtracted from all frames in order to remove

any pixel to pixel variations in the bias level. The over-scan region of the CCD was then fit with a low order polynomial, and this fit was subtracted from all columns on the chip for each image, in order to remove any small drift in the bias level throughout the night. The frames were trimmed at this point to remove poorly exposed pixels near the edge of the chip. Observations of a quartz lamp were used to construct a flat field image by fitting a low order polynomial along the dispersion direction. The lamp image was then normalized by this fit, in order to remove the spectral response of the spectrograph from the flat field. The resulting image was then used to flat field all frames. Cosmic rays were then identified and removed manually. Observations of a comparison lamp was then used to wavelength calibrate each set of observations. The wavelength range covered in the data collected at the Bok reflector was $3680 - 6990\text{\AA}$ at a dispersion of $2.77\text{\AA}/\text{pixel}$, and for the Mayall data was approximately $3945 - 9485\text{\AA}$ at a dispersion of $2.78\text{\AA}/\text{pixel}$. Finally, the galaxy spectra were flux calibrated using observations of spectrophotometric standards from the lists of Massey et al. (1988). Plots of the reduced spectra are given in Figure 6.1

Brief comments on the spectra for each galaxy are presented at this point. D 079 shows a spectrum characteristic of a strongly star forming system, although the continuum is not excessively blue. The excitation of the spectrum is not that high, suggesting that the galaxy is fairly metal rich. D 084 shows extended disk emission. The only detected emission lines are $H\alpha + [NII]$ and the [SII] lines at $\lambda\lambda 6716, 6731\text{\AA}$, with no emission lines detected in the blue. The non-detection of $H\beta$ suggests a fairly high dust content for this system. D 097 shows a red continuum, consistent with its red $B - R$ color. Again, only the $H\alpha + [NII]$ and the [SII] lines are detected. D 119 shows a rather neutral color continuum, with only $H\alpha + [NII]$ being detected. D 150 shows emission lines suggesting strong nuclear star formation, superimposed on the red continuum characteristic of a E/S0 galaxy. NGC 6056 shows a spectrum typical of an evolved E/S0 galaxy,

Figure 6.1. Spectra of six of the $H\alpha$ excess galaxies in the Hercules cluster. The spectra have been smoothed with a three pixel boxcar to suppress noise. In some cases, residuals of poorly subtracted night sky lines have been repaired.

Figure 6.1. —Continued.

Figure 6.1. —Continued.

Table 6.1. Derived fluxes in detected lines, in units of 10^{-15} ergs/sec/cm².

Galaxy	[O II] 3727Å	$H\beta$ 4861Å	[O III] 4959Å	[O III] 5007Å	[N II] 6548Å	$H\alpha$ 6563Å	[N II] 6583Å	[S II] 6717Å	[S II] 6731Å
D 079	12.2	7.4	2.2	5.0	4.3	35.7	12.0	3.9	3.2
D 084	—	0.56L	—	—	1.1	9.5	2.5	0.61	1.5
D 097	—	0.44L	—	—	1.5	6.6	4.5	1.5	0.95
D 119	—	0.52L	—	—	—	1.9	0.77	—	—
D 150	5.2	1.7	—	1.2	5.8	30.8	19.3	—	—

with no detectable emission lines. The lack of detected emission lines is probably due to a combination of the galaxy's relatively low $H\alpha + [NII]$ equivalent width (6Å), coupled with the spatially diffuse nature of its $H\alpha$ emission.

Fluxes for detected lines in the spectra were measured using gaussian fits to the lines, and are presented in Table 6.1. In cases where $H\beta$ was not detected, an upper limit to the $H\beta$ flux was estimated from the spectrum for use in estimating a lower limit to the extinction in the line emitting region, and is tabulated with an L to indicate that the value is an upper limit. Extinctions in the V band were calculated using the observed ratios of $H\alpha$ to $H\beta$ (or its upper limit) by assuming case B recombination with a temperature $T = 10,000^\circ K$ and electron density $n_e = 100\text{cm}^{-3}$ (Osterbrock 1989). These parameters give a ratio of $H\alpha/H\beta = 2.86$. The observed line fluxes of $H\alpha$ and $H\beta$ were corrected for 2 Å of absorption, following McCall, Rybski, & Shields (1985). The derived extinctions are given in Table 6.2, along with the redshift for each of the galaxies derived using the wavelengths of the detected emission lines. The line measurements reveal a moderate amount of extinction in these systems, typically in the range 1-3 magnitudes at V. The highest extinction is found for D 150, $A_V = 3.6$ magnitudes. It is possible that this high value of extinction is due to an under estimation of the $H\beta$ absorption equivalent width for this system. To examine this possibility,

Table 6.2. Derived V band extinctions and redshifts for the observed galaxies.

Galaxy	A(V)	z
D 079	1.0	0.03394
D 084	2.0L	0.03755
D 097	1.3L	0.03895
D 119	0.7L	0.03698
D 150	3.6	0.03692

the continuum color index $C(55 - 67)$ defined by Keel (1983) was determined for the D 150 spectrum. Keel finds a good correlation between this parameter and $H\beta$ absorption equivalent width, and gives a formula to predict the equivalent width using $C(55 - 67)$. Using this formula predicts that D 150 should have an $H\beta$ absorption equivalent width of 1.8 Å, suggesting that the adopted correction of 2 Å is correct. For reference, if the actual $H\beta$ equivalent width was 4 Å rather than 2 Å, the inferred extinction in D 150 would be $A_V \approx 1.4$ magnitudes.

6.2 Comments on Individual Galaxies

D 084. This galaxy is a somewhat peculiar Sa galaxy, located well west of the main x-ray peak in the cluster. The galaxy has a compact, somewhat distorted disk. The continuum subtracted $H\alpha$ image and spectra obtained for this galaxy show that this system is currently undergoing strong disk-wide star formation.

NGC 6040B. This S0 galaxy seems to be currently interacting with the neighboring spiral galaxy NGC 6040A. The $H\alpha$ image shows a compact core, with some extended $H\alpha$ emission. The galaxy is a fairly bright radio source, having a flux density of 101 mJy at 1400 MHz (Zhao, Burns, & Owen 1989). The pair was detected by IRAS, but because of their proximity to one another, it is impossible to separate the flux from the two components. Even if all the IRAS flux is attributed to NGC 6040B, the galaxy would still have a FIR-radio ratio

that would indicate that the radio emission was powered by an active galactic nucleus (AGN), and not star formation (Condon 1992). There is also an x-ray source centered on this galaxy (Huang & Sarazin 1996), again suggesting that this galaxy contains an AGN.

D 103. This normal appearing S0 shows a bright central disk of $H\alpha$ emission.

SC1. This appears to be a normal S0 galaxy. The galaxy has not been cataloged previously. The $H\alpha$ emission in this system is fairly compact.

SC2. This galaxy is a compact S0, which was also not previously cataloged. The $H\alpha$ distribution in this galaxy is fairly compact and high surface brightness.

D 129. This edge on spiral was detected in HI by Dickey (1997). Dickey finds that the HI distribution in this galaxy is asymmetric, with most of the HI on the east side of the galaxy while the west side is fairly HI deficient. In contrast, the $H\alpha$ emission in the galaxy is stronger on the west side. If Dickey's interpretation of the HI asymmetry being due to ram pressure sweeping is correct, then perhaps we are seeing ram pressure induced star formation in this case.

BO 107. This Sc galaxy is extremely blue, and fairly asymmetric.

D 061. This normal appearing S0 galaxy has compact $H\alpha$ emission.

BO 076. This normal appearing S0 has a somewhat extended disk of $H\alpha$ emission.

D 097. This system has fairly compact and high surface brightness $H\alpha$ emission. The nuclear spectrum of this galaxy suggests a moderate amount of dust absorption.

NGC 6054 This large barred spiral is somewhat blue for its type, and has a large HI disk (Dickey 1997).

D 079. This galaxy is an extremely compact elliptical, with compact, high surface brightness $H\alpha$ emission. The spectrum of this galaxy indicates that it is currently undergoing strong star formation. The relative strength of $H\alpha$ to $H\beta$ in this galaxy indicates modest reddening in this system. This, coupled with

the fact that the system is not exceptionally blue suggests that we are seeing a starburst, superimposed on an older stellar population. This system also appears to have been detected in HI in Dickey's (1997) VLA survey, but was not included in his catalog, probably because its small size caused it to fall below his detection threshold.

SC4. This normal seeming S0 has not been previously cataloged.

IC 1182. This galaxy is a merger remnant, and shows two tidal tails with associated HI (Dickey 1997). The nucleus of this galaxy has a spectrum that is a transition between an HII region and Seyfert 1 like emission, suggesting both star formation and an AGN in and around the nucleus of this object (Veron, Goncalves, & Veron-Cetty 1997).

D 119. This galaxy is a normal appearing S0. The spectrum of this galaxy suggests a modest amount of extinction.

IC 1189. This galaxy is a Markarian object, and so must show strong UV emission. The galaxy's $H\alpha$ emission is compact. The HI emission from this galaxy has an extent roughly comparable to that of the optical disk (Dickey 1997). The galaxy's radio emission at 1400MHz of 5.9 mJy (Dickey & Salpeter 1984) gives it a FIR to radio ratio (Helou, Soifer, & Rowan-Robinson 1985) of $q = 2.14$, consistent with the radio and FIR emission being powered by star formation (Condon 1992).

IC 1193. This large S0 galaxy shows a fairly bright $H\alpha$ nucleus, superimposed on a diffuse $H\alpha$ disk.

D 089. This galaxy is a compact elliptical. Its $H\alpha$ emission is compact, and has a high surface brightness, similar to D 079.

D 150. This S0 galaxy is the most luminous IRAS source within one Abell radius of the cluster center. The galaxy was detected at 1.5 GHz by Slee, Roy, & Andernach (1996), who find a flux density at that frequency of 7.4 mJy, giving a FIR to radio ratio of $q = 2.62$, suggesting that the radio emission is powered by star formation (Condon 1992). The optical spectrum suggests that this system is

suffering a relatively large amount of extinction in its nucleus, consistent with its large amount of FIR emission.

CGCG 108-154. This galaxy is a normal seeming spiral.

6.3 Classification

Examination of the properties of the $H\alpha$ excess galaxies suggest that they may broadly classified into four distinct types of objects. The major reason for doing this is that the common properties of the different classes may give insight into the external causes for their current $H\alpha$ excess. An important caveat to this is that at least some galaxies may have an $H\alpha$ excess without any external cause (Keel & Van Soest 1992; Telles & Terlevich 1995). Therefore, some care must be taken not to over interpret the properties of any of the following classes of $H\alpha$ excess galaxies.

6.3.1 Major Galaxy-Galaxy Interactions

Two $H\alpha$ excess galaxies can reasonably be put in this class, IC 1182, a merger remnant, and NGC 6040B, which seems to be interacting with the massive spiral NGC 6040A. As already discussed, the $H\alpha$ emission in both these systems seems to be powered by a mix of star formation and emission from an AGN. The role of interactions and mergers in stimulating star formation has been well documented (Keel, Kennicutt, Hummel, & Van der Hulst 1985; Kennicutt et al. 1987), but the long sought after connection between interactions and AGN has produced much less clear results (see Heckman 1990 for a review). The fact that only two of the twenty $H\alpha$ excess galaxies are of this class suggests that interactions or mergers between roughly equal mass galaxies cannot account for the presence of the $H\alpha$ excess galaxies in the Hercules cluster.

A few interesting points concerning major galaxy-galaxy interactions in the

Hercules cluster are worth further note. The first is that there are several examples of strongly interacting systems in Hercules (NGC 6045, NGC 6040A, IC 1178 + IC 1181, IC 1194, Mk 299) that show no $H\alpha$ excess. In fact, the early type galaxies IC 1178, IC 1181, and IC 1194 have no detectable star formation, in spite of possessing impressive tidal tails and bridges. At some level, finding interacting galaxies without enhanced star formation is not a surprise, since Kennicutt et al. (1987) find a significant fraction of interacting systems without enhanced star formation.

A second interesting point is that the number of strongly interacting systems in Hercules probably indicates that the cluster is dominated by substructures with lower velocity dispersions that are more conducive to galaxy-galaxy interactions and mergers than in a typical rich cluster with velocity dispersion $\sim 1000\text{km/sec}$. This is not a new idea in regards to the Hercules cluster (Bothun & Schommer 1982), and evidence for several sub-clusters in the Hercules cluster has been presented by Bird et al. (1995) and Huang & Sarazin (1996) (see section 4.1 for a more extensive discussion). The velocity dispersions for these sub-clusters derived by Bird et al. (1995) are still generally in excess of 500km/sec , so it is interesting to speculate that the partitioning of the cluster into sub-clusters may still be incomplete.

6.3.2 Spirals With Disk-Wide Star Formation

The earlier analysis shows that late type spirals with an $H\alpha$ excess occur with the same frequency in the field and Hercules cluster samples. There are five $H\alpha$ excess galaxies that fall into this category, D 084, BO 107, NGC 6054, CGCG 108-154, and D 129. All five show fairly strong star formation over most of the extent of their disks. NGC 6054 and CGCG 108-154 are normal seeming spirals, but D 084, BO 107, and D 129 show some level of asymmetry in their $H\alpha$ distributions. In addition, D 084 and BO 107 show asymmetries in their continuum disks, while

D 129 shows an asymmetric HI distribution (Dickey 1997). The lack of nearby companions may suggest that these galaxies are suffering from galaxy harassment (Moore et al. 1996), or from tides due to the cluster potential (Byrd & Valtonen 1990; Valluri 1993; Byrd & Henriksen 1996). The structure of D 129 could also be due to ram pressure effects, although the ICM density does not seem to be particularly high at the position of the galaxy. Whatever the explanation for these galaxies $H\alpha$ excess, the fact that only five such galaxies have been detected suggests that the mechanism is not currently affecting most cluster galaxies.

6.3.3 Compact Galaxies

The description of a galaxy as compact has traditionally been an inexact one, both because the term is used to refer to different types of objects by different people, but more importantly, because the compactness of a galaxy image has often depended on the observational material being used to do the classification. The most common criteria of a compact galaxy is a galaxy of relatively high surface brightness that is only marginally discernible from a star. A particularly frustrating consequence of this is that systems that would at a certain distance be classified as compact might not be classified as compact if they were more nearby. Catalogs of compact galaxies based on optical inspection of sky survey material are presented by Zwicky (1971) and Arp & Madore (1987) (their category 13). Not surprisingly, the nature of the compact galaxies in these catalogs seems to be highly heterogeneous, with some being normal seeming elliptical galaxies, while others are intensely star forming systems.

Recent interest in the study of compact galaxies at higher redshift has been sparked by the “faint blue galaxy problem,” the observation that at redshifts $z \sim 0.2 - 0.5$ there are many more faint, blue galaxies than can be accounted for by extrapolating the $z \sim 0$ galaxy population to $z \sim 0.2 - 0.5$ with no evolution in their star formation properties (Cowie, Songaila, & Hu 1991). One possible

explanation for the excess blue galaxies is that they are star-bursting dwarfs, which have faded to become the dwarf spheroidals of today. If this is the case, the excess blue galaxies would show up as compact high surface brightness galaxies at $z \sim 0.2 - 1.0$. Phillips, Guzman, Gallego, Koo, Lowenthal, Vogt, Faber, & Illingworth (1997) and Guzman, Gallego, Koo, Phillips, Lowenthal, Faber, Illingworth, & Vogt (1997) present studies of galaxies selected for their compactness in the flanking fields of the Hubble deep field. Their spectroscopy shows that approximately one third of the compact galaxies are normal ellipticals, while the remaining two thirds are star forming systems, characterized by strong emission lines and blue continua. They find that roughly half of these star forming systems have the characteristics of local star forming disk galaxies, while the other half have properties similar to local HII galaxies, which are characterized by small sizes and strong line spectra, characteristic of systems undergoing intense star formation (Salzer, MacAlpine, & Boroson 1989a, 1989b).

Salzer et al. (1989a, 1989b) present studies of samples of emission line galaxies selected from objective prism surveys. Salzer et al. (1989b) classify all galaxies whose line emission is powered by star formation into different categories, based both on the luminosity and structure of the galaxies. The largest galaxies tended to be normal spirals with starburst nuclei. Smaller galaxies were defined as either HII hot-spot or dwarf HII hot-spot galaxies, based on their irregular morphology and high excitation nebular spectra, suggesting relatively low metallicities on the parts of these galaxies. A class intermediate between the starburst nuclei and HII hot-spot galaxies was also defined, the dwarf amorphous nuclear starburst galaxies (DANS for short). The DANS are characterized by small physical size (diameters on the order of 10 kpc), symmetric, featureless disks, and spectra with excitations that suggest that the systems are fairly metal rich.

A recent announcement has been made of the discovery of galaxies that were compact enough that they were indistinguishable from stars on sky survey prints

(Drinkwater, Gregg, & Smith 1998). These systems have redshifts in the range $0.044 < z < 0.184$, and apparently have spectra showing signs of strong star formation. Although these systems have been claimed to be a previously undiscovered type of local galaxy, it seems more likely that they are simply DANS and HII hot-spot galaxies that are sufficiently far away that they are unresolvable from the ground.

How do the three $H\alpha$ excess galaxies found in Hercules (D 079, D089, and sc2) that may reasonably be called compact compare to the systems described in Salzer et al. (1989b)? Their small size and regular appearance suggest that they would most reasonably be identified with the DANS. To examine the plausibility of this identification, effective radii (r_e) and surface brightnesses within the effective radii (μ_e) were determined on the on the B band images, and are tabulated in Table 6.3. The effective radii should probably be considered as upper limits, since a physical size of 1.5 kpc corresponds to a size of only 3 pixels on the images. Nevertheless, the derived values correspond well to those found for compact emission line galaxies of similar absolute magnitude (Phillips et al. 1997). As a further check on the consistency of the identification of the Hercules compacts as DANS, the line ratios $[\text{OIII}] \lambda 5007/H\beta$ and $[\text{NII}] \lambda 6584/H\alpha$ for D 079 were compared to those for the DANs in Salzer (1989b). The ratios found in D 079 are consistent with the most metal rich of the DANS. It therefore seems likely that

Table 6.3. Effective radii and surface brightnesses for Hercules cluster compact galaxies.

Galaxy	r_e kpc	μ_e mag/arcsec ²
D 079	1.5	20.49
D 089	1.5	21.41
sc1	1.5	21.57

the compact $H\alpha$ excess galaxies in the Hercules cluster are members of the class of emission line galaxies studied by Salzer et al. (1989a, 1989b).

6.3.4 Star Forming S0's

The remaining $H\alpha$ excess galaxies in the Hercules cluster are otherwise normal seeming S0 galaxies. While it is not unusual for some S0 galaxies to have modest amounts of star formation, it is worth reiterating that the galaxies in Hercules were identified as having an $H\alpha$ excess relative to the star forming S0's studied by Pogge & Eskridge (1993). The observed equivalent widths of these galaxies range from the fairly modest 8.5 Å in IC 1193 to in excess of 40 Å for D 119 and D 150, with a mean value of 24 Å, close to the mean value for Sc galaxies. Thus, while these systems are not in the same league with intensely star forming galaxies, which generally have $H\alpha$ equivalent widths in excess of 50 Å, many of them are still doing a fairly respectable job of forming stars.

As noted in the previous chapter, the star formation in these systems tends to be concentrated in the galaxies' nucleus. While this is not particularly unusual for S0-Sa galaxies, it does suggest that gas has been concentrated in the centers of these systems. The relatively undisturbed appearance of these galaxies suggests that either minor mergers or the effect of the cluster potential, which tends to symmetrically distort a galaxy's disk, may have acted to recently deliver gas to the center of these galaxies. Ram pressure triggering of star formation can also not be ruled out based on the distribution of star formation alone.

6.4 The Color-Magnitude Diagram, Revisited

The purpose of constructing a color-magnitude diagram in section 4.4.3 was to search for post starburst galaxies or galaxies with recently truncated star formation. The conclusion from studying the color-magnitude diagram for the $H\alpha$

non-detections was that there is not a significant population of such systems in the Hercules cluster. A significant population of galaxies with strong star-bursts was also not found in the cluster. The $H\alpha$ excess galaxies that were detected showed more modest levels of $H\alpha$ emission, corresponding to more modest bursts of star formation. Here the question of whether these modest bursts of star formation would be detectable on a color-magnitude diagram after the burst of star formation subsides is considered.

The color magnitude diagram for the early type $H\alpha$ excess galaxies, excluding IC 1182 and NGC 6040B that may have significant $H\alpha$ emission due to AGN, is plotted in Figure 6.2. This figure reveals that the majority of the $H\alpha$ excess galaxies are already redder than the Butcher & Oemler (1985) blue galaxy criteria, and those that are bluer are not extremely blue. These red colors are due to two factors. One is that the modest level of current star formation in these systems, superimposed on the underlying red population of these galaxies do not produce extremely blue colors. The other factor is apparent in the analysis of the spectra obtained for a subset of the $H\alpha$ excess galaxies. There is moderate amounts of dust in these galaxies, which tends to be concentrated in the star forming regions of these systems. This means that the modest $H\alpha$ excess galaxies detected in the Hercules cluster will be difficult to identify by the traditional means of a color magnitude diagram during their burst phase, and even more difficult to detect after the burst subsides and the galaxy grows redder. Additionally, surveys that use spectra in the blue region will have difficulty detecting these systems, since the emission lines of $H\beta$ and [OIII] are often extinguished enough to not be detected. The [OII] line may be detectable in these systems, but the combination of modest star formation and extinction will make the line weak. The fact that 1-2 Gyr after their star formation subsides, the early type $H\alpha$ excess galaxies will be red systems is consistent with these galaxies being the progenitors of the $H\delta$

Figure 6.2. The color-magnitude diagram for the $H\alpha$ excess galaxies. The solid line is the best fit to the $H\alpha$ non-detections, and the dashed line is the Butcher & Oemler (1984) blue galaxy criteria.

strong galaxies, which show signs of past star formation through enhanced Balmer absorption lines, but red colors.

6.5 Local Environment and Possible Triggering Mechanisms

Three possible mechanisms have been considered for triggering the $H\alpha$ excess observed in the early type cluster galaxies: ram pressure, cluster tides, and minor interactions or mergers. All three will leave the morphology of the affected galaxy relatively undisturbed, so in order to constrain the possible mechanism, the local environment of the galaxies must also be considered.

6.5.1 Ram Pressure

Ram pressure was originally considered as a mechanism for affecting star formation by Gunn & Gott (1972), who suggested it may strip cluster spiral galaxies and thus truncate their star formation. Evrard (1991) performed simulations of the formation of galaxy clusters, and developed a scenario where star formation activity is triggered by the rapid rise in the pressure in a galaxy's interstellar medium (ISM), due to its initial ram pressure contact with the clusters ICM. Evrard considers a galaxy to be triggered if the pressure rises to five times the pressure in the galaxies ISM ($P_{ISM}/k \approx 10^{3.5} \text{K}/\text{cm}^{-3}$), in a time less than 0.36 Gyr. Evrard's (1991) simulations predict two characteristics of the population of galaxies that have had star formation triggered. The first is that the galaxies will tend to occur only within a certain radius of the cluster center, since they must be in an area of high ICM density before they are triggered. The second is that the triggered galaxies will have a fairly flat velocity histogram, and will actually show a marked deficit of galaxies at the systemic velocity of the cluster.

In order to see if the above criteria were met for the $H\alpha$ excess galaxies,

the size of the region where the ram pressure is high enough for triggering was determined for the Hercules cluster using the gas density profile for the clusters main x-ray peak presented in Huang & Sarazin (1996). To estimate the radius at which activity would be triggered, the density necessary to produce a ram pressure of $p_{ram} = 5 \times 10^{3.5} k$ dynes/cm² was calculated for a galaxy with a speed of 1200 km/sec. These parameters give a number density of $n \sim 0.1\text{cm}^{-3}$. This gas density is achieved only within 100-200 kpc of the cluster center in the Hercules cluster. Since many of the $H\alpha$ excess galaxies are at distances greater than 1 Mpc from the cluster center, it seems unlikely that their star formation activity is due to ram pressure triggering.

Redshift histograms were constructed for cluster galaxies with and without an $H\alpha$ excess, and are plotted in Figure 6.3, for comparison with Evrard's (1991) prediction. Examination of the histograms shows that the histogram for the $H\alpha$ excess galaxies is not markedly flatter than that for the non-excess galaxies, and most importantly has a peak at the mean redshift of the cluster, the opposite of what is predicted in Evrard's (1991) models. Therefore it seems that the spatial and redshift distributions of the $H\alpha$ excess galaxies are inconsistent with ram pressure as a triggering mechanism.

6.5.2 Cluster Tides

Byrd & Valtonen (1990) simulated the affect of cluster tides on a galaxy disk, and found that significant gas inflow is triggered in galaxies if the perturbation parameter, $P = (M_p/M_g)(r_g/r_p)^3$, has values greater than 0.1, where M_g and r_g are the mass and radius of the galaxy, and M_p and r_p are the mass of the cluster and the distance of the galaxy from the cluster center. In order to infer the area of the cluster over which cluster tides will be effective, r_p was calculated for $P = 0.1$ for a galaxy with $r_g = 10\text{kpc}$ and $M_g = 10^{10}M_\odot$, and a cluster mass of $M_p = 10^{14}M_\odot$ (Huang & Sarazin 1996). These values give $r_p = 460\text{kpc}$. Since

Figure 6.3. Redshift histograms for the Hercules cluster galaxies with an $H\alpha$ excess (dashed line), and no $H\alpha$ excess (solid line).

many of the $H\alpha$ excess systems are at a distance of 1 Mpc or more from the cluster center, it appears that cluster tides will also not suffice as a triggering mechanism for these galaxies.

6.5.3 Minor Interactions or Mergers

In principal, a test of whether minor interactions or mergers are responsible for the $H\alpha$ excess galaxies could be performed by searching for an excess of nearby companions to the $H\alpha$ excess galaxies, compared to galaxies with normal levels of emission. In practice, there are two complicating factors to performing such a test. The first is that, because the galaxies of interest are in a cluster, the surface density of unrelated galaxies projected along the line of sight is high, making any signal due to bona-fide companions difficult to detect. The other is that because the hypothesized companions are much less bright than the galaxy with which they are interacting, and possibly of low surface brightness, they would be difficult to detect even in the absence of the high surface density of cluster galaxies.

As a preliminary step in examining the possibility that minor interactions are responsible for the $H\alpha$ excess systems, the areas around the $H\alpha$ excess and $H\alpha$ normal galaxies were examined out to a distance of 50 kpc (slightly more than 1 arcminute at the distance of the Hercules cluster), for the presence of faint companions. This preliminary examination finds no excess of companions around the $H\alpha$ excess systems, compared to $H\alpha$ normal systems in similar areas of the cluster. This initial search suggests that there is not an over abundance of optically identifiable companions to the $H\alpha$ excess galaxies, but does not rule out minor interactions and mergers as a triggering mechanism, since the companions may be of low surface brightness, or have already merged with the $H\alpha$ excess galaxy, and thus not be detectable. Sensitive VLA HI observations would be useful in testing this idea, since Taylor, Brinks, Grashuis, & Skillman (1995) have shown that HII galaxies often have optically faint, HI rich companions, which presumably trigger

star formation in the HII galaxies. It is possible that a similar population of HI rich dwarfs is responsible for the star formation in the $H\alpha$ excess galaxies.

In summary, while there is little current evidence for minor interactions or mergers in the $H\alpha$ excess systems, they cannot be ruled out as a star formation triggering mechanism, in large part because the signs of such events are so difficult to detect.

6.6 Summary

Examination of the properties of the $H\alpha$ excess galaxies in the Hercules cluster shows that most are early type systems. These early type galaxies have a mean $H\alpha$ equivalent width of $\approx 24 \text{ \AA}$, about the same as that of normal Sc galaxies. The star formation in these systems is often concentrated near the nucleus of the galaxy, which is not uncharacteristic of star forming early type systems. The emission line spectra of these galaxies suggest a moderate amount of reddening in the star forming regions of these galaxies, with V band extinctions in the range of 1-3 magnitudes. This extinction helps hide the star formation in surveys using broadband colors or blue spectra, so the fraction of these types of galaxies in other clusters, particularly at higher redshift, may be underestimated. The relatively undisturbed appearance of the majority of these systems, along with the centrally condensed star formation suggests that if the star formation has been triggered, the mechanism is a fairly non-damaging one. Examination of the local environment of the $H\alpha$ excess galaxies shows that many of them are in regions of the cluster where neither ram pressure or cluster tides should operate efficiently to stimulate star formation, suggesting that neither of these mechanisms is responsible for the $H\alpha$ excess galaxies. This leaves minor interactions or mergers as the only mechanism considered that could explain these systems, with the main advantage of this mechanism being the difficulty with which it can be detected.

7 NGC 3312

This chapter presents a more in-depth case study of one galaxy that has been suggested to be currently undergoing a strong interaction with the cluster environment (Gallagher 1978), NGC 3312. This galaxy is a good candidate for more careful study, not only because of its suggested interaction with the cluster environment, but also because more detailed information is available for this object. In addition, it exhibits many of the characteristics that complicate the isolation of specific environmental factors that affect cluster galaxies.

7.1 Previous Work

NGC 3312 is large spiral galaxy (see Figures 7.1 and 7.2), which is located, at least in projection, near the center of the Hydra cluster of galaxies (Abell 1060). The heliocentric recession velocity of the galaxy is ≈ 2870 km/sec. The mean recession velocity and velocity dispersion of the Hydra cluster, determined using an iterative algorithm to remove outliers are $v = 3718$ km/sec and $\sigma_v = 658$ km/sec respectively (Zabludoff, Huchra, & Geller 1990). Therefore NGC 3312 has a radial velocity that lies 1.3σ from the cluster mean, suggesting that if it is a cluster member, it is probably falling through the cluster core at the current time. In a detailed study of the dynamics of the Hydra cluster, Fitchett & Merritt (1988) note that there are several other galaxies projected on the core of the cluster with velocities similar to that of NGC 3312, and suggest that these galaxies form a bound group with NGC 3312. Further, they suggest that the group is not actually associated spatially with Abell 1060, but instead is at a distance suggested by its

recession velocity, and thus is only projected on the cluster core. In support of this notion they consider the case of NGC 3314, a pair of overlapping galaxies also projected near the core of Abell 1060. The velocities of the two components of NGC 3314 have velocities that differ by $\sim 2000\text{km/sec}$, with the foreground galaxy having a velocity near that of NGC 3312, while the velocity of the background galaxy is consistent with membership in a another piece of substructure identified by Fitchett & Merritt (1988). They suggest this structure is a background group, not physically associated with the Hydra cluster, as opposed to a group currently falling into the cluster from the near side. The fact that the high velocity galaxy is in the background casts doubt upon whether the higher velocity substructure is in the background; it does not preclude the NGC 3312 group from currently falling through the cluster center, since in this case, the low velocity member would still be projected in front of the higher velocity galaxy.

The structure of NGC 3312 in the optical has several peculiarities, including an arc of star forming regions along one side (particularly prominent in B and $\text{H}\alpha$ images of the galaxy, see Figure 7.3). In addition there are several filaments that emerge from the western side of the disk (Figures 7.1 and 7.2), which Gallagher suggested were due to ram pressure stripped material as the galaxy moved at high velocity through the cluster core.

The HI properties of NGC 3312 have been studied by McMahon, Richter, Van Gorkom, & Ferguson (1992). They find that the galaxy is only mildly HI deficient, with the HI disk of the galaxy having roughly the same extent as the optical disk. The HI structure of the galaxy shares several similarities with the optical structure, including a ridge of high HI surface density along the eastern edge of the disk, and some filament or bridge-like structures extending outward from the disks western edge. McMahon et al. conclude that the relatively high HI content of NGC 3312 suggests that it indeed may lay in the foreground of the cluster. They attribute the optical and HI peculiarities of the galaxy to a past

interaction with the low velocity component of NGC 3314. Again, although this represents one plausible scenario to describe what is happening with NGC 3312, it still does not preclude the possibility that the in-falling NGC 3312 group is only now reaching the area of the cluster where ram pressure effects become important, and thus has so far been only mildly stripped of HI. Clearly, more study will be necessary before the status of NGC 3312 can unambiguously determined.

7.2 Optical Spectroscopy

In order to better determine the source of the material in the filament, W. Keel obtained a long-slit spectrum of the most prominent filament on the western edge of NGC 3312's disk. The spectrum was obtained using the ESO 3.6m in La Silla, and consisted of a single 30 minute integration. The wavelength coverage was roughly 3400Å to 7000Å, with a dispersion of approximately 7 Å/pixel.

7.2.1 Reductions

All data frames (object, arc spectra, and standard star) were cleaned of cosmic rays in the following manner. First, cosmic ray candidates were identified using the IRAF task COSMICRAYS. These candidates were then examined individually on the CCD frame to identify any features that were mistakenly identified as cosmic rays, as well as to identify any cosmic rays that were missed by the COSMICRAYS task. This resulted in a master list of cosmic rays that were then replaced by values interpolated from adjacent cosmic ray free lines or columns. The bias level was then removed by fitting low order polynomials to the over-scan region and then subtracting the fit from the data. Pixel to pixel variations in the gain were removed using observations of of a quartz lamp. The spectral response of the lamp was removed by fitting a surface to the flat field image, and then normalizing the flat using this fit. Surface fitting was necessary to remove the spectral response

Figure 7.1. Image of NGC 3312 reproduced from the IIIa-J plate of Smith & Weedman (1976). Notice the filaments emerging from the western edge of the disk. The arrow indicates the condensation for which the spectrum was obtained.

Figure 7.2. R band image of NGC 3312 taken with the 3.6m telescope at La Silla. The arrow indicates the condensation for which the spectrum was obtained.

Figure 7.3. Continuum subtracted $H\alpha$ image of NGC 3312 obtained with the 1.07m telescope at the Lowell Observatory. Notice the arc of star forming regions along the eastern edge of the disk. The image has been smoothed with a gaussian with $\sigma = 1$ pixel.

since the flat field image contained structure that varied along both the columns and lines (i.e. along the slit as well as along the dispersion direction). All data frames were flat fielded by dividing by the resultant frame.

The wavelength scale was determined using a combination of a Helium-Argon arc spectrum and the position of the [O I] 6300 atmospheric line. The oxygen line was included to help constrain the observed spectra in the 5900 – 6700 Å range, since the arc has no spectral lines in this range. Using the known wavelengths of the calibration lines, the object and standard star frame were transformed onto a linear wavelength scale. The sky spectrum was then traced and subtracted from the object and standard star frames. Next a one dimensional spectrum of the standard star was extracted and used to compute the sensitivity function for the observed spectra. This sensitivity function was then used in conjunction with a standard extinction curve to place the object spectrum on an absolute flux scale.

A plot of the sky subtracted, flux calibrated spectrum in the range 4000-7000 Å is given in Figure 7.4. Examination shows a fairly typical nebular spectrum; H β , H α (blended with its satellite [N II] lines), and the [S II] lines at 6716 and 6731 (also blended) are all present. The [O III] doublet at 4959,5007 Å is weak, and possibly undetected. No useful information is present in the spectrum below 4000 Å, since the blue response of the detector is poor. Specifically, no detection of the [O II] doublet at 3727 Å was possible.

Line fluxes for H α , H β , [O III] 5007 Å, [N II] 6548, 6583 Å, and [S II] 6716, 6731 Å were derived by jointly fitting a set of gaussians to each line, along with a low order polynomial, which was used to determine the continuum level for each line. The fit was constrained to have a single redshift and gaussian σ . The line fluxes of the Balmer lines were corrected for 2 Å of absorption, following McCall, Rybski, & Shields (1985). The spectrum was corrected for internal reddening by assuming case B recombination with a temperature $T = 10,000K$ and electron density $n_e = 100cm^{-3}$ (Osterbrock 1989). These parameters give a ratio

Figure 7.4. Spectrum of the emission line knot in NGC 3312. The spectrum has been interpolated across $\lambda = 5577$ Å, to remove residuals of the strong night sky line at that wavelength.

Table 7.1. Derived parameters from the line fitting. For all lines except $H\beta$, fluxes are quoted relative to $H\beta$.

	$v_{\odot}$	$f_{H\beta}$	O III	N II	N II	S II	S II
	km/s	ergs/s/cm ²	5007Å	6548Å	6583Å	6717Å	6731Å
Parameter	2853	1.28×10^{-15}	0.296	0.442	0.789	0.722	0.616
SNR		12.7	3.7	5.9	10.6	9.7	8.3

of $H\alpha/H\beta = 2.86$. The observed $H\alpha$ to $H\beta$ ratio suggests a modest amount of reddening, $A_V = 0.87$. The fitted value of the heliocentric velocity, along with the dereddened line fluxes are given in Table 7.1. Also included in Table 7.1 is the signal to noise ratio for each line (SNR), calculated in the same manner as in Zaritsky, Kennicutt, & Huchra (1994). The noise level is determined by the RMS value of the continuum near the base of the line in question, multiplied by the width of the line. The signal is the integrated flux in the line, determined by the Gaussian fit.

7.3 Abundance Determination

Before attacking the problem of deriving a specific oxygen abundance for the H II region, the more basic question of whether the region has a high or low metallicity is first considered. The calibration of optical line ratios for use in deriving the abundances of extragalactic H II regions has been an area of much active work in recent years (Alloin, Collin-Souffrin, Joly, & Vigroux 1979; Edmunds & Pagel 1984; McCall, Rybski, & Shields 1985; Dopita & Evans 1986; McGaugh, S. 1991; Zaritsky, Kennicutt, & Huchra 1994). These calibrations are all semi-empirical in nature. In the case where the oxygen abundance is relatively low, temperature sensitive lines of O II and O III are strong enough to be detected, allowing a direct calibration of line strength versus abundance using the observed

temperatures. In the cases where the abundance is higher, the strength of the temperature sensitive lines drops enough that they become undetectable. In these circumstances, the dependence of line strength on abundance is calibrated using calculated spectra from model nebula.

The reason for the dependence of nebular temperature on metallicity is that the most efficient nebular coolants are hyperfine lines that occur in the far infrared. As the abundance of the nebula drops, the cooling shifts from these lines to the less efficient optical lines ([O II] 3727Å and [O III] 4959, 5007Å). Therefore at relatively high abundance, the strength of the optical oxygen lines decreases with increasing abundance. If the abundance drops low enough, these lines begin to weaken again, due to the scarcity of oxygen atoms. This means that there is a possible ambiguity in an abundance determination based on the oxygen lines alone, since the nebula could lie on either the high or low abundance branch of the calibration curve (see the top panel in Figure 7.5). In order to resolve this degeneracy, another line ratio that is not double valued in the abundance is necessary. This discrimination can be provided by the ratio of the [N II] lines to either the [O II] or [O III] lines. The line ratio [N II] to [O III] is plotted against oxygen abundance (using the calibration of Edmunds & Pagel [1984]) in the lower panel of Figure 7.5. Notice that at low abundance, the relation becomes very steep, but remains single valued, making the line ratio suitable as a branch discriminate.

What do the observed line strengths in the NGC 3312 filament suggest about its oxygen abundance? The low strength of the [O III] lines relative to $H\beta$ suggests either a fairly high or extremely low oxygen abundance, depending on whether the region should lie on the low or high abundance branch of the calibration. In order to determine the correct branch, a plot of the [O III] to $H\beta$ ratio versus the [N II] to [O III] ratio is given in Figure 7.6. The diamonds are from the sample of predominantly upper abundance branch H II regions from the study of Ryder (1995). The squares are low abundance branch objects collected from

Figure 7.5. Calibration of the line ratios $(f_{[\text{OIII}]}(4959\text{\AA}) + f_{[\text{OIII}]}(5007\text{\AA}))/f_{\text{H}\beta}$ and $f_{[\text{OIII}]}(5007\text{\AA})/f_{[\text{NII}]}(6584\text{\AA})$ as a function of the metallicity of the HII region, from Edmunds & Pagel (1984).

the literature (Dufour, Garnett, & Shields 1988 [IZw18]; Edmunds & Pagel 1984 [n7793w]; Garnett & Kennicutt 1994 [M101h681]; Kunth & Sargent 1983 [Tol 65]; Salzer, Alghieri, Matteucci, Giovanelli, & Haynes 1991 [HI 1225]; Torres-Peimbert, Peimbert & Fierro 1989 [M101s13]). The regions on the high and low abundance branch are clearly separated on the diagram. The line ratios for the NGC 3312 filament are plotted as the filled circle on this diagram, clearly in the high abundance branch portion of the diagram. Furthermore, any reduction in the [O III] value for the filament would result in the point being moved up the relation towards even higher abundances. Therefore the abundance of the filament is high.

7.3.1 Derived Abundance

Having determined that the line ratios of the filament put in on the high abundance branch of the abundance calibration, the calibration can now be used to derive a specific oxygen abundance for the region. Using the calibration of [O III]/H β of Edmunds and Pagel (1984) gives an abundance of $12 + \log(O/H) = 9.08$. This abundance has been derived using the value for [O III] (5007 Å) given in Table 7.1. Since [O III] (4959 Å) is too weak to be measured, its strength has been inferred from the flux of the 5007 line using the theoretical ratio between fluxes in the 2 lines of $[OIII](5007\text{Å})/[OIII](4959\text{Å}) = 2.88$ (Nussbaumer & Storey 1981). Edmunds & Pagel's calibration of oxygen abundance versus [O III]/[N II] can also be used to derive an abundance, yielding an abundance of $12 + \log(O/H) = 9.04$, in excellent agreement with [O III]/H β derived value (which is not surprising given the position of the region in Figure 7.6). Using the average of these 2 values gives a best estimate for the oxygen abundance of the filament of $12 + \log(O/H) = 9.06$, which corresponds to 1.4 times solar.

A somewhat vexing problem is what the uncertainties in the determined oxygen abundance for the region is. Edmunds & Pagel (1984) quote an uncertainty in the calibrations of the line ratios of ± 0.2 dex. The signal to noise ratios given

Figure 7.6. Branch discriminate diagram for extragalactic HII regions. High metal branch objects are plotted as diamonds, while low branch objects are plotted as squares. The value for the NGC 3312 filament is plotted as a filled circle.

in Table 7.1 give some idea about the internal uncertainties of the line parameters; however external uncertainties are not so well constrained. In particular the uncertainties in the flux calibration, dereddening, sky subtraction, continuum estimation, and line deblending are more difficult to quantify.

7.3.2 Expected Abundance

What should the abundance of the filament gas be? The answer to this question depends in a large part on where in NGC 3312 the gas originated. In general, HII regions in spiral galaxies exhibit abundances that depend on their position in the galaxy, with abundances generally dropping with increasing distance from the center of the galaxy. Thus if the filament represents gas from outer parts of NGC 3312 we would expect a relatively low abundance, while if the gas is material that has been stripped from the inner parts of the galaxy, we would expect a fairly high abundance. The dependence of oxygen abundance on surface brightness for spiral galaxies has been quantified by Ryder (1995), who uses surface photometry and abundance measurements for 5 galaxies to derive an empirical relation between oxygen abundance and azimuthally averaged I band surface brightness. I have converted his relation from I to R band using Ryder & Dopita's (1994) V and I band surface photometry, along with a fit of the relation between (V-R) and (V-I) colors for galaxies (Buta & Williams 1995), giving

$$12 + \log(O/H) = 10.95(\pm 0.90) - 0.095(\pm 0.034)\mu_R \quad (7.1)$$

where μ_R is the R band surface brightness in magnitudes per square arcsecond.

Using a photometrically calibrated image of NGC 3312 obtained at the Lowell observatory, equation 7.1 can be used along with the surface brightness at the radius of the observed region to predict an expected oxygen abundance for material in that part of the galaxy. Doing this gives a surface brightness of $\mu_R \approx 26.5$ magnitudes per square arcsecond. This value of the surface brightness gives a

oxygen abundance of $12 + \log(O/H) \approx 8.43$. Although the scatter of Ryder's (1995) data around his mean relation was moderate, none of the HII regions considered in Ryder's paper with surface brightnesses fainter than $\mu_R \approx 24.5$ have $12 + \log(O/H) \leq 9.0$.

A possible explanation for the origin of the line emitting region is that it is not actually physically associated with NGC 3312, but is instead a dwarf galaxy in the cluster superimposed along the line of sight. In order to examine this idea, the relation between absolute blue magnitude and oxygen abundance found by Skillman, Kennicutt, & Hodge (1989) was employed to calculate the expected abundance of a dwarf galaxy of similar luminosity to the condensation. The observed R band magnitude using the Lowell image is $R \approx 20.75$. Since the filament is very blue in color, the blue magnitude was estimated using $B - R$ colors in the range 0.25-0.75, which gives absolute blue magnitudes in the range -13.5 to -14.0 at the distance of Abell 1060. Using this range of blue magnitude in Skillman et al. (1989) gives a predicted abundance of $12 + \log(O/H) = 7.5 - 7.6$, much lower than that observed.

These results suggest that the material does not originate at the observed position, but instead comes from somewhere deeper in NGC 3312. Using equation 7.1 to predict the mean surface brightness at which material with the observed abundance would originate gives $\mu_R \approx 19.9$, which would suggest an origin within the inner 1-2 kpc of the galaxies disk. Given the scatter in Ryder's observed relation, the above value should probably not be interpreted too literally. However it does seem likely that the material in the filament originates from somewhere in the inner disk of NGC 3312, and not from its present observed position.

7.4 Summary

Spectrophotometry for a filament in the outer part of the cluster spiral NGC 3312 is presented. The observed strengths of [OIII] and [NII] lines lead to an abundance estimate for the galaxy of $12 + \log(O/H) = 9.06$ (1.4 times solar). This abundance is much higher than would reasonably be expected if the gas originated either in the disk of NGC 3312 at its observed radius, or if the condensation were actually a dwarf galaxy. This suggests that the material in the observed filament originated somewhere deeper in the disk of NGC 3312, and has been transported outward, possibly by ram pressure as the galaxy moves through the ICM of Abell 1060. Although ram pressure seems like the most likely mechanism for moving the gas outward, a note of caution is in order in interpreting the overall appearance of NGC 3312 as being due to ram pressure effects. In a study of two galaxies that were considered to be excellent candidates for global ram pressure sweeping, Davis, Keel, Mulchaey, & Henning (1997) find that a more likely explanation for these galaxies whose morphology resembles that of NGC 3312 is tidal interactions with other galaxies. This is the same conclusion reached by McMahon et al. (1992) for NGC 3312 based on its HI properties. Davis et al. (1997) also conclude that some of the less prominent features of NGC 1961 and NGC 2276 may be due to ram pressure, whose efficiency is enhanced due to the tidal interactions, which may make galaxies more vulnerable to gas dynamical effects. Perhaps the ultimate explanation for the properties of NGC 3312 may be similar.

8 Conclusions

This dissertation had three purposes:

1. To determine whether there exists a population of cluster galaxies that has either a deficit or excess of current star formation compared to comparable field galaxies.
2. To examine the connection between any such population and the presence of significant substructure in the clusters that the galaxies reside.
3. To use the spatial distribution of star formation within galaxies to help constrain what environmental mechanisms are currently acting upon the galaxies.

Not surprisingly given the somewhat ambitious scope of what was undertaken, these goals have not been completely met, but progress has been made in each of the above areas.

This work has found evidence for populations of galaxies with both deficits and excesses of $H\alpha$ emission in nearby clusters, some of which had been noted before by other workers (Kennicutt 1983a; Gavazzi et al. 1991). The survey of the Hercules cluster presented here shows a population of early type galaxies with modest $H\alpha$ excesses.

The evidence for a connection between these deficits and excesses and substructures is less clear. Analysis of the postage stamp survey data for nearby clusters shows evidence that $H\alpha$ deficit galaxies are more likely to be in dynamically relaxed clusters, and $H\alpha$ excess galaxies are more common in less dynamically relaxed clusters. The evidence from the Hercules cluster shows that there

is no preference for the $H\alpha$ excess systems in the cluster to be associated with a particular subcluster. This either means that the subcluster environment is not important in stimulating the observed $H\alpha$ excesses, or that the Hercules cluster is dominated by sub-clusters, and thus most parts of the cluster have associated $H\alpha$ excess systems.

The question of environmental triggering has also not been conclusively addressed in this work. First, it is possible that the observed population of $H\alpha$ excess galaxies are not the result of interaction with the cluster environment, but may instead represent a manifestation that occurs in galaxies, regardless of their environment. While I do not believe this is the case, only a complete sample of field $S0$'s can decide conclusively whether this is the case or not. Assuming that there is environmental stimulation of the $H\alpha$ excess galaxies, the current data gives some constraint upon its nature, but is unable to pinpoint a single mechanism as being responsible. Strong galaxy-galaxy interactions seem an unlikely mechanism, because most of the $H\alpha$ excess galaxies show little sign of tidal damage. Ram pressure enhancement also seems unlikely, because most of the $H\alpha$ excess galaxies show central enhancements to their emission rather than disk-wide star formation, and because most of the $H\alpha$ excess galaxies are in parts of the cluster where the ICM density seems to be very low. The mechanism of high speed galaxy encounters sometimes referred to as galaxy harassment is also unlikely, since the fact the galaxies are probably falling into the cluster for the first time means that most galaxies have not yet spent enough time in the cluster environment to be harassed. Tidal triggering by the cluster potential has the advantage of distorting galaxies symmetrically, and thus leaving more subtle signs on the structure of the galaxy. However the range over which this mechanism should be effective in the Hercules cluster is much smaller in extent than the distribution of the $H\alpha$ excess galaxies, suggesting that cluster tides are not responsible for the $H\alpha$ excess galaxies. This means that the most likely environmental agent is minor galaxy interactions or

mergers, which would leave the affected galaxy relatively undamaged. Unfortunately, the major point in the favor of minor interactions or mergers is not that the process is observed to be happening, but that the signs that it is happening are very difficult to detect.

8.1 Future Work

Fortunately, the inability to answer all the questions put forth at the beginning of this dissertation leaves substantial room for further investigation. In the Hercules cluster, optical spectroscopy of the $H\alpha$ excess galaxies for which spectra have not already been obtained would be useful in determining more about the physical state of the star forming regions of these galaxies. Determination of the HI properties of the galaxies, either from the VLA survey of Dickey (1997), or from further VLA or Arecibo observations would help constrain the neutral gas content and kinematics of these systems.

Beyond the Hercules cluster, similar surveys of clusters carefully selected to span a range of substructures would help decide how unique the $H\alpha$ excess galaxies observed in Hercules really are. Finally, a complete $H\alpha$ field survey, which included significant numbers of S0 galaxies would show how common galaxies like those observed in the Hercules cluster are in the general galaxy population.

References

- Abell, G. O. 1958, *ApJS*, 3, 211
- Abraham, R. G., Valdes, F., Yee, H. K. C., & Van Den Bergh, S. 1994, *ApJ*, 432, 75
- Albert, C. E., White, R. A. & Morgan, W. W. 1977 *ApJ*, 211, 309 (AWM)
- Alloin, D., Collin-Souffrin, S., Joly, M., & Vigroux, L. 1979, *A&A*, 78, 200
- Andersen, V. 1992, M.S. Thesis, New Mexico Institute of Mining and Technology
- Andersen, V. & Owen, F. N. 1994, *AJ*, 108, 361
- Andersen, V. & Owen, F. N. 1995, *AJ*, 109, 1582
- Arp, H. C. & Modore, B. F. 1987, *A Catalog of Southern Peculiar Galaxies and Associations* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press)
- Beers, T. C., Forman, W., Huchra, J. P., Jones, C., & Gebhardt, K. 1991, *AJ*, 107, 1581
- Beichman, C. A., Neugebauer, G., Habing, H. J., Clegg, P. E. & Chester, T. J. eds. 1988, *Infrared Astronomical Satellite (IRAS) Catalogs and Atlases, Volume 1; Explanatory Supplement*, NASA, Washington DC
- Binggeli, B., Popescu, C. C., & Tammann, G. A. 1993, *A&ASS*, 98, 275
- Binggeli, B., Tammann, G. A., & Sandage, A. 1987, *AJ*, 94, 251
- Bird, C. 1994, *AJ*, 107, 1637
- Bird, C. M., Davis, D. S. & Beers, T. C. 1995, *AJ*, 109, 920
- Böhringer, H., Briel, U. G., Schwarz, R. A., Voges, W., Hartner, G., & Trümper, J. 1994, *Nature*, 368, 828
- Bothun, G. D. & Dressler, A. 1986, *ApJ*, 301, 57
- Bothun, G., Impey, C., McGaugh, S. 1997, *PASP*, 109, 745
- Bothun, G. D., Stauffer, J. R., & Schommer, R. A. 1981, *ApJ*, 247, 42
- Bothun, G. D. & Schommer, R. A. 1982, *AJ*, 87, 1368

- Bower, R. G., Lucey, J. R., & Ellis, R. S. 1992, MNRAS, 254, 601
- Buote, D. A. & Tsai, J. C. 1995, ApJ, 452, 522
- Buote, D. A. & Tsai, J. C. 1996, ApJ, 458, 27
- Burns, J. O., Roettiger, K., Ledlow, M., & Klypin, A. 1994, ApJ, 427, L87
- Burstein, D. & Heiles, C. 1984, ApJS, 54, 33
- Bushouse, H. A. 1987, ApJ, 320, 29
- Buta, R. J. & Corwin, H. G. 1986, ApJS, 62, 255
- Buta, R. & Crocker, D. A. 1992, AJ, 103, 1804
- Buta, R. & Williams, K. L. 1995, AJ, 109, 543
- Butcher, H. & Oemler, A. 1984, ApJ, 285, 426
- Butcher, H. & Oemler, A. 1985, ApJS, 57, 665
- Byrd, G. & Valtonen, M. 1990, ApJ, 350, 89
- Caldwell, N. & Rose, J. A. 1997, AJ, 113, 492
- Caldwell, N., Rose, J. A., Franx, M., & Leonardi, A. J. 1996, AJ, 111, 78
- Caldwell, N., Rose, J. A., Sharples, R. M., Ellis, R. S., & Bower, R. G. 1993, AJ, 106, 473
- Cayette, V., Kotanyi, C., Balkowski, C., & Van Gorkom, J. H. 1994, AJ, 107, 1003
- Christian, C.A., Adams, M., Barnes, J. V., Butcher, H., Hayes, D. S., Mould, J. R., & Siegel, M. 1985, PASP, 97, 383
- Coleman, G.D., Wu, C., & Weedman, D. W. 1980, ApJS, 43, 393
- Condon, J. J. 1992, ARA&A, 30, 575
- Couch, W. J., Ellis, R. S., Sharples, R. M. & Smail, I. M. 1994, ApJ, 430, 121
- Couch, W. & Sharples, R. M. 1987, MNRAS, 229, 423
- Cowie, L. L., Songaila, A. A., & Hu, E. M. 1991, Nature, 354, 460

- Davis, D. S., Keel, W. C., Mulchaey, J. S., & Henning, P. A. 1997, *AJ*, 114, 613
- De Blok, W. J. G., McGaugh, S. S., & Van Der Hulst, J. M. 1996, *MNRAS*, 283, 18
- De Jong, R. S. 1995, PhD Dissertation, University of Gronigen
- Dickey, J. M. 1997, *AJ*, 113, 1939
- Dickey, J. M. & Salpeter, E. E. 1984, *ApJ*, 284, 461
- Doi, M., Fukugita, M. & Okamura, S. 1993, *MNRAS*, 264, 832
- Dopita, M. A. & Evans, I. N. 1986, *ApJ*, 307, 431
- Dopita, M. A. & Ryder, S. D. 1994, *ApJ*, 430, 163
- Dressler, A. 1980a, *ApJ*, 236, 351
- Dressler, A. 1980b, *ApJS*, 42, 565
- Dressler, A. & Gunn, J. E. 1983, *ApJ*, 270, 7
- Dressler, A. & Gunn J. E. 1992, *ApJS*, 78, 1
- Dressler, A., Oemler, A., Butcher, H. R., & Gunn, J. E. 1994, *ApJ*, 430, 107
- Dreyer, J. L. E. 1888, *Mem. R.A.S.*, 49, 1
- Dreyer, J. L. E. 1895, *Mem. R.A.S.*, 51, 185
- Dreyer, J. L. E. 1908, *Mem. R.A.S.*, 59, 105
- Drinkwater, M. J., Gregg, M. D., & Smith, R. M. 1998, Preprint
- Dufour, R. J., Garnett, D. R., & Shields, G. A. 1988, *ApJ*, 332, 752
- Edmunds, M. G. & Pagel, B. E. J. 1984, *MNRAS*, 211, 507
- Elmegreen, B. G. 1997, *Rev. Mexicana Astron. Astrofis. Conf. Ser.* 6, 165
- Evrard, A. E. 1991, *MNRAS*, 248, 8p
- Fitchett, M. & Merritt, D. 1988, *ApJ*, 335, 18
- Frei, Z., Guhathakurta, P., Gunn, J. E., & Tyson, J. A. 1996, *AJ*, 111, 174

- Gallagher, J. S. 1978, *ApJ*, 223, 386
- Garnett, D. R. & Kennicutt, R. C. 1994, *ApJ*, 426, 123
- Gavazzi, G., Boselli, A. & Kennicutt, R. 1991, *AJ*, 101, 1207
- Gavazzi, G., Randone, I., & Branchini, E. 1995, *ApJ*, 438, 590
- Giovanelli, R. & Haynes, M. P. 1985, *ApJ*, 292, 404
- Gisler, G. R. 1980, *AJ*, 85, 623
- Gunn, J. E. & Gott, J. R. 1972, *ApJ*, 176, 1
- Guzman, R., Gallego, J., Koo, D. C., Phillips, A. C., Lowenthal, J. D., Faber, S. M., Illingworth, G. D., & Vogt, N. P. 1997, *ApJ*, 489, 559
- Harris, D. E., Forman, W., Gioia, I. M., Hale, J. A., Harnden Jr., F. R., Jones, C., Karakashian, T., Maccacaro, T., McSweeney, J. D., Primini, F. A., Schwarz, J., Tananbaum, H. D., & Thurman, J. 1993, *The EINSTEIN Observatory Catalog of IPC X-ray Sources (NASA)*
- Heckman, T. M. 1990, in *Paired and Interacting Galaxies*, J. W. Sulentic, W. C. Keel, & C. M. Telesco (Washington: NASA Conference Publication CP-3098), 359
- Helou, G., soifer, B. T., & Rowan-Robinson, M. 1985, *ApJ*, 298, L7
- Henriksen, M. J. & Byrd, G. 1996, *ApJ*, 459, 82
- Henriksen, M. J. & Markevitch, M. L. 1996, *ApJ*, 466, 79
- Hibbard, J. E. & Van Gorkom, J. H. 1996, *AJ*111, 655
- Huang, Z. & Sarazin, C. L. 1996, *ApJ*, 461, 622
- Hubble, E. 1926, *ApJ*, 64, 321
- Hubble, E. 1936, *The Realm of the Nebula* (Yale University Press)
- Jacoby, G. H., Quigley, R. J., & Africano, J. L. 1987, *PASP*99, 672
- Keel, W. C. 1983, *ApJ*, 269, 466

- Keel, W. C., Kennicutt, R. C., Hummel, E., & Van der Hulst, J. M. 1985, *AJ*, 90, 708
- Keel, W. C. & Van Soest, E. T. M. 1992, *A&ASS*, 94, 553
- Kennicutt, R. C. 1983a, *AJ*, 88, 483
- Kennicutt, R. C. 1983b, *ApJ*, 272, 54
- Kennicutt, R. C. 1989, *ApJ*, 344, 685
- Kennicutt, R. C., Bothun, G. D., & Schommer, R. A. 1984, *AJ*, 89, 1279
- Kennicutt, R. C., Keel, W. C., Van Der Hulst, J. M., Hummel, E., & Roettiger, K. A. 1987, *AJ*, 93, 1011
- Kennicutt, R. C., & Kent, S. M. 1983, *AJ*, 88, 1094
- Kennicutt, R. C., Tamblyn, P., & Congdon, C. W. 1994, *ApJ*, 435, 22
- Koopmann, R. A. 1997, PhD Dissertation, Yale University
- Kunth, D. & Sargent, W. L. 1983, *ApJ*, 273, 81
- Landolt, A. U. 1983, *AJ*, 88, 439
- Landolt, A. U. 1992, *AJ*, 104, 340
- Markarian, B. E., Lipovetsky, V. A., Stepanian, D. A., Erastova, L. K., & Shapvalova, A. I. 1989, *Soob. Spets. Astrofiz. Obs.* No. 62
- Massey, P., Strobel, K., Barnes, J. V., & Anderson, E. 1988, *ApJ*, 328, 315
- McCall, M. L., Rybski, P. M., & Shields, G. A. 1985, *ApJS*, 57, 1
- McGaugh, S. S. 1991, *ApJ*, 380, 140
- McMahon, P. M., Richter, O. G., Van Gorkom, J. H., & Ferguson, H. C. 1992, *AJ*, 103, 399
- McMillan, S. L. W., Kolwaski, M. P., & Ulmer, M. P., 1989, *ApJS*, 70, 699
- Merrit, D. 1983, *ApJ*, 264, 24
- Mohr, J. J., Fabricant D. G., & Geller, M. J. 1993, *ApJ*, 413, 492

- Moore, B., Katz, N., & Lake, G. 1997, preprint
- Moore, B., Katz, N., Lake, G., Dressler, A., & Oemler, A. 1996, *Nature*, 379, 613
- Morgan, W. W. 1958, *PASP*, 70, 364
- Moss, C. & Whittle, M. 1993, *ApJ*, 407, L17
- Naim, A., Lahav, O., Buta, R. J., Corwin Jr., H. G., de Vaucouleurs, G., Dressler, A., Huchra, J. P., van den Bergh, S., Raychaudhury, S., Sodre Jr., L. & Storrie-Lombardi, M. C. 1995, *MNRAS*, 274, 1107
- Newberry, M. V. 1991, *PASP* 103, 122
- Nilson, P. 1973, *Uppsala General Catalog of Galaxies*, (Uppsala: Royal Society of Science Uppsala)
- Nussbaumer, H., & Storey, P. J. 1981, *A&A*, 99, 177
- Odewahn, S. C., Stockwell, E. B., Pennington, R. L., Humphreys, R. M., and Zumach, W. 1992, *AJ*, 103, 318
- O'Neil, K., Bothun, G. D., & Cornell, M. E. 1997a, *AJ*, 113, 1212
- O'Neil, K., Bothun, G. D., Schombert, J., Cornell, M. E., & Impey, C. D. 1997b, *AJ*, 114, 2448
- Osterbrock, D. E. 1989, *Astrophysics of Gaseous Nebulae and Active Galactic Nuclei* (Mill Valley, CA: University Science Books)
- Owen, F. N., Dwarkanath, K. S., Smith, C. C., Ledlow, M. J., Keel, W. C., Morrison, G. E., Voges, W., & Burns, J. O. 1996, in *Energy Transport in Radio Galaxies and Quasars*, P.E. Hardee, A.H. Bridle, & J.A. Zensus eds., (San Francisco, CA; Astronomical Society of the Pacific), 353
- Paturel, G., Fouque, P., Bottinelli, L., & Gouguenheim, L. 1989, *Catalogue of Principle Galaxies* (Lyon: Obs. de Lyon)
- Pennington, R. L., Humphreys, R. M., Odewahn, S. C., Zumach, W., & Thurmes, P. M 1993, *PASP*, 105, 521
- Phillips, A. C., Guzman, R., Gallego, J., Koo, D. C., Lowenthal, J. D., Vogt, N. P., Faber, S. M., & Illingworth, G. D. 1997, *ApJ*, 489, 543

- Pilachowski, C., Landolt, A., Massey, P., & Montani, J. 1991, *NOAO Newsletter*, 28, 26
- Pogge, R. W. & Eskridge, P. B. 1993, *AJ*, 106, 1405
- Quirk, W. J. 1972, *ApJ*, 176, L9
- Reike, G. H. & Lebofsky, M. J. 1985, *ApJ*, 288, 618
- Richstone, D. O. 1975, *ApJ*, 200, 535
- Romanishin, W. 1990, *AJ*, 100, 373
- Ryder, S. D. 1993, Ph.D. Thesis, Australia National University
- Ryder, S. D. 1995, *ApJ*, 444, 610
- Ryder, S. D. & Dopita, M. A. 1993, *ApJS*, 88, 415
- Ryder, S. D. & Dopita, M. A. 1994, *ApJ*, 430, 142
- Salzer, J. J., Alighieri, S. D. S., Matteucci, F., Giovanelli, R., & Haynes, M. P. 1991, *AJ*, 101, 1258
- Salzer, J. J., MacAlpine, G. M., & Boroson, T. A. 1989a, *ApJS*, 70, 447
- Salzer, J. J., MacAlpine, G. M., & Boroson, T. A. 1989b, *ApJS*, 70, 479
- Sandage, A. 1961, *The Hubble Atlas of Galaxies* (Carnegie Institution of Washington)
- Sandage, A., Binggeli, B., & Tammann, G. A. 1985, *AJ*, 90, 1759
- Sandage, A., & Visvanathan, N. 1978, *ApJ*, 225, 742
- Sarazin, C. L. 1988, *X-ray Emissions from Clusters of Galaxies*, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, UK
- Silk, J. 1997, *ApJ*, 481, 702
- Smith, M. G. & Weedman, D. W. 1976, *ApJ*, 205, 709
- Snowden, S. L., Plucinsky, P. P., Briel, U., Hasinger, G., & Pfeffermann, E. 1992, *ApJ*, 393, 819

- Skillman, E. D., Kennicutt, R. C., & Hodge, P. W. 1989, *ApJ*, 347, 875
- Taylor, C. L., Brinks, E., Grashius, R. M., & Skillman, E. D. 1995, *ApJS*, 99, 427
- Telles, E. & Terlevich, R. 1995, *MNRAS*, 275, 1
- Torres-Peimbert, S., Peimbert, M., & Fierro, J. 1989, *ApJ*, 345, 186
- Tully, R. B., & Shaya, E. J. 1984, *ApJ*, 281, 31
- Valluri, M. 1993, *ApJ*, 408, 57
- Van den Bergh, S. 1976, *ApJ*, 206, 883
- Van Dokkum, P. G., Franx, M., Kelson, D. D., Illingworth, G. D., Fisher, D. & Fabricant, D. 1998, preprint
- de Vaucouleurs, G. 1959, *Handbuch der Physik*, 53, 275
- de Vaucouleurs, G., de Vaucouleurs, A., Corwin, H. G., Buta, R. J., Paturel, G., & Fouqué, P. 1991, *Third Reference Catalog of Bright Galaxies*, Springer-Verlag, New York (RC3)
- Veilleux, S. & Osterbrock, D. E. 1987, *ApJS*, 63, 2
- Veron, P., Goncalves, A. C., & Voren-Cetty, M. P. 1997, *A&A*, 319, 52
- Vorontsov-Velyaminov, B. A., Archipova, V. P., & Krasnogorskaja, A. A. 1974, *Morphological Catalogue of Galaxies* (Moscow: Moscow State University)
- Walker, I. R., Mihos, C. J., & Hernquist, L. 1996, *ApJ*, 460, 121
- Wang, Q. D. & Ulmer, M. P. 1997, *MNRAS*, 292, 920
- Wyse, R. F. G. 1986, *ApJ*, 311, L41
- Wyse, R. F. G. & Silk, J. 1989, *ApJ*, 339, 700
- Zaritsky, D., Kennicutt, R. C., & Huchra, J. P. 1994, *ApJ*, 420, 87
- Zabludoff, A. I., Huchra, J. P., & Geller, M. J. 1990, *ApJS*, 74, 1
- Zabludoff, A. I., & Zaritsky, D. 1995, *ApJ*, 447, 21
- Zhao, J. H., Burns, J. O., & Owen, F. N. 1989, *AJ*, 98, 64

Zwicky, F. 1971, Catalogue of Selected Compact and Post Eruptive Galaxies (Guemlingen)

Zwicky, F., Herzog, E., Karpowicz, M., Kowal, C. T., Wild, P. 1968, Catalog of Galaxies and Clusters of Galaxies (Pasadena: California Institute of Technology)